

**Ayrshire Herstories:
Reconfiguring specific South Ayrshire heritage sites
through feminist performance practice**

Victoria Bianchi

**Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of the
West of Scotland for the award of Doctor of Philosophy.**

February 2018

Abstract

This thesis employs Doreen Massey's conceptualisation of gendered space in order to explore the ways in which the unrepresented narratives of women in heritage sites can be promoted through site-specific performance practice. Focussing on three specific South Ayrshire sites of heritage, The Robert Burns Birthplace Museum, Rozelle House and Ayr beachfront, the aim of this study was to extrapolate principles of feminist performance practice that can be used to respond to the lack of women's stories, termed *Herstory*, in such sites. Implementing a practice-as-research (PaR) methodology, three new performances were developed from the research findings and presented on site between February 2015 and May 2017. These performance works comprise half of this thesis, and can be understood as a practical enactment of the theoretical and Herstorical research carried out throughout the study. This thesis draws from discourses surrounding women and heritage, site-specific performance and spatial theory.

The findings of this research are primarily drawn from the three performances developed: *CauseWay: The Story of the Alloway Suffragettes* (October, 2015), *In Hidden Spaces: The Untold Stories of the Women of Rozelle House* (June, 2016) and *Souvenir* (May, 2017). These performances and the data collected from these works were each theorised in a critically reflective written exegesis that comprises the other half of this thesis. The combination of practice and theory serves to interrogate the efficacy of performance practice in representing marginalised narratives of women, while simultaneously exploring how audiences' and performers' conceptualisations of space can be altered through such work. This thesis highlights the importance of time in engaging with heritage sites, in addition to offering three key principles for developing feminist heritage performance: the incorporation of mobility; flexible characterisation; and the prioritisation of care.

Contents

Acknowledgements	5
Author's Declaration	6
1. Introduction	7
1.1 Overview	7
1.2 Ayrshire Herstories: a summary	8
1.3 Feminism and Herstory	9
1.4 Alloway	10
1.5 In Hidden Spaces and Souvenir	16
1.6 Gendered spaces	19
1.7 Gender and the heritage site	21
2. Literature Review	26
2.1 Introduction	26
2.2 Spatial theory	27
2.3 Heritage sites	33
2.4 Site-specific performance	40
2.5 Conclusion	44
3. Methodology	46
3.1 Introduction	46
3.2 Practice, thesis and exegesis	46
3.3 Practice-as-research	48
3.4 Analysis, exegesis and bricolage	53
4. CauseWay: The Story of the Alloway Suffragettes	61
4.1 Introduction	61
4.2 Performance summary	62
4.3 Mobility and CauseWay	64

4.4 Herstorical (in)accuracy	73
4.5 Gender and site	80
4.6 Conclusion	87
5. In Hidden Spaces: The untold stories of the women of Rozelle House	88
5.1 Introduction	88
5.2 Performance summary	89
5.3 On Hierarchy, Collaboration and Care	95
5.4 Im/Mobility and the Artistic Collective	102
5.5 Characterising the site	108
5.6 Conclusion	117
6. Souvenir	118
6.1 Introduction	118
6.2 Performance summary	120
6.3 Nature, heritage and performance	123
6.4 Mobility: wind and waves	132
6.5 Revisiting care	140
6.6 Conclusion	150
7. Conclusion	151
7.1 Introduction	151
7.2 Visitors, performers and the socio-spatial dialectic	152
7.3 Feminism and heritage sites	156
7.4 Feminist principles for heritage performance	160
7.5 Final thoughts: space and time	165
8. Appendices	167
9. References	230

Acknowledgements

To my friends and colleagues that I haven't mentioned by name here but who have contributed to this work in so many diverse ways, thank you.

To Joan and Laura at South Ayrshire Council. Thank you for believing in my work and supporting it over the past three years.

To staff at the Robert Burns Birthplace Museum, Rozelle House and The Gaiety. Thank you for letting me take over your space and for your interest in my work.

To my supervisors Rowena and Susan. Thank you for your insight and your support throughout this study.

To Anne. Thank you for your attention to detail, for your time and for your dedication to my work. It has all been invaluable to me.

To Jamie and Mark. Thank you for the music.

To Poppy, Annaliese, Pamela, Rebecca, Kirsty and Teri. Thank you for your creativity, your commitment and your friendship. You have shaped this thesis immeasurably.

To Vicki. Thank you for being my library support system and for making this seem achievable.

To my family. Thank you for being at every performance and for listening to me talk about feminist heritage performance even when you weren't sure exactly what I meant by it.

To David. Thank you for convincing me to do this, for being a part of it and for always believing in me.

To Iona. Thank you for your love and for being a distraction.

Thank you all for making this possible.

Author's Declaration

This thesis has not been previously submitted for another Ph.D. or comparable award.

Word count (excluding ancillary data, reference lists, appendices) – 48,795.

Victoria Bianchi

1. Introduction

1.1 Overview

Ayrshire Herstories was a practice-as-research (PaR) project, supported by University of the West of Scotland and the South Ayrshire Place Partnership, which involved the creation of new performances for heritage sites in the area. The project was supervised by Dr Anne Pirrie as Director of Studies, and by Professor Rowena Murray and Dr Susan Henderson as second and third supervisors respectively. These performances created were intended to investigate and portray the un/underrepresented narratives of women as they related to three specific sites: The Robert Burns Birthplace Museum (RBBM), Rozelle House and Ayr Beachfront. This thesis offers a reflection upon and analysis of the three performances created throughout the Ayrshire Herstories study. The performances, *CauseWay: The Story of the Alloway Suffragettes*, *In Hidden Spaces* and *Souvenir*, were created for the three heritage sites in South Ayrshire, and were performed at their respective sites over the course of 2015-2017. This chapter introduces the project and the theoretical frameworks employed in the study.

This chapter begins with a thesis summary, including the research questions for the project and a description of each subsequent chapter. The first performance work, *CauseWay*, and the story behind it, can be understood as a stimulus for the entire study. Therefore, section 1.4 introduces the village of Alloway where the performance, and the events that inspired it, took place. This is followed by a brief overview of the second and third performances, *In Hidden Spaces* and *Souvenir*. The next subsection expands upon the discussion of gender and space. Particular focus is given to the features, both physical and perceptual, that impact upon how individuals conceptualise space. The final section of

this chapter introduces debates surrounding the representation of gender within heritage sites and outlines the rationale for this study.

1.2 Ayrshire Herstories: a summary

As is common within the PaR methodology, the performance works created constitute half of this thesis (Haseman, 2007). The full scripts for each performance can be found in the Appendices section. This document, then, can be understood as a written exegesis that comprises the other half of my work. For the benefit of the reader, this document will be referred to as a thesis throughout, with the performances being referred to as such. The study was structured around four research questions, which were:

- How does feminist performance practice impact upon visitors' and performers' interactions with heritage sites?
- To what extent can feminist performance practice reconfigure the androcentric nature of heritage sites?
- In what ways can feminist principles be enacted to create performance that can be termed both site-specific and feminist?
- Which aspects of or strategies for creating site-specific performance practice are particularly relevant to a feminist process?

The aim of these questions was to draw together both the theoretical and practical concerns of my research, and to direct the study towards specific aspects of heritage performance. These questions were developed in order to contribute to a framework for feminist performance in heritage sites, by exploring the experiences of the individuals involved and the strategies used to develop such work.

Following this introductory chapter, Chapter 2 is comprised of a review of relevant literature in the fields of human geography, heritage studies and performance studies. This

is followed by a discussion of the methodology of the study in Chapter 3. In Chapters 4 to 6 each of the performances will be discussed in turn, before a discussion of the conclusions drawn from this study in Chapter 7. In the chapters on the performances I explore how each work was developed in response to the questions above, the theoretical frameworks that informed the performances, and how each work was interpreted by both the audience and performers involved. The locations for the performances themselves were as follows:

- *CauseWay* – The Robert Burns Birthplace Museum, Alloway
- *In Hidden Spaces* – Rozelle House, Ayr
- *Souvenir* – Ayr Beachfront, Ayr

While each of the performance locations were central to this study, it is the Robert Burns Birthplace Museum (RBBM) in the village of Alloway that can be understood as the primary catalyst. More specifically, the story, shared with me in 2014, of two notable women whose narrative currently has no presence within the museum. As this story marked the beginning of my research into women and heritage sites, the following section discusses the rationale for this project by way of introducing Alloway, the RBBM and the *CauseWay* project.

1.3 Feminism and Herstory

The word 'feminist' is employed throughout this thesis, and I wish to take a moment here to note the development, and sometimes conflicting nature, of the term. Feminism is generally discussed as occurring in 'waves', with Western society currently conceptualised as existing within fourth-wave feminism (Cochrane, 2013). Much like the overarching theoretical framework of this thesis, which draws upon a number of discourses surrounding gender, space, performance and heritage, a variety of feminist scholars and ideas have informed this thesis. *CauseWay*, set during the suffragette movement, was

theoretically informed by first-wave feminism; in particular I note arguments on mobility posited by Susan B. Anthony (see Chapter 4). The work of Greer (1970), a radical feminist, is employed alongside that of Noddings (1984), an advocate of the relationship between feminism and care. Theorists exploring questions of feminist embodiment are combined with those prioritising the relationship between women and space; indeed, many of the works cited are aligned with ideas of post-structural feminism (Braidotti, 1994; Rose, 1999, Massey, 1994). This thesis is, therefore, not rooted in one specific wave or ideology, but draws upon a variety of feminisms that have occurred during the lives of the women I have researched and portrayed. The primary aim of this study was to and locates women's stories as its central concern (see Austin, 1990).

In relation to women's stories, my research is concerned specifically with women's history which is henceforth referred to as Herstory throughout this thesis. The term was originally used by Morgan (1970)¹ and was subsequently defined by Miller and Swift thus:

When women in the movement use herstory, their purpose is to emphasise that women's lives, deeds, and participation in human affairs have been neglected or undervalued in standard histories
(1976:135)

I employ the term Herstory to refer to historical narratives of women, History for historical narratives of men and history as a gender neutral term (as it is popularly understood).

1.4 Alloway

The village of Alloway in South Ayrshire is the birthplace of – and shrine to – Robert Burns. As it is impossible to reach by rail, you will most likely enter the village via signposts enticing you towards the Robert Burns Birthplace Museum. This £21million building is dedicated to all things related to Burns, and was opened to the public in 2011 (Hopes,

¹ Morgan adapted the acronym of the feminist organisation W.I.T.C.H. (Women's International Terrorist Conspiracy from Hell) to stand for Women Inspired To Commit Herstory.

2015). Approaching the village from the opposite end will take you directly alongside the cottage where Scotland's Bard was born in 1759. As the only thatched cottage in the main street, it is impossible to miss. Across from the cottage is Poet's Corner, a delightful cafe where toasted sandwiches are served at a pace that befits a sleepy, quasi-rural Scottish village. Further down the road is Brig O'Doon House Hotel, the interior of which is covered with images and characters from the work of Burns. Both the Brig O'Doon itself and the ruin of Alloway Auld Kirk, both made famous by Burns' epic *Tam O'Shanter*, are still standing in the village. The Auld Kirk, in fact, is often the focus of guided tours and is illuminated by evening light displays. Combine all of this with the Burns Monument and Gardens; a lane featuring art work inspired by his poetry named Poet's Path; and street names such as Auld Nick's View and Shanter Way (again, both references to the poem) and the pervasive influence Burns-based touristic topography has over this small community becomes abundantly clear.

Undoubtedly the tone I have adopted here is far from detached. My aim is not to denigrate the choices made by the various regional and national organisations that have shaped Alloway. It is self-evident that such a small area would choose to draw attention to the fact that it produced Scotland's most famous poet. My concern is for the stories that cannot be heard over the dominating drone of Robert Burns' scandalous love affairs and the emblematic echoes of *To a Haggis*. Specifically the stories of women, the gender that inspired so many of Burns' works, have been sidelined in the heritage sites of Alloway. Burns' lovers are symbolised through items that reinforce the stereotypes of women found throughout the heritage industry. Below is one example of this, noted in my interview with a member of RBBM staff:

Agnes Broun is Burns' mother (...) her milking stool is there next to the father's chair. So you have this interesting hierarchy; you have quite a high chair, which is the father's chair, and you have this low milking stool (...) it's an interesting

semiotic, really, that you've got a lowly chair for a woman and a high chair for a man.

(Participant IRB1, interview on 12/10/15)

In the interview, Participant IRB1 also discussed how some of Burns' lovers were portrayed through love letters or, in one instance, coins used to pay off a woman that he impregnated. While some of these curatorial decisions are due to availability of artefacts, the focus upon one famous man, and the reduction of women to lovers or caregivers, elevates men and maleness above Herstory in the gender hierarchy of the RBBM. This hierarchy does not exist separately from the village of Alloway, but diffuses into wider perceptions of gender and identity (Smith, 2008). Alloway can be understood as a microcosm of the wider heritage landscape of South Ayrshire, and of the industry-at-large. The RBBM and, in turn, Alloway, are both 'irreducibly gendered' due to the individuals and values represented (Urry, 1995: 26). I employ Alloway as an allegory for the gendering of space and the heritage industry on a grander scale.

Gender, Alloway and Burns

The coding of any space as gendered is by no means exact or concrete. Indeed, the individualistic nature of interacting with any space problematises the aligning of it with one gender or another. With regards to the interplay between gender and space, Massey has been one of the key theorists whose work I have drawn from throughout this study. She asserts that,

the observer is inevitable within the world (the space) being observed. And this in turn means that it partly constitutes the observer and the observer it, and the fact of the observer's constitution of it means that there is necessarily a multiplicity of spaces, or takes on space.

(Massey, 1994:3)

Thus, simply by being present in a space we transform it, bringing with us not only our physical beings but also our personal schemas. Our perceptions of the spaces we interact with and inhabit contribute not only to our own experience, but also to the experience of

others within the space (Soja, 1980). The interaction here is twofold; an individual brings with her a 'constitution' of the space, therefore reconstituting it for herself, and also transforms the space for the observer by being present in it.

That the identity of a space depends on the perceptions of those interacting with it introduces a problematic aspect of my argument as to the gendering of Alloway. If we all experience space in a different way, then perhaps there can be no consensus on the hegemonic gender within it. A space that one individual finds androcentric may be argued as being neutral or feminist by another individual. To this end, I have employed Massey's (1994) framework of space and gender as a key tool in analysing the heritage sites chosen for this study. Massey (1994:179) suggests that, in understanding the gendering of space, we consider the messages they convey in relation to inclusivity:

space and place are important in the construction of gender relations and in struggles to change them. From the symbolic meaning of spaces/places and the clearly gendered messages which they transmit, to straightforward exclusion by violence, spaces and places are not only themselves gendered but, in their being so, they both reflect and affect the ways in which gender is constructed and understood

I propose a relevant example of this 'exclusion' to be the Burns Suppers that happen annually in Scotland and, indeed, across the Scottish diaspora worldwide. Although these events are for the most part open to men and women, women traditionally play a subordinate role in such events. Indeed, Tarbolton Bachelor's Club, which is viewed as the model for Burns Clubs worldwide, didn't permit any women to attend their Burns Supper until 2015 (see Mackay, 1992; BBC, 2015).

Burns Suppers are a tangible example of a gendered space, and those that now permit women still bear the traces of this legacy. For example, there is only one point in the evening set aside to be delivered by women ('the reply from the lassies'). This is reflected in the heritage landscape in Alloway where women are very much subordinate in the

representation of a specific masculine History. The dominant nature of the Burns narrative in Alloway, and with it the undertones of the exclusionary suppers, engenders an explicit sense of androcentrism within the space.

The suffragettes

On a typical weekend in high season, crowds of people descend on Alloway in search of an authentic experience of Scottish history. Many already know the name of Robert Burns, along with selections of his works and life story. How many, though, know the story of Frances Parker and Ethel Moorhead? One might assume that the majority of those wandering around Alloway's bucolic streets have no knowledge of an event which 'roused in the locality the most intense indignation' (Anon., *Glasgow Herald*, 1914). Depending on one's political leanings, this event may be viewed as either a radical protest or an attempted act of terrorism, but the facts are as follows. In the early hours of the 9th of July, 1914 two women cycled – presumably from Glasgow – into Alloway armed with pipe bombs. They inserted these bombs into the gutter outside the back of the cottage and would have ignited them had they not been interrupted by Robert Wyllie, a night watchman (Anon., *Glasgow Herald*, 1914). While one woman was caught and eventually identified (despite initially giving a pseudonym) as Frances Parker, the other escaped and we can only presume her identity to be Frances' frequent accomplice Ethel Moorhead (Workers' Educational Association Lothian Women's Forum, 2013). Frances was imprisoned, although was eventually released to a nursing home due to weakness brought on from hunger strike. She escaped from the home, and before being recaptured was given amnesty due to the outbreak of WWI (Leneman, 2004).

While this dramatic encounter was reported in the local and national press at the time, the story now seems to have faded into relative obscurity. I make this claim due to my work as

a playwright commissioned by the National Trust to write a script for this story that was presented as a work-in-progress on site at Burns' Cottage in June 2014. Discussing these events with colleagues, friends, family members and even residents of Alloway often resulted in a surprised response: many had never heard this story, and couldn't seem to grasp why it had not become a popular anecdote from Scottish history. Perhaps the marginalisation of female stories due to institutionalised patriarchy is to blame (Smith 2008). It may be the case that news of such blatantly militant acts has been suppressed in order to give the impression that the ultimate success of the suffragettes' cause was achieved through more peaceful means.

Whatever the reasons, when the work-in-progress play of the story, entitled *CauseWay*, was performed in the summer of 2014 it offered a new interpretation of Alloway's history for public consumption². Rather than reading about these women in an old newspaper or on a museum plaque, audiences stood in the same space as the events of 100 years before. It was my intention that the audience *experiencing* these stories, and being physically placed in the position of these women, would allow for a more holistic, phenomenological understanding of this episode in South Ayrshire Herstory (see Chapter 4). Embree and Fisher (2000:4) has posited the 'potential for interaction' between the philosophical disciplines of phenomenology and feminism, and in the case of *CauseWay* both such lenses were employed to create an atmosphere of empathy and shared experience around the story.

On being told the story of Parker and (most likely) Moorhead, I developed an interest in finding such untold stories. This, in turn, generated the question of how they could be most effectively disseminated. Furthermore, I began to explore ideas of locality, of identity, and of place and space. Historical and historiographical writings are doubtlessly helpful in

² 2014 work-in-progress was directed by David Overend

researching the stories of individuals. However, the lives of certain social groups, for example those of a lower socioeconomic status, ethnic minorities and, of course women, have been un/under-documented in such works (see Bock, 1989; Smith, 2008). In attempting to uncover such stories, and therefore attempting to provide a more complete account of the history of a certain site, I was moved to find more creative research means. A precedent for the employment of creative practice as a method of historical and site-based research has been set by practitioners such as Mike Pearson (2010) and the performance company Wrights & Sites (see Smith, 2010).

Given the impossibility of documenting the stories of all minority groups throughout UK history, my work focused particularly on the women of South Ayrshire. Whilst it is by no means a comprehensive account of every female life lived in the area, it offers an alternative Herstory of specific sites in the area. The central aim of the performances created during this study was to reconfigure specific heritage sites through creative feminist intervention. The term creative feminist intervention is used here to refer to creative practice encompassing prose writing, playwriting, and performance that is focused on and/or performed in a specific site and employs a feminist lens. My research investigated these stories through the lens of spatial theory, recognising that 'just as bodies are in place, places are bodied' (Heddon, 2008:89). The interaction between women and the spaces they inhabit was, therefore, crucial to the exploration of undocumented lives.

1.5 In Hidden Spaces and Souvenir

After commencing this study in February 2015, I returned to Alloway to develop a final version of the *CauseWay* play, which was performed on site on the 10th-12th of October 2015. This new production drew from the theoretical frameworks of the study, in particular

Pearson's (2010) work on site specific performance and Smith's (2008) discussion of women in heritage. Following the performances, audience members were asked to attend focus groups or complete online feedback forms describing their impressions of the work. The themes that I identified from these accounts were then used in the creation of the subsequent performance works, *In Hidden Spaces* and *Souvenir*, performed at Rozelle House and Ayr beachfront respectively. All three of the performance works, and the data derived from them, are explored in detail in this thesis. This section offers a brief overview of the *In Hidden Spaces* and *Souvenir* projects.

In Hidden Spaces was the second performance piece of this study, and took the form of an exploratory development period and public performance at Rozelle House, Ayr. The project lasted from the 4th-22nd of July 2016, with the performances taking place on the 23rd and 24th of July. Rozelle House, the former country residence of slaver Robert Hamilton, was selected for this project due to Smith's (2008:165) assertion that country houses are 'indisputably elite-masculine in the symbolic power and prestige they represent'. Although the house has been turned into an art gallery by South Ayrshire council, its patriarchal, colonial past is still evident throughout the space (see Chapter 6). The project involved myself and five other female performers working collaboratively in the space to explore its Herstory. While historical documentation was scant, those involved in the project made use of Aitchison's (1994) study of the women of Rozelle, in addition to census data taken during the residential period of the house.

Throughout this project we used Smith's (2010) concept of mythogeography, and the practical tools offered within the framework, as a guideline for exploring what the space could be or have been. Mythogeography played a central role in this study, and can be broadly understood as an ambulatory approach to exploring space by prioritising myth and obscure narratives (ibid). While the chapter on *In Hidden Spaces* primarily explores the

development process, the performance is also discussed. The piece was performed four times and drew on a variety of performances styles including durational, one-to-one and recorded and written notes for audiences. This decision was made in order to reflect the wide range of experiences and lives lived within the house. As was the case with *CauseWay*, audience feedback was used in the analysis of the work, along with documentation gathered during the project.

The final performance piece of this study, *Souvenir*, was developed with input from local community groups in Ayr. Written documentation of Herstory, particularly of the lives of working class women, is often elusive therefore the aim of this project was to record and share the stories of local women who had grown up or lived in South Ayrshire (Bock, 1989). In order to do this, I facilitated reminiscence workshops in October 2016 and January 2017. The participants were, for the most part, older women, although some men participated in the groups as well. In creating the script for the performance, I used stories shared at the workshops alongside local folklore and text generated from the development process.

The performance was created on Ayr beach, and made use of the concepts and tools that had come to be central to the study so far including mobility and mythogeography (see Wilkie, 2012; Smith, 2010). In addition to this, Berger's (2016) discussion of the relationship between the sea and the maternal provided a strong basis for our exploration of rhythm, femininity and water throughout the process. The final performances took place at Ayr beach on the 27th-29th of May 2017. While *CauseWay*, *In Hidden Spaces* and *Souvenir* were all performances in their own right, the themes and theories behind each of the works threaded them together. Therefore, in the chapters exploring each of these works, I discuss both their unique traits as performance works and the thematic links between them.

1.6 Gendered spaces

An exploration of what genders a space, and the effect of the dominant narratives of that space, are key theoretical components of this study. In a manner indicative of patriarchal culture, Urry (1995:26) devotes only a brief paragraph to discussing feminist concerns with space, asserting that it is 'irreducibly gendered'. The individualistic nature of how one conceptualises gender is inarguably a facet within spatial interactions (Heddon, 2008). Accepting that gender is a dynamic, interpretive concept raises the question of whether notions of gendered space are derived from personal schemas or from architectural and topographical aspects of a site. Indeed, it is fair to assume that psychology and architecture both impact upon how we interpret space. Let us begin, then, with the physical features of space.

Man-made is, for the most part, not a sexist or erroneous term when discussing site; most townscapes and cityscapes were overwhelmingly designed and created by men (Dreyer, 2005). The spaces we inhabit and interact with were generally built from a masculine perspective, and therefore prioritise the requirements of men (see below). Indeed, Massey (1994:7) has argued that the notion of 'boundaries' is aligned with the 'violent either/or distinction between polarised genders', and therefore links exist between the formation of regions and borders and patriarchal gender constructs. It requires no great stretch of the imagination to understand bounded spaces like heritage sites within such a conceptualisation. This leads to the question of how the topographical dominance of the male impacts upon women's experience of space.

It is important to consider how, from an architectural perspective, spaces were created, and who they were created for. Dolezal (2010:357) states that one of the legacies of patriarchy is the invisibility of women within 'power and social relations'. Such a legacy (if

that is, indeed, the correct term for a structure which still impacts upon society so profoundly) undoubtedly influences women's experience of space. The sites with which they interact on a daily basis were created by men, most likely for men. Consider the doorframe; an opening that is generally two feet higher than the head of the average woman. Now, to intimate that door frames should be made smaller is, arguably, misandrist; the average man would have to stoop in order to pass through it. Instead, I suggest that continually passing through spaces created to meet the requirements of a larger individual may have a causal relationship with the sense of powerlessness suggested by Dolezal (2010).

Moving from the physical to the conceptual, much discussion of space as a gendered entity relies on classical interpretations of gendered traits. In her discussion of the city as a gendered construct, Dreyer (2005:7) cites Vanessa Beecroft's 1998 performance work *Show* where 'twenty models with flawless figures posed as lifeless mannequins in a performance of three hours'. Dreyer uses this work as a metaphor for the city, which she codes as feminine due to its beauty and position as an aloof seductress. Furthermore, Kolodny's (1996:176) exploration of the rural American landscape characterises the land as 'nurturing, giving maternal breast'. However, few feminists would describe beauty, motherhood and the ability to seduce as (the only) key characteristics of the modern woman. In Western society, virtues associated with the feminine – beauty, passivity, subordination – are no longer necessarily held in high regard by all women. This begs the question of whether it is possible to define a space as gendered when the traits that define gender have become uncertain (see Massey, 1994).

The previous discussion of Alloway highlighted a location that is dominated by the story of one (male) person – Robert Burns. However, whether or not one dominant story in and of itself can be deemed responsible for gendering a space is open to debate. Alloway's

cultural identity revolves around a historical male figure, but this need not mean that the space is unquestionably coded as masculine. Many Herstories are untold, but so are many narratives of men's experience. This raises the question of whether Alloway and the RBBM can be coded as masculinist spaces because of the story of one man. In order to explore this further, I wish to consider Massey's (1994:7) proposed feminist antidote to the issue of masculine boundaries; 'thinking in terms of relations'.

Massey (1994) conceptualises sites as relational, constructed through links with other places rather than through borders that would render them a separate entity. Indeed, heritage sites are an excellent example of this relationality: while ostensibly separate spaces, they are managed by one local or national authority, and are therefore continually effected by changes in consumer needs and policy. In Massey's work, relationships between different places are understood as formative, and spatial shifts have the capacity for impact beyond designated boundaries. If the relationship of one site to another impacts upon space so, too, can the relationship of a body to a site. Indeed, the relationships between bodies, and therefore the stories created, effect the formation of space. In accepting that human stories influence the formation of space, then it is reasonable to suggest that the gender of an individual featured in a space contributes to the gendering of the space itself.

1.7 Gender and the heritage site

The following section outlines the interplay between gender and heritage sites. Over the course of this study, I used creative interventions (such as writing, playwriting and performance) as methodological tools to investigate this issue. The primary focus of my research was to represent the Herstory of South Ayrshire's heritage sites. The work involved exploring three designated heritage sites through walking and performance

experiments, in addition to using oral accounts and historical research. The decision to employ creative methods in my research is based upon the argument that where there is lack of documented accounts there is a possibility of reconfiguring space by reclaiming stories sidelined by traditional narratives (Smith, 2013).

The heritage site exists as a 'nostalgic utopia' that, through careful conservation, is allegedly immune from the natural changes and deteriorations that come with time (Smith, 2013:103). Heritage sites transport us back to their era where, for the most part, women were subjugated. The temporal position of such sites can lead to a lack of criticism of the dominance of male stories – women existed, but were not important, therefore needn't be considered within this particular site. The intact, preserved nature of heritage sites gives rise to largely unquestioned representations of the oppressive, patriarchal society present in that era (see Smith, 2008). In response to this, throughout my study I have employed Massey's (1994:3) concept of the relationship of time and space as 'dynamic' and 'ever-shifting'. If we accept the view of space as a dynamic entity then it follows that even spaces of heritage can be transformed by intervention. Despite its status as a fixed representation of history, the heritage site exists within the conceptualisation of space as a dynamic, changeable entity. Within this study, my approach to the three heritage sites was to understand them not as fixed, but as susceptible to the shifting impacts of time and society. Though these sites were created or developed to commemorate one set of stories, the aim of this study was to reconfigure them to represent uncelebrated Herstories.

The argument that our experience of space is affected by our gender is perhaps particularly evident in heritage sites (Massey, 1994). As a woman, to enter a heritage site is generally to enter a space where female voices are absent. For the most part, heritage

sites represent periods when women were almost universally oppressed, and the narratives promoted within these sites are largely male:

heritage is gendered, in that it is too often 'masculine', and tells a predominantly male-centered story, promoting a masculine, and in particular an elite-Anglo-masculine, vision of the past and present
(Smith, 2008:159)

The lack of Herstory has resulted in the explicit gendering of such spaces by aligning them almost exclusively with men and maleness. This is, of course, a legacy left by patriarchy; the eras depicted in heritage sites were, for the most part, periods where women were viewed as naturally subordinate to men. The narrow nature of (most) women's lives before the advent of the twentieth century means that the majority of notable historical figures are men, and that celebrated narratives are androcentric. However, as is evident with the case of the Alloway suffragettes, notable, site-based Herstories do exist.

However, one must question the impact that heritage sites have on the wider community. It could be argued that visits to heritage sites occur so scarcely within a life that they could not have anything other than a fleeting influence upon the formation of gender. In other words, such spaces may be representative of only masculine experience, but this does not necessarily matter to gender relations. However, I would suggest that every space we experience has a cumulative effect on the formation of gender. Of the relationship between gender, identity and heritage, Smith (2008:159) notes that,

we protect, manage, interpret for visitors, and visit heritage sites because they are, in some way, symbolic of our identities. Material heritage and intangible heritage performances offer corporeal reinforcements of a sense of belonging and sense of place, but whose identities are being represented and reinforced? How are identities constructed by, or in association with, heritage places and events? What are the contemporary consequences of those constructions – particularly for gender roles and identities?

Here Smith introduces the debate about the interplay not only between heritage and identity, but the identity of heritage itself. The gendering of heritage has the potential to

reinforce negative gender roles within society as a whole, thus necessitating intervention within heritage sites, and the wider industry. Many of the ideas posed here underline the rationale for my research, in particular the importance of the formational relationship between heritage and gender identity.

Experiencing sites that are so dominated by masculine stories exacerbates the (patriarchal) notion that women are subordinate. One solution, offered by Massey (1994:2), is that of 'challenging the currently dominant form of gender definitions and gender relations'. There can be little doubt as to the meaning of the term 'dominant' here; Massey refers to patriarchy which, more than twenty years after her words were written, remains a powerful force in social relations. The assumption here is that in order to reconfigure how we explore space and place we must find alternative viewpoints. I argue that this can be achieved, in part, by reclaiming the lost stories of female inhabitants throughout designated spaces. History is a crucial element in how we relate to such sites, and the missing Herstories mean that our experience of them is weighted towards a patriarchal interpretation of history and of gender roles. The challenge Massey poses here against dominant structures is crucial in all spaces, including heritage sites. The feminist reclaiming of such spaces is simply one of myriad potential methods that can begin to represent the Herstories of the spaces we inhabit.

Massey (1994:4) posits that the reconfiguration of space may be approached through events and occurrences, arguing that 'within this dynamic simultaneity which is space, phenomena may be placed in relationship to one another in such a way that new social effects are provoked.' Intervening in a space to create social change was precisely the aim of my performances. In developing the performances, I worked with the Herstory of each site to bring about a new understanding of it, and to create new relationships between the

site and the people who experience it. Whilst Massey does not specify whether these 'phenomena' should be organic experiences, or whether rehearsed interventions would also fit into this category, I argue that site-specific performance has the potential to achieve the effects mentioned here.

In a sense, creative interventions such as plays, community projects and short stories are essentially synthetic; they are rehearsed and edited, rather than a natural interaction with space. However, they are also a real moment experienced by individuals within the space, and can therefore, be regarded in the same manner as the 'phenomena' posed by Massey (1994). Throughout this thesis, I explore how the three performances created interacted with and impacted upon their respective spaces. Subsequent chapters offer an elucidation of how I developed a practice that drew from the theoretical frameworks mentioned here, and that responded to the specific sites of the RBBM, Rozelle House and Ayr beachfront. In order to contextualise my work, Chapter 2 is comprised of a review of relevant literature in the fields of performance studies, spatial theory and heritage studies. This review includes definitions of specific terms used in this study, in addition to a more profound discussion of the key theorists in my work.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The work-in-progress performance of *CauseWay* in 2014 was, as aforementioned, a precursor to this study. In order to develop the performance further, it was incumbent upon me to find theorists whose ideas could be employed to strengthen the relationship between the performance and the RBBM site, and to question the implications it had for representations of women. My research led me towards two complementary theoretical frameworks: spatial theory (a strand of human geography) and heritage discourse. Current research into site-specific performance was also important in setting a precedent for my work.

This literature review will focus primarily on spatial theory and heritage studies, with a short section on site-specific performance. Discussions of identity, how it is formed in relation to these areas, and feminism are also key components of my research. While this chapter does not contain a specific subsection on feminist theory, several of the theorists within the disciplines considered have approached their work from a feminist standpoint. Given the extensive nature of these fields, the following literature review focuses on the overlapping areas. The discussion of spatial and heritage theory is limited to that which pertains to gender and identity as I am primarily interested in exploring feminist critiques of space, place and heritage. I shall propose definitions of specific terms and concepts, particularly those with contested definitions. The review will briefly introduce each key theoretical concept before exploring its application to my research, and will also incorporate a discussion of gaps in current literature.

2.2 Spatial theory

Before reviewing the literature surrounding the interaction between gender and space it is necessary to outline the developments in spatial theory that led to such discourse.

Massey, who was one of the leading theorists in this area, has written extensively on space and gender. I have employed her work to provide a theoretical structure with which to explore the interplay between female identity and heritage sites. As Massey (1994) notes, the idea that space is shaped not only by its physical properties but also by social interaction was first posited by Marxist geographers in the 1970s. However, she also notes that,

while it is surely correct to argue that space is socially constructed, the one-sidedness of that formulation implied that geographical forms and distributions were simply outcomes, the endpoint of social explanation.
(1994:253-254)

In her discussion, Massey highlights the necessity for geographers of this era to consider space not as an 'endpoint' of social interaction, but also as agential in transforming society itself. What followed, then, was the necessity to challenge the notion that space is formed by society, but has no impact on society itself.

At around this time, Lefebvre (1974:73) suggested that the interaction between space and society is multidirectional in nature:

(Social) space is not a thing among other things, nor a product among other products: rather it subsumes things produced, and encompasses their interrelationships in their coexistence and simultaneity - their (relative) order and/or (relative) disorder. It is the outcome of a sequence and set of operations, and thus cannot be reduced to the rank of a simple object. At the same time there is nothing imagined, unreal or 'ideal' about it as compared, for example, with science, representations, ideas or dreams. Itself, the outcome of past actions, social space is what permits fresh actions to occur, while suggesting others and prohibiting yet others. Among these actions, some serve production, others consumptions (i.e. the enjoyment of the fruits of production). Social space implies a great diversity of knowledge.

Here Lefebvre offers a conceptualisation of space that indicates its position as both an outcome and producer of social interaction. Indeed, his words are demonstrative of the

agency that space possesses in a profusion of social contexts. Space draws upon those things that are said, imagined and created by society and, in doing so, shapes what comes next. Lefebvre was one of the first theorists to conceptualise space as both a producer and a product of society, thereby critiquing the Marxist position of a unidirectional relationship between the spatial and the social.

Reacting to this, Soja (1980:207) introduced the idea of a 'socio-spatial dialectic', arguing that Marxist geographers should focus their analysis more on the reciprocity of the relationship between the social and the spatial. The nature of Soja's (1980:211) proposed dialectic is thus:

the fundamental premise of the socio-spatial dialectic: that social and spatial relationships are dialectically inter-reactive, interdependent; that social relations of production are both space-forming and space-contingent.

Moving forward from an accepted Marxist viewpoint that 'space is a social construct' (Massey, 1994:254), Soja (1980) asserted that whilst the social certainly impacts upon the spatial, the relationship also works in the opposite direction. Therefore, both the spatial and the social form and are formed by interaction with each other. Throughout this thesis, Soja's concept of a socio-spatial dialectic will be employed to refer to the relationship between the spatial and the social. Whilst Massey and Soja's works were published over two decades ago, they remain highly influential in the field of human geography. Indeed, the formational nature of the relationship between the social and the spatial has subsequently been acknowledged and employed by a number of theorists in their analyses and discussions of space and society (see, for example, Natter & Jones III, 1997; Grossberg, 2010; Saldanha, 2013). This interplay between space and society has developed into a well-established theoretical standpoint in spatial theory and human geography.

Accepting the concept of the socio-spatial dialectic within the parameters of this study leads to the question of how this dialectic can be applied within heritage sites (see section 2.3 for a definition of this term). In order to address this, I return now to Massey. A significant theme within Massey's (1994:3) writing is the fluid nature of space:

The view (...) is of space-time as a configuration of social relations within which the specifically spatial may be conceived of as an inherently dynamic simultaneity. Moreover, since social relations are inevitable and everywhere imbued with power and meaning and symbolism, this view of the spatial is as an ever-shifting social geometry of power and signification.

In order to challenge the dominant messages present within a space, we must first understand it as adaptable rather than fixed. Natter and Jones III (1997) concur that space should not be conceptualised as fixed, and this is indicative of the potential for it to be reconfigured through the actions of individuals within it. Furthermore, Featherstone and Painter (2013:4) argue that 'spatial relations can be articulated and generated in different, potentially antagonistic, ways'. This notion of *antagonising* space is useful in understanding the Ayrshire Herstories study, as the performances created attempted to unsettle the identities of the chosen sites. My research integrated live performance, understood here as a directly political intervention, with the understanding of space as a dynamic entity that both informs social relations and is informed by them. Throughout this thesis I explore the extent to which the spaces were altered through performance, thereby investigating the potential of creative interactions in reconfiguring spatial conceptualisations of heritage sites.

Space and place

It is necessary here to take a moment to define two of the slightly problematic terms in relation to spatial theory: space and place³. Whilst they are key terms within the sphere of geography, there is by no means a unanimous view on their meaning. Before discussing

³ The definition of site, another spatial term used throughout this thesis, will be discussed in section 2.3

space, and how space and place impact upon one another, I shall begin by focusing upon place. Place is, perhaps, a more contested term as it is commonly defined as somewhere physical and fixed, and is popularly 'reduced to locations between which movements of physical bodies occur' (Casey, 1998:x). Featherstone and Painter (2013:11) note that even the semantics of the term 'place' have been debated:

the meaning of the English word 'place' is often carried in Latin languages by the words for territory (...) This can lead to confusion in translation since the English term 'territory' carries a much stronger sense of a coherent, bounded space (...) Haesbert proposes a concept of territory that, like Massey's notion of place, is processual, porous and endowed with multiple identities.

Haesbert (2013), much like Massey (1994), argues that place is not a static physical encasing in which space exists fluidly. Instead, Haesbert (2013) argues that the changes that occur within space through social interaction and temporal shifts also impact upon place and render it just as dynamic and multifaceted as space itself.

The conceptualisation of place as shifting and flexible is contested. For example, Hardt and Negri (2001:426) have argued that 'a notion of place that has no boundaries empties the concept completely of its content'. However, I consider that defining space and identities as relational directly leads to place being a relational entity also. Within my research, I recognise space as somewhat ephemeral, constituted of concepts, impressions, meanings and narratives, 'a simultaneity of stories-so-far' (Massey, 2005:9). The multiplicity of ideas and narrative that form a space are, in turn, borne of interactions with a more concrete, physical place. Therefore, while space can be reconfigured in a more immediate sense, the changes that happen within space can impact upon place as the two are inextricably linked. In a sense, place creates space, and to an extent the opposite is also true.

Gendered space

The understanding that space and society impact upon each other's development leads to the question of how this affects individual identity. Little (2007) notes that feminist geography – that is, geographical enquiry specifically concerned with gender and women – gained academic attention around the mid 1970s. Within this section, I primarily discuss feminist geographers from the late 1980s onwards in order to consider both established works and more recent research.

As previously stated, Massey's work is key to my research as it focuses on the relationship between space and gender. The principal argument in her influential work *Space, Place and Gender* is that,

geography matters to the construction of gender, and the fact of geographical variation in gender relations, for instance, is a significant element in the production and reproduction of both imaginative geographies and uneven development.
(1994:2)

Massey's assertion here of a strong link between geography and gender makes the case for a feminist standpoint within spatial theory. Rather than exploring space from a neutral (i.e. male) perspective, Massey questions how gender identities are constructed in relation to the spaces with which they interact. She moves beyond simply exploring the relationship between space and humans-as-one-entity to indicate that gender differences will lead to a difference in interaction with space and place. Whilst this work deals mainly with examples from 1970s/80s Britain, her contribution to feminist geography has had a significant impact within the field (see Cresswell, 2015; Featherstone & Painter, 2013).

Blunt and Rose (1994:3) have also explored the interplay between space and gender, arguing that,

the social construction of gender differences establishes some spaces as women's and others as men's; those meanings then serve to reconstitute the power relations of gendered identity.

In essence, Blunt and Rose (1994) proffer Soja's socio-spatial dialectic, repositioned within a feminist standpoint, as a means of understanding the gendered nature of space. Many theorists in the field of feminist geography employ the constructivist understanding of gender proposed by Blunt and Rose. In her discussion of the field, Little (2007:337) notes that,

breaking down the idea of the feminine as natural turned attention away from the idea that gender differences were biologically fixed and towards the recognition that they reflect socially constructed notions of masculinity and femininity.

With the original distinction between sex as biological and gender as social having been made some decades ago, the constructivist nature of gender is generally an accepted concept within the academy (Oakley, 1972). Little (2007: 339) notes that 'biology has thus been relegated in favour of a focus on the social' in feminist geography, and in the wider feminist discourse. The neglected question of how biology influences our experience of space is a concern within my research, with a particular focus on pregnancy and motherhood. Encountering space whilst pregnant, menstruating, breastfeeding or during menopause will undoubtedly influence a woman's experience. Whilst not all women will encounter experiences associated with motherhood, they are biological examples of difference that are incorporated into my explorations of the socio-spatial identities of women.

The interplay between space, place and narratives is also a key theme in feminist geography. Anzaldúa (1987:78) offers an understanding of space based on the 'borderlands' between the USA and Mexico; one that is particularly pertinent to spaces that contain multiple narratives:

At some point, on our way to a new consciousness, we will have to leave the opposite bank, the split between two mortal combatants somewhat healed so that we are on both shores at once, and at once see through the serpent and the eagle eyes.

This perspective is particularly pertinent to my work, as it highlights the necessity of viewing space through a variety of lenses. To understand the multiple narratives present in any space is to move one's viewpoint closer, as it were. It is also to appreciate that it exists as a combination of experiences and perspectives, some substantially different to our own. The notion of 'mortal combatants' (which I use hyperbolically) can be applied to the understanding of gender as polarised and binary. Such an understanding of gender is highly evident in spaces of heritage, where women are generally represented within the confines of the domestic sphere. In order to promote History and Herstory it is necessary to employ Anzaldúa's notion of being 'on both shores at once'. One narrative need not engulf the other; both may co-exist in order to create a richer understanding of heritage spaces.

2.3 Heritage sites

The following section addresses two key themes within heritage theory as it relates to my research: heritage and performance (incorporating discussions of audience); and heritage and gender. Beginning with a definition of heritage sites, and their relationship to previously discussed theories of space and place, current and influential literature is reviewed alongside a discussion of relevant practice-based projects. The term 'heritage performance' is used to describe any performance events occurring within heritage sites. In addition to this, I use 'feminist heritage performance' to denote performance work that explores or represents narratives of women in heritage sites. Some of the works discussed here make reference to museums rather than heritage sites specifically. As we shall see, museums may be viewed as heritage sites and vice versa, therefore I have taken such literature into account.

I begin by defining the term heritage site in relation to this study. Within my research, the term site is used as it is commonly understood; to delineate an area within a place. As place itself is conceptualised as dynamic and reconfigurable so, too, is site (Kaye, 2000). UNESCO (2017:n.p.) states ten different criteria for selection of a World Heritage site, including 'to exhibit an important interchange of human values, over a span of time or within a cultural area of the world'. While none of the heritage sites used in my work were UNESCO World Heritage sites, I would argue this criterion can be applied to all three. Tivers (2002:188) discusses the contested definition of heritage, bringing attention to the fact that it can include,

mythical sites (...), reconstructions of real places (...), locations where significant features no longer exist (...), museum collections, Medieval 'Fayres', community culture, vernacular building styles, and the ways of life of people of the past.

Smith (2008) and Kidd (2011) have also suggested that heritage can take the form of more than just specific sites or exhibitions. Within my research, I will employ this interpretation of heritage sites. Although the term is generally associated with conserved locations it can also be used to describe places and/or spaces that have significant links to times past.

Before beginning my review of heritage literature I anticipated a strong argument for heritage sites as static spaces. I expected these spaces, which represent events and people past, would be conceptualised as quite still: as a 'monument' (Smith, 2008:167) or 'sacred space' (Marstine, 2006:9) within contemporary society. Viewing heritage sites as 'sacred' or untouchable has direct implications for the application of the socio-spatial dialectic. Such sites may impact upon the identities of those who visit, but their iconic status could, arguably, render them closed to the multidirectional nature of the dialectic. Although many aforementioned theorists define space as fluid and dynamic, the nature of visitors' relationships with heritage spaces is perhaps deemed less open to change or adaptation. Smith (2013:103) notes that heritage sites,

seemed to trigger strong personal and social resonance for their visitors, with a tendency, despite their management and policing, to act as fanciful or nostalgic utopias.

With this in mind, it might be argued that individuals may be more resistant to reconfiguration of such spaces than those deemed quotidian or contemporary.

There is much crossover between Massey's (1994) ideas of flexible space and current conceptualisations of heritage sites. One of the key theorists in this area is Smith whose work explores the function and impact of heritage. Smith's (2008:167) interpretation of heritage sites is as follows:

If we consider heritage as a cultural process, and what happens at heritage places is part and parcel of heritage, then notions of heritage not only become more complex, but they allow the possibility of active public or visitor engagement with heritage sites. Heritage is as much what happens at sites, places, exhibitions and so forth as the places themselves.

That heritage sites are interactive, fluid spaces remains an important point of discussion in current heritage discourse (see Bohlin et al, 2010; Smith 2013). This perception of heritage sites aligns them with the understanding of space posited by, amongst others, Massey (1994), Soja (1980) and Lefebvre (1974). Furthermore, Smith (2013) has stated that his attempts to encourage visitors to question heritage sites through performance practice were successful, indicating the possibility for reconceptualisation of such spaces. My research is positioned within the view that heritage sites are, like any other space, adaptable and open to reconfiguration. Therefore, in the remainder of this section I shall specifically explore literature surrounding heritage performance and gender (including gendered identities) and heritage sites.

Heritage performance

The interplay between performance practice and heritage sites has been relatively well researched, particularly within the 2005-2008 Performance, Learning and Heritage project

(PLH) and by the artist and researcher Phil Smith (2013; 2012; 2010). The following section will briefly discuss the PLH project and Smith's work before giving an overview of current literature on heritage performance.

The PLH project, conducted at Manchester University from 2005-2008, was the first longitudinal study of heritage and performance in the UK, and remains the most substantial to date (Jackson & Kidd, 2011). Jackson and Kidd (2011:3) identify the rationale for the study as exploring 'the use and impact of performance as a medium of learning and interpretation at museums and heritage sites'. The project involved several strands of inquiry, the first being a study of existing heritage performance (Kidd, 2011). It also involved the creation of several performance pieces at venues such as the National Maritime Museum, and The Manchester Museum (Jackson, 2011).

Smith has created numerous site-specific performances and generated a wealth of research on performance and site (2009; 2010; 2012; 2013; 2014). His work within and around heritage sites, in particular his doctoral research, involved producing a variety of creative interventions. Smith (2013:103) has delineated the aims of his work thus:

The intention of my interventions was to set visitors in disrupted and self-conscious motion through heritage sites; to hypersensitise them to the fine textures, the conflicting and multiple narratives and the accidental ironies of these places; and to provoke them to make their own interrogations of them.

Smith's practice challenges the hegemonic narratives presented by heritage sites in order to enable visitors to create new interpretations and understandings, and to imbue such spaces with a sense of agency. The parallels between Smith's work and the PLH project are clear, and understanding their methodologies has been particularly useful throughout this study. My work builds upon this research by focusing more specifically on heritage performance and gender (by considering Herstory), which was not a key concern in either

Smith's work or the PLH project. This exploration of gender, performance and heritage in my research is one of the primary contributions to knowledge about women's identities in sites of heritage.

Whilst the above are examples of heritage performance more aligned with my own work, there is a great variety in both style and content of performances in heritage sites. Current research often focuses on sampling certain styles rather than aiming to delineate a definitive method or form (see Tivers, 2002; Kidd, 2011). A recurring theme in such literature is that of accuracy. Discussing the performance aspects of Llancaiach Fawr Manor house in South Wales, Tivers (2002:192) states that the performers are 'as dedicated to the educational value of the 'living history' experience as are the owners of the house (...) the concern is for historical accuracy'. Within my research, 'historical accuracy' is difficult to achieve due to the lack of documentation of women's lives. However, Kidd (2011:24) notes that in the PLH project audiences found 'authenticity' to be an important factor in heritage performance. Kidd (2011:26) states that the focus upon authenticity,

could (...) become a distraction, one instance of perceived inauthenticity becoming a primary focus (indeed an irritant) that proves an insurmountable hurdle in the meaning-making process.

This highlights an apparent necessity of rooting performance within historical accuracy, at least partially. The literature suggests that it is important that an audience can believe in the accuracy of a performance in order for them to relate it to their interpretation of a heritage site. Therefore, although some conjecture was required, I have attempted to imbue the works throughout this study with a sense of Heristorical authenticity by including accounts of real people and events.

The importance of a relationship between heritage sites (often falling under the wider bracket of 'museums') and performance has also been relatively well explored. In her study of theatre and museums, Bennett (2013:3) has noted that the fact that both are aimed at engaging and educating the public renders them 'symbolic and actual neighbours'. Furthermore, Kidd (2011: 28) observes that,

most locations (for museum theatre presentations especially) are only temporarily theatricalised through performance, and their quick return to the normality of the museum even helps to highlight the transience of history and the impermanence of the people and stories that constitute it.

Whilst live performance and history may seem diametrically opposed (one being immediate and present, the other fixed and past), their ephemerality creates parallels in form. Therefore, a relationship between the two can allow for exploration of their potential to influence and mould space and identity. Smith (2013) has also discussed how the unique position of heritage sites, as a representation of the past existing within the present, renders them a somewhat liminal space. This liminality, at least in Smith's estimation, allows for a unique interplay between space and performance, where we have the ability to acknowledge and interact with history, space, and our present selves simultaneously.

In relation to my work surrounding heritage performance, there are currently two specific areas that are under-researched and will therefore be a key focus. The first is gender and the second is the experiences of the audiences and performers. Whilst there are a modest number of publications focusing on heritage and gender (see above), to date there have been no substantial studies into heritage performance that locate gender as a central concern. With regards to audience, Jackson's (2011) analysis of engagement in heritage performance highlights the dynamic nature of such audiences, as they must constantly renegotiate their position in relation to a performance they may not even have intended to watch. In relation to performers, there have been no substantial studies into the

experience of the performer within the heritage site. Smith (2008:167) has called for 'a better understanding of how people interact, engage and experience heritage sites'. Furthermore, Jackson (2011) has noted the necessity for a deeper understanding of people's interactions with heritage sites, specifically in relation to heritage performance. By exploring the possibilities of site-specific performance in reconfiguring the individual's experience of a heritage site, my research contributes to discourse surrounding audiences and performers and their interactions with this style of performance.

Heritage and gender

Accepting that heritage sites are not exempt from Soja's (1980) socio-spatial dialectic necessitates an exploration of the potential for heritage to impact upon identity. As this study is particularly concerned with the experiences of women, the following section explores literature on the relationship between gender and the heritage site. The documentation of human history is biased, as Schouten (1995:24) notes: 'history has always been written by the winners and not by the losers, and winning in itself does not prove historical truth'. Dominant (male) groups have created the historical narratives that form contemporary heritage (Aitchison, 1996). A corollary of this is that adhering only to documented history naturally renders Herstorical narratives incomplete. Smith (2008:161) discusses the interplay between heritage and gender, stating that heritage 'reproduces and legitimises gender identities and the social values that underpin them'. Given her argument that heritage is androcentric, and that women are visually represented as 'passive (...) often behind or below males' (ibid:164) it follows that the 'social values' presented in the heritage sector are those of women being subordinate to men.

The time periods represented in most heritage sites are generally pre-first wave feminism, which has been defined as occurring at the end of the nineteenth century (Heilmann,

2000). Perhaps, then, it is not particularly surprising that women's experiences are not foregrounded. However, the underrepresentation of women's narratives is also present within academic discourse surrounding heritage. Returning to the work of Smith who offers a comprehensive discussion of heritage and gender, the lack of academic focus in this area is clear. Smith (2008:172) states that,

widening academic and policy understandings of heritage and the roles and consequences it has in everyday lives is vital in developing socially inclusive cultural policies that consider and celebrate (...) the diversity of people's gendered experiences and identities.

Whilst I cannot represent the vast array of gendered identities present in contemporary society, my work addresses this gap in knowledge about the interplay between heritage and gender. There have been few publications surrounding gender and heritage since Smith's work, and my research therefore responds to this gap in heritage studies.

2.4 Site-specific performance

Given the practice-as-research design of this study, it is necessary to review some of the current research into site-specific performance. There are a number of influential works that explore site-specificity in the arts in general, rather than theatre (see Kwon, 2002; Kaye, 2000). However, given the scope of this study, the following section will only discuss literature that deals particularly with theatre and performance. While some theorists primarily analyse the work of other artists, there are also practitioners who use their own work as data in a similar style to my project. The following section will cover key theorists in this area, artist/academics, and will briefly discuss the current landscape of site-specific performance in the UK.

I begin by delineating the terms 'site-specific' and 'performance' in relation to my research. In terms of theatre practice, various terms for work outside of a theatre space have been mooted in artistic discourse. These include site-based, site-responsive, site-generic in

addition to the more widely used site-specific. To clarify my working concept of site-specificity, I employ Wilkie's (2002:158) definition: 'site-specific performance engages with site as symbol, site as story-teller, site as structure'. The essential characteristic of site-specific performance in my research is that the performance work responds to the site, interacts with it and could not be performed in any other space.

With regards to the term 'performance' there is a far greater wealth of discourse concerned with its meaning. Schechner's (1977:xvii) influential theorisation of the word proposes it as,

a continuum that reaches from the ritualisations of animals (including humans) through performances in everyday life – greetings, displays of emotion, family scenes, professional roles, and so on – through to play, sports, theatre dance, ceremonies, rites, and performances of great magnitude.

Whilst I accept Schechner's position that any conscious act can be viewed as performance, my conceptualisation of the term is quite different in reference to this research project. I align myself instead with Pearson's (2007:3) interpretation:

[my work] focuses upon activities with an aesthetic or rhetorical quotient – moments of extra-daily practice. Such performative activities, it is suggested, constitute special opportunities (...) to examine the implications of material conditions of exposition for the form and function of performance.

One of the central aims of my research is to examine the potential for live performance to reconfigure space, rather than an analysis of how a space is affected by quotidian activities. Therefore, in line with Pearson's conception of the term 'performance', my research is primarily based in the understanding of performance as a planned, created event that is presented to an audience.

In current writing on site-specific performance, the question of how an artist engages with a site is deemed pertinent. To return to Wilkie's (2002:140) work, which reviews the 'terrain' of this style of work in the UK, the notion of narrative is considered to be of low importance. Wilkie (2002:155) notes that,

in many cases, a thematic engagement is deemed less necessary (or, in one or two instances, less desirable) than a geometric or structural one in order for a piece to be termed site-specific

However, this conception of a hierarchy between narrative and space is not the case in the work of all artists/companies creating performance in this area. Pearson, for example, is an academic and practitioner who has worked extensively within the sphere of site-specific performance (see Pearson and Shanks, 2001; Pearson, 2006; Pearson, 2010). Turner (2004:376), discussing Pearson's work, states that 'site-specific performance is viewed as an archaeological investigation of place'. It is worth noting that archaeology, which brings with it the narratives of human history, is viewed as integral to the creation of site-specific performance. Within my research, the topographical layout of a space is understood as of equal importance to its Herstorical narratives.

Site-specific performance became more popular in the UK in the late 1990s/early 2000s as the term began to appear in newspapers and other mass media (Wilkie, 2002). Now a relatively well-established term even beyond theatre circles, companies and artists that work almost exclusively in this area have developed their practice towards what Wilkie (2012:203) has termed a 'mobility turn'. Wilkie (ibid) defines this turn as 'site-specific artwork that only makes sense in relation to the contexts of mobility'. Examples of this include Pearson's tour of his childhood home *Bubbling Tom* (2000); Smith's *The Crab Walks* (2003); Wrights & Sites' *Mis-Guided Tours* (various); and Wilson's *The Gathering/Yr Helfa* (2014).

Wilkie (2010: 212) has suggested potential reasons behind this relationship between mobility and site-specificity, theorising 'conceptions of place as fundamentally tied up with questions of mobility'. Furthermore, Overend (2013:379) suggests that, 'the journey form is frequently used by contemporary performances in order to respond to site as part of an

increasingly mobile relational realm.' While a consensus seems to have been reached on mobile site-specific theatre responding to globalisation, the question of gender remains unrepresented. The link between feminism and mobility is clear in Massey's (1994:11) assertion that 'one gender-disturbing message might be – in terms of both identity and space – keep moving!'. Juxtaposing this against the idea of women as home, Massey (ibid) advocates that mobility is one method of opposing such gendered stereotyping. She discusses the classical notion of men wanting to 'fix' women in a space, as a 'stabilising' influence for their own mobility (see, also, Oakley, 1972). Therefore, my research will explore not only the relationship between mobility and site-specific performance, but also the currently under-researched potential this has to reconfigure the gendered nature of space.

Before concluding this section on site-specific performance, I wish to outline two concepts that were employed as frameworks for the creation of the performances in this study. The first, that of mythogeography, has been mentioned already within this thesis (Smith, 2010). Given that it has, however, been central to the study, I take a moment here to offer a brief outline. In his book on the subject, Smith (2010:113-116) offers a 'mythogeographical manifesto' stating the philosophies and practical considerations of the framework. The practice can holistically be defined as an ambulatory approach to exploring space, paying particular attention to ostensibly unremarkable details in order to investigate and develop alternative site-based narratives (Smith, 2010). The aforementioned lack of available Herstorical data in the heritage sites chosen for this study led to a synergy between my work and the principles offered by mythogeography; creative practice became a necessary means for challenging the masculinist hegemony.

The second framework I wish to note pertains to Berger's (2016) explorations of the links between the sea and the maternal. The concepts described by Berger in her work became a consideration towards the end of this study. This can be attributed to two factors: first, that the final performance took place by the sea and, second, Berger's work was not published until 2016. In her work, Berger proposes specific tools and structures for exploring the links between femininity and the sea, including exploring improvisation, rhythm and repetition. Both Smith and Berger offer practical examples of how to approach the development of a performance that responds to a specific space, and their work has been extremely influential throughout this study. My work, then, can be understood as building upon these frameworks; combining an exploration of the feminine with an approach to site, in order to explore specific, heritage-based narratives.

2.5 Conclusion

This review of literature has identified specific elements within each of the fields discussed that are currently lacking in academic analysis. In particular, the relationship between biology, gender and space; the exclusion of Herstory in heritage sites; audience and performers' interactions with heritage performance; and the links between feminist performance and mobility and these are all secondary considerations within my research. The primary contribution of this study, however, lies in the combination of the key theoretical bases for my work. At present, within the fields of human geography and heritage studies, there is a wealth of literature upon the formation of identity. Furthermore, the potential for interaction between live performance and heritage sites has gained currency within the past decade, due in no small part to the work of Smith and the PLH. However, the key concern of my research, one currently under-represented in these disciplines (excepting spatial theory), is that of women and gender. I argue that live performance has the potential for radical, immediate spatial intervention due to its

ephemeral nature. As it stands, there have currently been no substantial studies that focus upon the efficacy of site-specific performance practice in reconfiguring the androcentric nature of heritage spaces. Therefore, my research seeks to address this gap in the literature by integrating the socio-spatial dialectic with site-specific performance in order to challenge the androcentric nature of heritage sites. In Chapter 3, I offer a discussion of the methodological framework used to achieve said integration, before exploring the performance works created in Chapters 4-6.

3. Methodology

3.1 Introduction

The following chapter is a delineation and exploration of the research methods employed in this study. The primary methodology used, practice-as-research (PaR), is relatively new in research terms and remains somewhat debated within the academy (Thomson, 2003). Therefore, I begin by discussing current debates surrounding the methodology, and also my rationale for employing it within my research. This chapter also covers the ways in which the PaR methodology is applied throughout my research. As is often the case in PaR studies, my work draws from methods used in qualitative tradition including questionnaires and focus groups, therefore such methods will also be discussed here (Haseman, 2007). I finish this chapter by touching upon the bricolage method, which I employed in constructing the theoretical framework for my research. Before exploring the methods used in the study, however, I will begin by defining some contested terms that I make use of throughout this chapter.

3.2 Practice, thesis and exegesis

While creative practice (as a research output) has begun to gain traction within UK universities, the precise term that should be used for the methodology remains debated. A variety of designations for this methodology have been proposed as artistic works (musical scores, theatre scripts, visual art, etc.) continue to become accepted as research within the academy. These include, but are not limited to, practice-led research, practice-based research and creative arts research practice (see, for example, Barrett & Bolt, 2007; Smith & Dean, 2011; Rogers, 2012). I have decided on the term practice-as-research as it reflects the form of this study, and highlights that both the performance and written works constitute the research findings:

the 'as' in the phrase functions to problematise conventional notions of theatre and performance practice (...) the 'as' makes a claim that the performance or theatre event itself may be a form of research (Kershaw, 2011:107)

This term also acknowledges that the research has developed from both the practical and the theoretical explorations, and that the two are fundamentally interconnected. Smith and Dean (2011:5) argue that,

practice as research can best be interpreted in terms of a broader view of creative practice which includes not only the artwork but also the surrounding theorisation and documentation

In my research, I employ the term PaR in the manner posited here: that is to say that both the practice and the written exegesis are used to disseminate the research findings and PaR is the methodology used to develop both.

The terms thesis and exegesis will also be used throughout this and subsequent chapters and I will now define these terms in relation to my work. In the case of this study, dissemination occurs through two interlinked strands: performance and written exegesis. The *practice* in this PaR study refers to the work of creating and presenting new performance works for three specific sites. In order to define the term exegesis as it pertains to this study, I employ Haseman's (2007:156) definition of the term: 'an additional commentary commonly referred to as an exegesis (...) an explanation or interpretation of the creative or artistic work'. As mentioned in the introduction, this thesis comprises both the performances and the written exegesis of this study. In order to differentiate between this document and the performances, outwith this chapter I employ the term 'thesis' as a shorthand to refer to this written document. The performance-based elements of my thesis will be referred to as performances, and both are essential in conveying the findings of my work.

3.3 Practice-as-research

While it is difficult to pinpoint an exact inception date of the PaR methodology, Sullivan (2011) notes the debates around research and the arts that occurred in 1980s Australasia and in the UK. He describes the clash between ‘rationalist’ thinkers and those supporting the arts, and how this impacted negatively upon arts within the academy. In Sullivan’s estimation, this was the beginning of the development of PaR as a methodology. In terms of the methodology becoming more widely acknowledged, Kershaw (2011:105) states that PaR gained traction within western academia ‘towards the end of 2000s’. Given the relatively short timescale between the development, subsequent wider acceptance of this methodology and the beginning of this project, it is perhaps unsurprising that I have often been required to explain my methodology to peers and academic staff alike. Therefore, I will begin this section with an elucidation of the current debates surrounding the methodology itself, before discussing the application within my work.

The efficacy of practice and its potential to contribute to knowledge is an area covered by a number of writers on PaR. This can, perhaps, be viewed as a response to PaR being misunderstood within traditional academic systems (Sullivan, 2011). However, in order for the PaR methodology to be applied to its full potential, the unique potential of art in engendering conceptual and social change needs to be acknowledged:

artist-researchers take us (...) to where we’ve never been before, to see what we’ve never seen. And then they bring us back and help us look again at what we thought we knew. Facing the unknown and disrupting the known is precisely what artist-researchers achieve as they delve into theoretical, conceptual, dialectical and contextual practices through artmaking
(Sullivan, 2011:62)

Of particular note here is the concept of challenging accepted knowledge through creative work. An archaeological or historiographical exploration of the heritage sites chosen for my study would potentially gather new information about unrepresented lives. But it is

particularly the presence of creativity and imagination that allows these lives to be represented fully, in a manner that can challenge traditional knowledge paradigms while also stimulating the interest of the general population.

The importance of PaR as a methodology stems from the rejection of logocentrism as a prerequisite of knowledge exchange: as argued by Barrett (2007:1), 'artistic research demonstrates that knowledge is derived from doing and from the senses'. This phenomenological perspective underpins the development of the works created in my study. Given the importance of the relationship between people and space in my work, it is crucial that the performances be experienced in the site where they were developed. I have employed the PaR methodology in order that those attending the work will be enabled to understand the site through words but also through other senses. In experiencing the research works in the space, information is received and processed holistically by the mind and body. Indeed, live performance work is comprised of a 'multiplicity of factors' that can only be understood through experience (Freeman, 2010:x). Furthermore, I have developed my work as a theatre maker and a writer over the past decade, through study and practice. Therefore, the route I chose for this study allowed me to employ these skills throughout, both in the research and dissemination (see Gray, 1996).

A common debate within PaR discourse is whether the methodology is regarded as a branch of qualitative research, or whether it should be understood as a separate paradigm. Smith and Dean (2011:4), for example, argue that 'conceptual research' (within which they position research in the creative arts) 'is often seen to sit within the qualitative tradition but is not necessarily identical with it'. While it seems common for PaR researchers to borrow methods from the qualitative tradition, several theorists argue that the methodology itself should be understood as a 'third paradigm' (Haseman, 2007:150).

Within my research, I tend towards the understanding of PaR as a separate research paradigm, due to the specific set of skills necessary for developing and analysing art as a research work. As Sullivan (2011:62) argues:

there is acceptance that traditional systems for knowledge that rely on probable outcomes or plausible interpretations cannot fully respond to the challenge of new interpretive possibilities

The use of myth and the subjective nature of art do not easily fit into existing paradigms.

Several scholars have, therefore, argued for PaR to be understood as a methodology in its own right, rather than as a branch of qualitative work (see Haseman, 2007; Sullivan, 2011; Nelson, 2013). The exploration of site through performance practice can only be fully explored and theorised through the use of PaR. Furthermore, given the efficacy of creative work in accessible knowledge exchange, I would argue that the acceptance and growth of PaR as a separate paradigm can only lead to novel and compelling approaches to research in the creative arts.

In understanding PaR as a paradigm in its own right, it is also important to accept that it covers a wide range of artistic activity, and that 'there is no one "cookie-cutter" template (...) that can be applied across disciplines and projects' (Haseman, 2007:154). In order to develop my own specific method of employing PaR, I turned to Smith's (2010) concept of mythogeography as a methodological framework. In his writing on mythogeography, Smith (2010:9) gives particular examples of how he applies the creative, 'anti-wayfinding' approach in practice. One example of this is his discussion of exploring unguarded yet technically closed spaces (Smith, 2010). I used this approach throughout the process of creating *In Hidden Spaces* as it allowed those involved in that project to explore aspects of Rozelle House which were not public-facing or tourist friendly. The use of collective walking as a tool for disrupting notions of space and place was employed in the creation of *CauseWay*, where our movement as a group across the site became a protest against the

hegemonic, androcentric narratives within it (Smith, 2010). Furthermore, during the rehearsal process for *Souvenir*, solo walking, similar to that described by Smith (2010), was used as a tool to explore the rhythms and ostensibly unremarkable features of the space.

While Smith's work was used in practical terms as a theoretical framework for the development of the performances, the ideas of different performance scholars and those from other disciplines informed the work throughout. I began the *In Hidden Spaces* project by handing the performers Pearson's (2010) list of questions to ask when exploring a space, which involved investigating both physical and perceptual understandings of the space we were working in. These questions encouraged the performance artists to interrogate their immediate impressions of Rozelle House. In order to imbue the creative processes with the notion of Soja's (1980) socio-spatial dialectic, those working on *In Hidden Spaces* and *Souvenir* (myself included) continually discussed how we understood the space(s), how this was changing and what had led to these changes. Furthermore, relationships to and conceptualisations of the performance sites were discussed at length with audience members and performers in the post-performance focus groups for each work. By foregrounding stories of women in the space, we brought into question the problematic, gender-based issues inherent in heritage spaces, thereby applying the questions raised by Massey (1994) and Smith (2008) to the selected sites.

In discussing the methodological construction of the performances in this study, it is necessary to acknowledge the human contribution. Each of the performances drew upon the skills and stories offered by a variety of individuals. In the first instance, the creative teams and audiences for each project had a significant impact upon the public performances; indeed, performers and audience alike must be understood as active agents within the performance 'spectacle' (Rancière, 2011:8). In addition to this, there are

two particular elements of the performance projects that necessitate elucidation: friendship and reminiscence. In Chapters 5 and 6 I discuss care within artistic practice. I argue that the development of a care-full process grew from evolving artistic friendships. MacDonald (2010) has called for a deeper understanding of the interplay between friendship and creative practice, noting that it is often integral to the artistic working process. Throughout this thesis I use the names of performers (all of whom waived their anonymity) because their presence and their friendship was at the core of the performances created, and their contribution must be acknowledged.

In addition to this, I wish to note the contribution of community participants to the creation of *Souvenir*. The interplay between heritage and community holds great significance for how we interpret and respond to our own social groupings (Crooke, 2010). Furthermore, the lives of 'ordinary' women are so often excluded from the narratives presented in heritage sites (Smith, 2008). Therefore, I carried out three reminiscence sessions where women and men from South Ayrshire were invited to share their stories of growing up or living near the beach. Participants were all older adults (65 and above) and were members of various community groups in the region. Those who wished to contribute their stories to the final performance work were asked to indicate this on their consent form. By participating in these sessions, respondents were able to contribute to a tangible form of living heritage, which is becoming a valued facet of recorded history (Nicholson, 2012).

My research within the specific heritage sites has been suffused with moments and interactions during which notable changes in spatial relations occurred: for example, using Rozelle House as a playground for hide and seek, or reclaiming Poet's Path as a route for protest. Such moments took place by virtue of the creative team and the audience being physically present in the space. Furthermore, one of the key aims of this study is to

understand the impact that the socio-spatial dialectic can have upon site-specific performance. These ideas can only be partially explored through a written exegesis. It is vital that the relationship between the performance and the space be analysed and presented within the site in order to comprehend the effects of interrelations between performer, audience and site. To offer only a written analysis means that the audience cannot respond to the site or to the performance itself.

Throughout the creation of each performance, spatial relations were foregrounded within the devising and rehearsal of the work. The renewed understandings of the spaces that occurred were then communicated in the medium of performance. Developing my findings into performance works rendered the dissemination of my research more accessible (Sullivan, 2011). Furthermore, it allowed the audience to experience the reconfiguration of the site *in situ* rather than simply read about it. Indeed, the immediate impact of viewing live performance is difficult to express in a written reflection, as Haseman (2007:148) notes:

a continued insistence that practice-led research be reported primarily in the traditional forms of research (words or numbers) can only result in the dilution and ultimately the impoverishment of the epistemological content embedded and embodied in practice

Site-specific performance work offers a range of visual, aural, physical and emotional stimuli. While this can be explored through written analysis, the experience of viewing the performance cannot be encapsulated in words alone.

3.4 Analysis, exegesis and bricolage

The written exegesis of a PaR PhD has been deemed 'crucial to articulating and harnessing the outcomes' of the practical works (Barrett, 2007:5). While I do not argue that it is essential for PaR theses to be accompanied by a separate written exegesis, I intended

to use this format for the dissemination of my work from the outset of the study. It may be the case that practice-only PhDs become more prominent within the academy. However, the most widely-employed style, at present, is to accompany practice with a written document, and it is also the required submission format at the University of the West of Scotland. Furthermore, I concur with Barrett's (2007) assertion that the written exegesis can provide a valuable and tangible documentation of the performance work for those who wish to employ the processes and techniques in future research.

The written exegesis of this study is a theoretically-informed analysis of the performances created, with each chapter centred on a different element of the performance product. Chapter 4 focuses on the audiences' experience of the performance; in Chapter 5 the emphasis is placed on the relationship between the artists and the site; and in Chapter 6 the artistic process is the primary focus. Within my research I made use of interviews, questionnaires and focus groups in order to gain an understanding of a range of perspectives on the performances. As aforementioned, Haseman (2007) notes that using such methods within PaR is relatively commonplace. The responses collected were combined with my own reflections on the work in order to identify the key themes occurring, and these themes form the basis of the written exegesis. In compiling this analysis, I used a form of theoretical bricolage, employing a 'critical, multi-perspectival, multi-theoretical and multi-methodological' lens to explore the themes identified (Rogers, 2012:1). In this section I explore first the methods of gathering data, followed by the use of thematic analysis and bricolage in compiling an exegesis.

The first set of focus groups, carried out after *CauseWay*, resulted in a low response rate. While several audience members noted their interest in attending, some were unable to attend the specific times of the focus groups and others cancelled on the day. As a result

of this, I decided to use questionnaires in order to cover a wider range of participants who, for a variety of reasons, did not participate in the focus groups. The table below illustrates the response rate for each method.

CauseWay	In Hidden Spaces	Souvenir
Total audience: 65	Total audience: 57	Total: 33
Focus Group: 17	Focus Group: 4 (performers)	Conversation: 2 (performers)
Questionnaire: 12	Questionnaire: 40	Questionnaire: 22

It should be noted that the relatively high uptake of the *CauseWay* focus group was due to a large group of performance students attending en masse and, in fact, only two other audience members attended a separate group. It was due to this that, for *In Hidden Spaces* and *Souvenir*, I decide to exclusively use questionnaires for the audience. After each of these projects I carried out a focus group with the performers from *In Hidden Spaces* and facilitated a conversation with my collaborator from *Souvenir*. I use the term conversation rather than *interview* to reflect the egalitarian, dialogical nature of the session (see Stern, 2016). My original intention to use focus groups stemmed from the understanding that ‘focus groups are a direct method of obtaining rich information within a social context’ (Robinson, 1999:905). The inference here is that focus groups allow for a more profound level of reflection and feedback than quantitative surveys and questionnaires. I would add to this that focus groups allow for tangential discussion due to their interactive nature that can, in turn, reveal a new set of considerations and themes to be employed in theorising the performance work (Robinson, 1999). However, given that the responses were vital in carrying out my analysis, the decision to include questionnaires as a secondary method was a pragmatic one.

The dynamic, open nature of the focus group means that 'participants hear other peoples' responses and are allowed to make additional comments as they go along' (Robinson, 1999:906). This reflects the shared experience of a theatre audience; unless a work is created in a one-to-one format, it will not be viewed alone. The presence of others can, arguably, impact upon the reading of the work just as much as the performance itself. Therefore, a synergy exists between the viewing of a performance and the focus group format. Ideas and responses are formed and challenged through group interaction. This lead both myself and members of the focus groups to reconsider our standpoint on various issues. For example, during the *In Hidden Spaces* focus group a number of issues (such as perceptions of safety within a group and the importance of care in the process) were raised that hadn't been previously considered by myself or other group members.

While focus groups did not cover every audience member, the sessions I facilitated allowed for an exchange of viewpoints and insights in a relaxed atmosphere. Robinson (1999:906) notes that 'jokes, teasing and arguing' are often part of the focus group dynamic. She goes on to argue that

this enables complex dimensions to be revealed that are not accessed by more traditional methods and can identify cultural values and group norms as a result of the shared an common knowledge
(Robinson:ibid)

The differences I noted across the focus groups allowed me to understand how the differing frames of reference contributed to the various conceptualisations of the performance works. As an example, one of the *CauseWay* focus groups was carried out with a class of final year performance students, ranging in age from 20-25. The other had an older age range (55-65), and none of the participants had studied or worked in the theatre industry. Therefore, the level of assumed knowledge differed between the two groups. I was aware that with the students I could use theatrical shorthand, and discuss theoretical concepts that they were familiar with. In the second focus group, some

participants struggled more to unpack the piece as they had never particularly engaged with political performance work before. The varied experience of the participants was clearly a contributing factor in the sessions, and impacted upon the course of the dialogue within them. While no response is more correct than the other, the varying levels of expertise amongst audience members must be acknowledged.

While still noting that they were not my primary method of data collection, it is necessary here to note the value of questionnaires and interviews within my work. Before developing the final public performances of *CauseWay*, I interviewed two members of staff at the RBBM. These interviews were semi-structured, in order that the participants would have more flexibility of input and control over the direction of the session (Drever, 1995). The data from these interviews was employed to contextualise the RBBM space rather than in the development of the performances. In terms of the *In Hidden Spaces* and *Souvenir* questionnaires, which were distributed and collected immediately after the performance, the 60-70 per cent response rate demonstrates that a far higher number of audience members were able to offer feedback on the work. The *CauseWay* questionnaire also received a high response rate. Unfortunately, this questionnaire was only available online which made access difficult for those without access to computers. In comparing the methods I used, it should be noted that the depth of data and flexibility of inquiry within the focus group setting is desirable. However the social element of the focus group method can lead to pressure to conform to dominant opinions (Geis et al, 1986). Furthermore, Robinson (1999:908) argues for the use of questionnaire after the focus group as it gives space for 'private comments'. This clearly indicates the benefit of questionnaires as, given the previous findings about group dynamics, this is a chance for participants to bring up issues that they could not comfortably state within the group discussion.

The transcripts from the focus groups and the questionnaire data were the first sections of data to be analysed for the written exegesis. That analysis of art, particularly art created by the researcher, can be subjective is not to be understood as necessarily problematic (Barrett, 2007). The subjectivity of my analysis brings with it a profoundly personal account of the creation of the performances in this study. However, the use of reflective accounts from performers and audience members provided an additional perspective on the work, offering a fuller understanding of the performance events. I began my analysis by drawing themes from the accounts of audience members and performers involved in the project.

In order to do this, I employed semantic thematic analysis, through which 'the themes are identified within the explicit or surface meanings of the data' (Braun & Clarke, 2006:13). This can be understood in relation to latent thematic analysis, which explores the underlying reasons for the responses given (Braun & Clarke, 2006). I used this form of analysis due to the nature of the enquiry; I was not looking to analyse the participants themselves, but rather to allow them to report their experiences. Therefore, rather than attempt to explore latent issues and group dynamics, I employed the accounts given as an accurate representation of how each individual had perceived the performance discussed. Key words and phrases continued to appear in the transcripts and, when related to the theoretical framework of the study, I found that the primary themes were mobility, characterisation, accuracy and care. These themes were then used as a basis for the written analysis of each performance.

The construction of this exegesis combined reflections from the audience and performers involved with theoretical lenses of three academic disciplines that have informed the study as a whole: human geography, performance studies and heritage studies. Rather than using a single framework, I found that combining these areas allowed for a form of

theoretical bricolage that permitted me to explore the performance works from a variety of angles. Bricolage is a relatively new theoretical concept within the academy, and Rogers (2012:1) defines the term thus:

Generally speaking, when the metaphor is used within the domain of qualitative research it denotes methodological practices explicitly based on notions of eclecticism, emergent design, flexibility and plurality. Further, it signifies approaches that examine phenomena from multiple, and sometimes competing, theoretical and methodological perspectives.

It is this process of piecing together theories and ideas in order to create new performance works and, in turn, to analyse and interpret them that is the cornerstone of my work. The research carried out draws from and contributes to a variety of disciplines and, therefore, it would be inappropriate to use only one academic discipline as a framework for the study.

The forging of new understandings through combining theoretical frameworks affords a distinct and unique perspective to new research. As Kellner (1999:xii) argues:

the more perspectives one can bring to their analysis and critique, the better grasp of the phenomena one will have and the better one will be at developing alternative readings and oppositional practices

The bricolage method advocates interdisciplinary study and, while still engaging with the structures of specific disciplines on a profound level, embraces the use of perspectives drawn from different academic fields (Kincheloe, 2001). Indeed, as Denzin (2010:423) notes, bricolage necessitates not only drawing from a number of theories but employing 'many different interpretive practices and methodological tools'. As PaR scholars have been seen to make use of qualitative methods in their work, I argue that there exists a synergy between this and the multi-disciplinary nature of bricolage. Both the PaR methodology and the bricolage method are rooted in an understanding of the potential of combining methods and disciplines. Bricolage has allowed me to consider not only the theatrical relevance of my practice, but also the implications for explorations of heritage consumption and the construction of spatial relationships. With this in mind, and with an

understanding of the methods used in the study, the three chapters that follow will discuss each performance in turn. In these chapters, I explore the process of employing a PaR methodology in the development of performance work, while also reflecting on the theoretical implications of the performances themselves.

4. CauseWay: The Story of the Alloway Suffragettes

4.1 Introduction

This chapter explores the creation and performances of *CauseWay: The Story of the Alloway Suffragettes*, which was presented at the Robert Burns Birthplace Museum (RBBM), Alloway on the 10th, 11th and 12th of October 2015. This was a site-specific, promenade work. It was developed to be performed specifically at the RBBM and the performers physically led the audience to different locations throughout it. The performers were cast in roles and given scripts, rather than taking part in a devising process. The piece told the true story of Ethel Moorhead and Frances Parker, played by

Fig. 1: Broughton and Reid performing the opening scene behind the RBBM

Annaliese Broughton and Pamela Reid respectively⁴. Both women were active in the fight for women's suffrage and, in July 1914, they cycled to Alloway and attempted to blow up Burns' Cottage. Moorhead escaped, but Parker was caught and subjected to violent force-feeding in prison before escaping. For the benefit of the reader, I will first give a brief synopsis of the work. Throughout *CauseWay* the line between performer and character was by no means firm⁵, with Broughton and Reid playing both the characters and versions of themselves as tour guides at various points, therefore I use the form of Performer/Character names to acknowledge this.

4.2 Performance summary

The performance began behind the RBBM with Broughton and Reid introducing the site and the story in the style of tour guides before becoming the characters of Moorhead and Parker (see Fig. 1). After Broughton performed a verbatim speech from a 1913 Ayrshire anti-suffrage meeting, the performers led the audience away from their seats and onto an obscure path that curved round the side of the museum. The performers here picked up bikes, and the audience followed on foot. The performance then moved to the front of the museum, and along Poet's Path (which links the RBBM and Burns' Cottage). The performers would stop periodically along this path to tell of the journey from Glasgow to Alloway on bicycle. This section was also accompanied by original music from Ayrshire musician Jamie McGeechan aka Little Fire. At the end of Poet's Path, the audience followed the performers into the grounds of Burns' Cottage, and then into the cottage itself. Here the performance departed from realism, with the performers breaking into Burns songs and revealing their partial omniscience as they discussed the outcomes of WWI and the links between Burns and feminism. The piece then moved back into the world of the

⁴ All performers mentioned have waived their right to anonymity in this thesis.

⁵ The shifts between character and performer in *CauseWay* can be understood as a starting point for the flexible characterisation model developed during this study

story as the performers assembled a pipe bomb behind the cottage, only to be caught and chased by the night watchman (played by McGeechan). In the final scenes, Broughton/Moorhead stood in the fields next to the cottage and told of the chase, and of Parker's capture. After a brief reunion between the characters, the performance moved to the Education Pavilion next to the cottage where Parker's court speech was performed (based, in part, on documentation of the real speech given in 1914).

I kept reflective journals during each of the performances and have used these as data sources in analysing the development of each work. The reflective journal I kept during the rehearsal and performance period was based on immediate impressions of the work. I documented my thoughts and feelings on what I saw, rather than presenting a detailed analysis. By documenting the work in this way, I attempted to capture the experience of an audience member and offer an account that was not necessarily rooted in the theoretical basis of this study (as far as is possible). In this chapter I combine these observations with the theoretical framework in order to offer an analysis of the performance that is as complete as possible, representing the lay and academic context. In the weeks surrounding the performances I interviewed two senior members of staff at the RBBM and carried out focus groups with audience members. I also offered the audience a chance to participate in an online survey were they unable to attend a focus group. Of the 65 audience members, 25 participated in the surveys, ranging in age from 20-68.

In order to begin my analysis of the performance, I first employed semantic thematic analysis to organise the audience responses (Braun & Clarke, 2006). I did not directly ask audience members about their impressions of gender, performance and spatial identities. Instead I asked more general questions and have used the answers collected to gain an insight into the overarching perceptions of the audience. I have combined data from

audience feedback with extracts from my reflective performance journal in order to offer a variety of perspectives on the performance, its impact and its relationship with the RBBM site. The key themes I ascertained from the audience responses were that of mobility and the relationship between site and gender. Combining these with my own reflections and issues arising in current writing on heritage performance, the question of historical accuracy also holds significance. In this chapter I will discuss each of these in turn, drawing from journal extracts, excerpts from the script (indicated through the use of Courier New font) and relevant literature in order to offer an understanding of the work that is as full and as nuanced as possible.

4.3 Mobility and *CauseWay*

As noted in my article on the creation of *CauseWay*, there is a precedent for discussions of the relationship between feminism and mobility (Bianchi, 2016). Wilkie (2015:3) has incorporated the global 'mobility turn' into her performance research. She has also, more specifically, explored the interplay between mobility and site-specific theatre (Wilkie, 2012). *CauseWay*, then, can be viewed as somewhat of a performance-based Venn diagram; a meeting point of feminism, mobility and site-specificity. One of the major objectives of the performance was to create a practical dissemination of the connections within this diagram: to demonstrate how these three concepts can be integrated in the exploration of Herstory. In the section that follows, I consider the effect of this integration upon audience members and upon the performance itself.

One of the key tools in the evaluation of *CauseWay* was my aforementioned reflective journal, developed from photos and a diary kept during rehearsals and performance. The following extract, discussing a section on Poet's Path (see Fig. 2), recalls a particular moment of connection between site, Herstory and mobility:

As we approach, Parker stands atop a stone wall, her bike propped up nearby, and an aeroplane passes by overhead. It's a moment where the centuries clash together, where the difficulties of Parker and Moorhead's journey are contrasted by the cheap and easily-available flights that criss-cross the globe on a minute-by-minute basis. I am struck by how the suffragette movement contributed so much to the mobility enjoyed by women in the UK today.

This kind of serendipitous association is made possible specifically by the medium of the performance. It is the site and the interaction with the public sphere that allows the Herstorical narrative to fuse with the variety of contemporary mobilities that are hidden from view within a traditional theatre space (by which I mean a room with a stage and a

Fig. 2: Reid/Parker addresses the audience on Poet's Path. Photograph reproduced with written consent from photographed subjects.

seated audience). As noted by Pearson (2010:1) 'site is frequently a scene of plenitude, its inherent characteristics, manifold effects and unruly elements always liable to leak, spill and diffuse into performance'. As I note in Chapter 2, site is understood as physical yet malleable; a defined place within a place that remains susceptible to spatial shifts. The site

creates the performance, both in development and in the moment of the live sharing. In this instance, the mobile nature of the performance (the section discussed above travelled along Poet's Path) allowed the site to 'leak' into the work, and to enact the relationship between feminism, mobility and site-specificity.

In the feedback gathered from audience members, mobility was continually noted as an important feature in the work. Several respondents discussed how the promenade style of the performance engendered a sense of empathy with the characters. The following is a response from focus group participant FG1K, discussing the section of the performance where the characters were chased into the fields behind the cottage. In this instance, the participant is referring to the moment she ran after Broughton/Moorhead into a field, when the audience was supposed to remain behind the gate:

I think we felt invested in it because we were almost on the journey with them. So, like, when they'd stop and talk to us it would be like, 'oh, we must keep going, our legs are sore' and you almost felt that with them. You felt this power through, power on, even by the pace that we were moving as well, and I do think that's why, I do apologise for going in the non-entry zone, but, like, that's why I felt so... I was almost like 'oh my god, this woman's getting attacked, what's going on? I need to run after her'. I felt like I was involved in the performance because I was like 'oh my gosh, this is getting serious' and we were, like, worried for her.

It is clear that the mobile form of the work played an important role in her engagement with the work. Of walking and pathways, Urry (2007:63) writes that 'people can imagine themselves treading the same paths as earlier generations as a given path comes to be iteratively impressed into the ground'. As was evident in the discussions of *CauseWay*, the audience was able to imagine the journey undertaken by Parker and Moorhead due to the mobile nature of the performance. They were moving towards the same destination as these women had, perhaps even following the same path. This generated a sense of connection between the audience, the performers and the real women upon whom the piece was based.

Fig. 3: Broughton/Moorhead details the aftermath of the attempted bombing.

The words 'relate' and 'invest' were used a great deal in this particular focus group, which led me to ask why this was important for them. As participant FG1K explained, 'the idea of relating to a character means that you understand what they're feeling, you understand the issues that they're going through'. Forming an attachment and relating to the characters was deemed important in engaging with the themes and 'issues' of the performance. This connection between performer and audience member should be viewed as key in reconfiguring the heritage site, a space that 'may be produced *through and in* interaction' (Pearson, 2010:13, original emphasis). In *CauseWay*, this interaction generated a connection between the performance and those watching, affording the opportunity for the site to be transformed, even if only for a moment. In terms of reclaiming

the RBBM as a feminist space, the audience responses suggested that the use of mobility within the performance prompted an engagement with the Herstorical issues of the piece.

The investment in the piece noted by some audience members can be understood as borne of the group dynamic that is, in turn, generated through the mobile configuration of the audience. Mobility has a formational impact upon collective identities, as 'movements are located within and help to constitute different kinds of 'society'' (Urry, 2007:17). In the case of *CauseWay*, the movement of the performers established the narrative world of the piece, but also brought the group together inasmuch as we were marked out from the rest of the visitors and villagers. We (the audience) clearly moved together, with a shared purpose, much like a tour group organised by the museum. Our mobility gave us added visibility within Alloway, marking us out and marginalising us from the rest of the community. In this way, parallels can be drawn with the mobile audience and political protestors (such as suffragettes): both are visibly different from others in the space; both have a distinct purpose. Furthermore, due to the subject matter of *CauseWay*, a feminist agenda underwrote the audience's mobility. In this way, the 'society' we created mirrored, to an extent and for a limited time, the marches and the politics of the Women's Social and Political Union (WSPU).

A number of physical and cognitive factors affect our experience of being in a site, for example, whether one walks to get to the site and is, therefore, tired; whether one has been somewhere like this before; and whether the site brings back memories. Experiences and perceptions such as these are embodied, and all of this impacts upon our reception of a performance (see Merleau-Ponty, 1945). Our mobility as people, or lack thereof, is just one of a set of 'multiple contingencies of subjective response, context, and environment which condition an individual's interpretation of a particular performance

event' (Freshwater, 2009:5). The promenade style of the performance work, and the varying levels of difficulty this holds for different audience members, creates another physical 'contingency' that impacts upon their reading. In the case of *CauseWay*, while the individual nature of each audience member's experience cannot be denied, the promenade style of the work seemed to engender a sense of collectivism. The group moved as one and, if nothing else, had the experience of journeying along this particular path on this particular day in common. Embarking upon a literal journey with the characters creates a shared understanding: we have created a mobile community, our bodies move in harmony, and we have the perception of knowing each other better because of it (see Urry, 2007).

There are, however, problems surrounding issues of accessibility with this style of performance. In order to further understand the impact of mobility in performance, I turn once more to Wilkie (2012:208):

Even when site-specific practice is conceived as intrinsically tied to the physicality and meanings of one site, and therefore in some ways immobile, attending it often requires a different kind of mobility of its audience than the usual modes of theatre-going.

Attending a site-specific performance, even one in which the audience is standing still, is a greater physical undertaking than sitting in a chair to watch a performance. In *CauseWay*, further physical demands were placed on the audience through the requirement to walk, which in turn impacted upon the reading of the work, and not always in a positive way. One audience member, for example, noted her friend's 'mobility issues', indicating that this had made following the performers difficult (Participant SM5). Walking itself is influenced by our past experiences, as 'each kind of walking involves a set of bodily techniques, each dependent upon different pre-cognitive ways of anticipating how to be in the world that surrounds and constructs each person' (Urry, 2007:64-65). The ways in which we walk

around any terrain are underwritten by tacit knowledge that has developed through interactions with different terrain and the journeys we have undertaken (Ingold, 2008). I argue that, just as our mobility is influenced by our experiences, our experiences are influenced by our mobility. The experience of watching *CauseWay* was underwritten by the varying levels of mobility of each audience member, and, while this was generally viewed positively, it must be acknowledged that it presented problems for certain audience members.

On cycling

Within *CauseWay*, the bicycle functioned not only as a historically accurate method of transport, but also as a symbol of women's liberation. Bikes were key in enhancing the mobility of Western women in the late nineteenth and early twentieth century (Urry, 2007). Furthermore, cycling was noted by Susan B. Anthony to have 'done more to emancipate women than anything else in the world' (Bly, 1896:n.p.). However, as access to cars has increased, other forms of movement have had to compete with this 'ferocious enemy' (Urry, 2007:76). During the performance, the tension between the slow, physically arduous mobility of those on foot or bicycle was presented directly alongside the swift ease of those travelling in cars. At the end of Poet's Path, the audience stopped and could see clearly onto the road. Broughton/Moorhead highlighted this by referring to the white lines that had been added to public roads in 1914, drawing attention to the traffic rather than attempting to pretend it didn't exist. Furthermore, later scenes took place directly beside main roads, and at points dialogue had to pause as a particularly loud van or lorry drove past. The bicycles, emancipating and unrestrained by road signs or traffic, competed with the bulk and the roar of the powerful car engines. In this way, the performance struggled against the sound of the traffic, symbolising the struggle of Parker and Moorhead against the dominant politics of their time.

Mobility and Gender

In recent years a shift has occurred within various disciplines of arts and social science research towards exploring paradigms of mobility. This shift, termed by Urry (2007:6) as the 'mobility turn', has provided a strong basis for discussion of interactions between people and various methods of transport. It should be noted, however, that much discourse surrounding mobility has traditionally taken a male perspective (Heddon & Turner, 2012). Discussing what one might term the flâneurs of pre- and Victorian London, Urry (ibid:67) notes that,

for single, upper-class, heterosexual, young men, rambling involved walking without a definite route, distracted and concerned with adventure, entertainment and sexual pleasure. Rambling converts the city into a space of flows with women on the streets being made visible, on display, waiting to be 'consumed'.

While Urry's remarks here refer to cities in the 18th and 19th centuries, echoes of such patterns remain in contemporary society. Women feel far less safe walking alone through a city, particularly at night, which has led to intervention through political marches such as Reclaim the Night (reclaimthenight.co.uk). While mobility has increased exponentially, the freedom to inhabit and move through places and spaces remains to some extent the privilege of males.

Within *CauseWay*, the mobility of the characters challenged the inhibition of female mobility, while also highlighting through their ironic oration that this is not just a historical problem.

FRANCES

My legs keep moving so that those women, and those men, they can have a voice, and so that, maybe not today, but maybe 100 years from now we can have equal rights and fair pay and abuse and assault will lead to trials and convictions.

While audience responses clearly indicated that the mobility of *CauseWay* prompted an engagement with the stories of the characters, links were not explicitly made between mobility and feminism. That women's equality was a key theme of the piece was clear to many of respondents, which leads to the question of how mobility interacted with issues of gender in the performance.

To begin with, the journey along Poet's Path was framed as entwined with the struggle for women's suffrage, highlighted by Frances Parker's speech:

FRANCES

My legs keep moving because they have to, because they are obliged to. They are obliged to keep the wheels turning, keep pushing forward for those who can't...those who don't understand. The women and the men all over this great nation who base their lives around the belief that our two sexes are fundamentally, irretrievably different. My legs ache more and more as they push me forward, and I can feel a burning in them that matches the fire of rage that burns in my chest. All the while I think of those who believe that one half of civilisation is only good for matters of the home, matters of childcare, for needlepoint and piano playing. The people who think that we only fight for equal rights because we hate men, or we have nothing better to do with our time. I think of them as the miles roll by, and my legs keep moving.

Here the mobility of Parker and Moorhead is directly aligned with first-wave feminism, and the audience in turn became party to this mobile protest. Following from Massey's (1994:11) assertion that female mobility is 'gender disturbing', the text of *CauseWay* demonstrably intertwined mobility with a struggle against traditional concepts of gender; the mobility of these women was shown to be essential in their fight against patriarchy.

The key aim of the *CauseWay* project was to offer a renewed, feminist interpretation of the RBBM site. The reconfiguration of androcentric concepts and spaces requires a departure from traditional forms of knowledge, understanding and dissemination. As Braidotti (1994:1-2) notes:

I feel a real urgency to elaborate alternative accounts, to learn to think differently about the subject, to invent new frameworks, new images, new modes of thought. This entails a move beyond the dualistic conceptual constraints and the perversely monological mental habits of phallogentrism. I take it as the task of the feminist – as of other critical intellectuals – to have the courage to face up to the complexity of this challenge.

While the performance of *CauseWay* offered a feminist interpretation of the RBBM site, it must be acknowledged that the performance existed within and made use of overarching patriarchal structures. Gender relations impact upon both human and spatial interactions (Massey, 1994), and the social world continues to be conceptualised through the omnipresent binary of man vs. woman. To apply a feminist lens to social processes is to understand that modern language developed in line with patriarchy, and that words often viewed as neutral have their roots in the subordination of women (Spender, 1980). *CauseWay* had some of the features of a traditional play (with a script and linear narrative) that was developed for a specific site, and as such language was the primary method of communication used by the performers. The use of mobility should be understood as a response to logocentrism; it offered the audience a chance to connect physically with the piece. Where language can be viewed as patriarchal, there is the possibility that an embodied, phenomenological interpretation can offer an alternative, feminist experience (see Embree & Fisher, 2000). In this sense, mobility was employed in the performances to generate a phenomenological understanding of the characters through the shared experience of moving.

4.4 Herstorical (in)accuracy

Theatre practice is, at least traditionally, rooted in pretence. The script has come from the imagination of the writer, the performers are pretending to be their characters and inhabiting a world that has been carefully designed, constructed and placed on a stage. The acceptance of this pretence partially forms the basis on which the audience engages

with the work; to sit through a play continually reminding oneself that everything is false would, in all likelihood, result in a reading of the work quite different to that intended by the creative team. While there are exceptions to this, perhaps most notably Brecht's (1964) *Verfremdungseffekt* (alienation effect), the majority of realist plays ask the audience to regard the imagined world in which they exist as authentic, at least for an hour or two. Heritage performance, however, exists beyond traditional performance spaces, and in a site that claims to accurately represent the facts of historical existence. This begs the question of what an audience is willing to accept in terms of pretence or artistic license, i.e. does heritage performance need to offer an 'accurate' representation of history in order to be deemed a success? The following section explores the development of *CauseWay* in terms of the historical research undertaken, the tension between fact and fiction, and how perceptions of historical accuracy impacted upon the audience.

Finding Frances and Ethel

The story of Parker and Moorhead's attempted attack was recounted to me by the Learning Manager at the RBBM. In early conversations about the project I was given a brief overview of the facts; the women involved, the cycle to Alloway, the foiled attack and the imprisonment of Parker. While these fragments of information provided a valuable skeleton for the play, in order to develop the characters I felt it prudent to find more historical sources on the events. The necessity for strict adherence to fact in heritage performance has been debated. Tivers (2002), for example, suggests that the strength of such work comes not from specific facts or dates but from an interpretive representation of history that can reveal greater truths about the lives of marginalised people. However, at the beginning of the writing process, with a blank screen and little information about the lives of Parker and Moorhead, I needed to gain a more profound understanding of these women.

The route of the performance work was developed through a site-responsive devising practice, whereas the fictionalised characters of Parker and Moorhead were formed from media accounts of the event and the political climate of 1910s Ayrshire in addition to online archives concerning the women themselves. The employment of such documents, however, must come with the acknowledgement that they are an edited and biased account of events. Kidd (2011) notes that critiques of heritage performance have generally focused upon its perceived lack of authenticity, an evaluation which in itself has been criticised due to the fact that museums and heritage sites are restored interpretations of history. The editing process of historical documentation engenders the sense that it is impossible to give an 'authentic' account of the past, rendering the process of accurately representing a historical figure a complex and difficult task. Furthermore, as I noted in Chapter 1, Herhistorical documentation of women's lives is often insufficient. One strategy I used to integrate authenticity was to include verbatim monologues; in Scene 1 of the play, Broughton took on the character of Mrs Archibald Colquhoun, and delivered the same speech that she delivered at an Ayrshire anti-suffrage meeting in 1913 (see Appendix 1). It should be noted, however, that Broughton's performance was an interpretation of Colquhoun's words, and even verbatim performance cannot be offered as a complete and accurate representation of the past (Gibson, 2011).

Although there were moments in the script where the performers spoke exactly the words of the person they were portraying, for the most part I used sections from newspaper clippings and incorporated them into the words of the characters. In many places throughout the script this was necessary, given the scarcity of documented testimony. Frances Parker's final speech, for example, was crafted around a 1914 article about her court appearance. For the reference of the reader, in the section below I have put the verbatim phrases in bold:

FRANCES

As to the question of Robert Burns, you should know that we do not wish to attack the man and his works - in fact many of his writings resonate with our cause. **Burns once wrote of Robert the Bruce and the Scottish struggles for independence, "Liberty's in every blow, let us do or die"**. And that is exactly what we believe - we will strike blow upon blow until our cause is won, and we are happy to die for our beliefs. **You, all of you proud Scotsmen, you used to be so proud of your heroes like the Bruce, and now you have taken to torturing women.** I wonder what your heroes would say, those who fought so fiercely against oppression, to see you now oppressing the women of your country. No, we do not attack Robert Burns, but we attack the symbol of patriarchal power that you have bastardised him as - and that's why we attack his cottage.

The creative license taken here offered the audience the means to question the performance site. Rather than accept the RBBM at face value, this speech encouraged the audience to view the site as part of a larger problem of androcentrism in heritage, and acknowledge that it should not be accepted as 'politically or culturally neutral' (Smith, 2008:161). As in the work of Smith (2013), I wanted to encourage the audience to interrogate the site, specifically in terms of gender relations, by explicitly linking the cottage to patriarchal power structures.

Fact, fiction and mythogeography

During the development and rehearsal period of *CauseWay* the potential spaces of interaction and connectivity between site and performance revealed themselves in unplanned and fortuitous ways. The opening scene, for example, was placed in a rounded seating area at the back of the museum. During rehearsals, the performers began to play with the varying levels of the bench and the grass behind it, weaving in and out of the audience area so as to include them in the performative interactions occurring between the characters. In this scene, this bench started as a waiting area, became a space for protest, and then for oppression, as the following excerpt from my journal illustrates:

They set up a playful, friendly relationship before becoming galvanised by the classic suffragette chant “votes for women!”. At this point they begin to move in and out from behind the audience, including us in their chants, before turning on each other. Broughton takes on the role of antagonist, telling Reid to “go home and mind the baby”, and the performers shift once again to become attendees of a 1913 anti-suffrage meeting.

While this space had not originally played any role in Parker and Moorhead’s journey to Alloway, in this moment it became the beginning of the story. Furthermore, its identity continually shifted and alluded to the ‘inherently dynamic’ nature of the space (Massey, 1994:3). In layering the script onto the site we found the potential for the space to take on multiple identities within the world of the play, and for the performances to be shaped by its physical layout.

Thinking in terms of historically accurate representation, however, leads to the question of whether the places in which heritage performance is staged must themselves be accurate. Is it imperative to stand exactly where these women stood? Furthermore, if space reveals new ideas and concepts within the performance text, can these be included within the final piece without jeopardising its perceived accuracy? The relationship(s) between space(s) and the individual are in a state of constant flux; as we move through different spaces we bring and develop different perceptions, and our interactions with said spaces vary accordingly (Massey, 1994). In developing *CauseWay* I felt it more urgent to allow the spaces of performance to impact upon the work than to adhere rigidly to the historical facts of the journey. The site of the RBBM required room to breathe within the performance text, and to impact upon it.

In developing the relationship between performance and site, I turned to the concept of mythogeography posited by Smith (2013:103), who describes it thus: ‘sustaining the multiplicity of a place’s meanings against homogenisation and privileging trajectories over the bounding of place’. The journey of the characters, and the performance-based

discoveries that could be made within the site were prioritised over any notions of accuracy or fact. I would note here that, while the process of creating the performance drew from the concepts posited in mythogeography, Smith (2013) does advocate a more open, ambiguous engagement with site. Indeed, he proffers the 'actor-as-signpost' model, which rejects character and 'psychological acting' in favour of the performer gesturing outwards towards the site in order to highlight its heterogeneous narratives (Smith, 2009:159). While there were moments in *CauseWay* where the performers signalled out towards the space, it cannot be denied that the piece was rooted in psychological drama. This decision was made primarily due to the suffragette story being an obvious narrative to explore in my work at the RBBM. Furthermore, as posited by Rancière (2011:2-3) the energy inherent in the 'theatrical spectacle', regardless of its form, can be offered to the audience and allow them to be active participants in the co-creation of the experience. Therefore, the use of character can be viewed as an agent in this transfer of energy and can use internal conflict as a springboard to activate the audience's understanding and reconfiguration of space (Rancière, 2011).

The purpose of the performance was to offer new meanings of the site through eschewing the Burnsian narrative, but this required room for speculation. Herstorically accurate performance in heritage sites is almost impossible. At best, heritage sites underrepresent women's narratives and at worst they exclude them entirely (Aitchison, 1996). Therefore, the 'multiplicity of meanings' present within the site was allowed to trickle into the performance text: a semi-circular bench transformed the work and was transformed by it; a quiet pathway became a 40-mile journey; a small room within a cottage existed simultaneously in 1914 and 2015. Combining the exploratory nature of mythogeography with the transformative possibilities of the socio-spatial dialectic gave the performers license to reconfigure understandings of the site; to give rein to Parker and Moorhead's

story (Soja, 1980). The lack of evidence of these women's lives, instead of limiting the performance, enabled the performance to engage and interact with the site in a manner that may not have been suitable for a play concerned only with historical accuracy.

Authenticity and the audience

In the various responses given by the *CauseWay* audience, the concept of historical accuracy was not mentioned particularly frequently. The reasons for focusing upon this aspect of the work arose from data gathered by the Performance, Learning and Heritage (PLH) project (discussed in greater detail in Chapter 2). In one of several published disseminations of this project, Kidd (2011:26) notes that a perceived lack of 'authenticity' in heritage performance 'could also become a distraction, one instance of perceived inauthenticity becoming a primary focus (indeed an irritant) that proves an insurmountable hurdle in the meaning-making process'. Although Kidd (ibid:25) does not seek to explicitly define the term, she notes 'continuing analogies between authenticity and some sense of 'reality' or 'truth''. This highlights the apparent necessity, at least from an audience perspective, of rooting performance within historical accuracy.

While the questions asked of the *CauseWay* audience did not focus specifically on authenticity, one survey respondent in particular found certain perceived historical inaccuracies particularly problematic. In the section where they were invited to provide any additional comments, they stated that,

Fannie Parker's name as it appears in archival material should be used, some historical inaccuracies e.g Burns did not build the cottage (he left as a child), Fannie was New Zealand born and Oxbridge educated, Her citing of Burns and nationalism would have rankled at the time. (...) Don't forget that the women (matrons) involved in force feeding were culpable. Remember most Scottish GPs refused to force feed, hence the butcher at Perth prison.
(Participant SM1)

Of particular interest in this statement is that two of the 'mistakes' highlighted were never mentioned in the performance: Burns was not stated to have built the cottage, and the gender of those involved in force feeding was never mentioned. From this response I infer that the feminist nature of the work led the participant to believe that men were being blamed for Parker's suffering, rather than institutionalised misogyny, which exists regardless of gender (as was evident in Mrs Colquhoun's speech). Although this participant stated that they enjoyed the play, noting these errors seemed to be of great importance and clearly impacted upon their reading of the performance.

While noting that this comment came from only one of 25 participants, the strong objection to ostensibly incorrect information must be taken into consideration. Bohlin et al (2012: 654) argue that the conceptualisation of heritage as 'negotiated and unstable' has gained traction in heritage studies. In this instance, however, the participant in question viewed this performance as a concrete representation of truth. The pretence within which traditional plays operate may not be as readily accepted within the heritage site. Such spaces are 'cast as a receptacle[s] of history, indexical to time rather than part of it', and as such the information offered there, whether by plaque, tour guide or performer, is received as a true and accurate representation of the past (Parry-Davies, 2014:15). In order for audiences, or at least some members, to invest in the heritage performance text and engage with its thematic content, it seems that some importance must be placed on historical accuracy. The tension that arises, then, is between the need for authenticity and the artistic freedom to allow the space to tell the story.

4.5 Gender and site

One of the primary aims of the *CauseWay* project was to foreground gender issues within the RBBM site. While the museum itself focuses specifically on the life of Robert Burns, he

is not the only individual portrayed. Unfortunately, the representation of the men and women in his life conforms to the androcentrism present across the heritage industry in general (Smith, 2008). During an interview with one of the senior staff at the museum, the representation of Burns' parents was discussed:

The first object that you encounter that is about women is [Burns' mother] Agnes Broun (...) her milking stool is there next to the father's chair. So you have this interesting hierarchy; you have quite a high chair, which is the father's chair, and you have this low milking stool. Now, Agnes would have only used this in the byre to milk the cows, but they're brought together in the museum because that's simply all we've got on Agnes, but it's an interesting semiotic, really, that you've got a lowly chair for a woman and a high chair for a man. (Participant IRB1)

Whether intentionally or not, the placement of objects such as this convey 'secondary messages' (Katriel, 1997:68), which can support the sense of female subordination already engendered by the promotion of masculinist histories. During the interview noted above, it became clear that, while the museum is moving towards offering a more diverse interpretation of Burns and his life, it is not currently a space in which the values of feminism are promoted. The following section explores the response(s) of the audience in relation to the issues of gender raised in *CauseWay*. I also present a critical reflection on aspects of the performance that could be understood as lacking in engagement with theories of feminist performance practice.

Gendered space and the audience

In order to understand and interpret the audience's experience of *CauseWay*, it is important first to understand the audience itself. The play was first shown to a group of 4th year Performance students from University of the West of Scotland (UWS) on the 7th of October 2015 (during the rehearsal period), and the public performances took place on the 10th, 11th and 12th. Over the seven performances, the audience generally consisted of those who had booked tickets prior to the event. Although tickets were available at the front desk throughout the weekend to those visiting the museum, the uptake was low. This

meant that most of those who watched the piece had come specifically to the RBBM for that reason. Below is an account from my reflective journal of issues arising from my interactions with the museum staff:

Are box office promoting the performance? There seems to be an uncertainty about what the play is. No management present so no ticket numbers available. Perhaps one hour is too difficult to sell when visitors are not expecting it. Front of House, however, don't seem to know exactly what's going on. Marketing has not been pushed by museum. However, the aim is to interest typical heritage visitors, who seem happy to attend a guided tour. Money could be an issue, but this is a wealthy area. (...)No access to audience numbers as no managers are in. Is performance worthwhile if it only reaches those already interested? (...) Consultation with strategy and marketing would have been beneficial. I have to accept a level of culpability, as I assumed, rather than checked, that everything would run OK.

The key point in the above extract is the effectiveness of heritage performance when it is not promoted to all of those visiting the heritage site. Performance created only for those already interested in the issues represented can result in what Melrose (1998:132) has termed 'remarginalisation': creating theatre that is viewed as only relevant to select groups, and therefore lessening its impact upon society at large. While not every audience member would necessarily describe themselves as a feminist, they had generally sought out the performance, which indicates an interest in the suffragette narrative. Therefore, in the discussion that follows it is important to bear in mind that I do not claim the audience feedback is representative of all heritage site visitors: rather, it offers an insight into the experiences of a specific group of people who shared in the performance event.

The historical context of the performance played an important role in attributing meaning to the work, to the extent that several audience members noted a sense of relief that they did not have to grow up as a woman in Victorian times. One audience member noted:

It reminded me that if I had been born at a different time, I would not have had the opportunity to go to University and become a working mother with a career outwith the home environment. It was quite moving as it made me think about

the lengths people went to secure equal rights for us and that we shouldn't take it for granted.
(Participant SM2)

It is clear from this response that the participant believes women's equality has been achieved, at least in her own experience. The heritage setting of the piece may be problematic in this regard, as aligning the performance with history renders it unable to be perceived as representative of contemporary gender politics. That heritage contributes to the formation of identity is well recognised within the field of heritage studies. Heritage sites should not, therefore, be categorised as antiquated representations of days gone by that have no significant bearing upon contemporary life (Smith, 2008). Unfortunately, as was the case with this participant, it seems that the placement of *CauseWay* within the heritage site rendered the performance a representation of history rather than an allegorical account of gender issues in modern society.

The parallels between the suffragette struggle and modern day feminism were, however, apparent to several audience members. When asked about the prevalent themes of the play, Participant FG1R stated; 'I think the obvious one is equality, because we're still not quite there, are we? You know, it's moved forward but it hasn't moved forward enough'. This parallel was noted by a number of other participants, and the fight for women's equality arose as a clear theme in the responses overall. In this way, *CauseWay* highlighted the potential for exploring gender issues within the RBBM site. As Massey (1994) notes, our conceptualisations of space are connected to the narratives we bring to it, and the narratives we experience therein. Given that the majority of participants noted that the play emphasised the experience of women within the RBBM site, it follows that, at least for the duration of the performance work, it became a space focussed upon feminist debate. However, the work of Burns was also present within the piece, through the dominant identity of the space and the use of his songs. Rather than simply offering the

story of Burns or the story of the suffragettes, these 'phenomena' combined to create a new understanding of the multiple stories present in the site (Massey, 1994:4).

CauseWay: A feminist critique

During the development of *CauseWay* I continued to face theoretical obstacles in terms of creating a work that can be explicitly coded 'feminist'. The overarching narrative of the work raised many issues of gender and feminism, from a historical perspective and through parallels with contemporary society. Furthermore, the piece told the story of two first-wave feminists who fought for women's equality. In these ways, I argue that *CauseWay* was rooted in feminism, and contributed to debates surrounding the rights of women. While Austin (1990:136), argues that 'a feminist approach to anything means paying attention to women', there are other considerations to be acknowledged in terms of feminist performance practice, some of which are discussed in the following section.

If language can be understood as a patriarchal construct, it follows that text-based performance could also be interpreted thus (Spender, 1980). In developing the performance, I allowed for moments of silence, where the space and the bodies of the performers communicated their message without the use of spoken, text-based language:

We head into Burns' Cottage grounds to see Parker and Moorhead standing in front of their bikes in the manicured main garden. Their stance is defiant, and places them almost in opposition to the site; their politics and anger are a challenge to the quiet, bucolic nature of the space.

In this example from my reflective journal, the physicality of the performers poses a challenge to the site: the air of rebellion is communicated without words. However, the scenes that take place in the grounds of Burns' Cottage have been contextualised within the broader narrative of the piece, and the gender issues within it have been highlighted through dialogue. While I agree with the stance that language is rooted in patriarchy, it did not feel appropriate that this performance should be delivered entirely through image or

movement. The predominant method of communication used at the RBBM is that of language and, although it can reinforce the notion of 'male-as-norm', it is important that women retain the ability to use language without being ruled by patriarchal structures (Spender, 1980:3). In order to demonstrate the feminist potential of language, and to fit with the 'rules' of the site, I wanted to use words to tell the story of Parker and Moorhead (Wilkie, 2002:244).

In addition to the theoretically problematic use of language, it is important to acknowledge that the representations of Parker and Moorhead within the performance text were influenced by overarching concepts of gender. Indeed, the position of women and female characters in theatre has been problematised by Melrose (1998:131-132), who asks,

how do 'we' act like women (in theatres), if acting is indeed one aspect of a 'patriarchal' institution; which, if it has a determining role, must also have determined our perceptions and modes of (theatrical) representation of ourselves?

The relationship between theatre and gender is, indeed, complex. This question, however, has implications beyond the world of theatre and performance, as society and most of the institutions upon which it is based developed in a climate of patriarchy (Austin, 1990). If we accept that the notion of equality for women began with first-wave feminism, then this 150-year-old fight is only a speck in the maelstrom of human history.

The position of men within the performance is also worth consideration, particularly the roles given to them. The first time a male performer is seen is at the beginning of Poet's Path, described below in this extract from my journal:

As we make our way onto Poet's Path, Moorhead is standing up ahead of us on a raised embankment. Beside her is a musician (Jamie McGeechan), who sings an original song based upon the story of CauseWay. He is the first man that we have seen in the performance and, given the theme of misogyny inherent in the play, the reasons behind his presence seem unclear. Will this man be friend or foe to the cause? Moorhead continues to talk about the bicycle journey, and begins to illustrate her fears for the mission she is about to complete. She resolves that she will go through with it anyway, mounts her bicycle, and moves

off around the corner. As we follow her, McGeechan accompanies our walk with his pro-suffrage song.

The use of music in the performance was intended to have an alienating effect, breaking from the imaginary world of the performance and engendering a sense of reflection (Brecht, 1964). However, as neither Broughton nor Reid could play the guitar, McGeechan took on this role. Mark McCrone joined the group in Burns' Cottage to add a second line of guitar music while Broughton and Reid sang along. This decision was simply made due to the skills of the performers, and could be viewed as a contingency. While casting male performers is not necessarily problematic, I would note that relying on men to carry out roles that women were unable to is, from a feminist perspective, unfortunate. Furthermore, the only figure of designated legal authority present in the work was a night watchman portrayed by McGeechan. While the night watchman being male is true to the historical event, it reinforced the notion so problematically offered by the heritage industry that power and importance are aligned with patriarchy (Smith, 2008).

Our notions of gender, social relations and various languages all developed in a world where women were almost universally oppressed. Therefore, in creating written texts and female characters, as was the case with *CauseWay*, there must be an acceptance that such work could be critiqued as not truly feminist. The performance exists within and makes use of many patriarchal conventions and tools, and this must be viewed as problematic. Some specific examples of this include the dresses and make-up worn by the performers. These are generally understood as specifically for women, enhancing their aesthetic appeal for the male gaze, and therefore are difficult to interpret as feminist (Mulvey, 1975). Furthermore, the director/performer paradigm has been critiqued as aligned with patriarchal power structures, which I discuss further in Chapters 5 and 6. While *CauseWay* contributed to the canon of feminist performance, and to the narrative of the RBBM site, there are limits of the work that must be acknowledged.

4.6 Conclusion

Each of the performances in this study can be understood as building on the findings of the previous work. *CauseWay*, then, was prototypical in nature; it was the first performance created, where theories were being developed and concepts tested with only my theoretical – rather than practical – research to draw from. As noted in section 4.5, some audience members understood the work as historical rather than analogous of contemporary gender issues. Therefore, in developing *In Hidden Spaces*, I began to draw from the real experiences of the performers in addition to Herstorical accounts in order to accentuate the links between the past and present experiences of women. The work of Massey (1994) and Smith (2010), amongst others, continued to be used in order to understand and investigate the space. Furthermore, the director/performer paradigm was replaced with a collaborative approach in order to develop a more egalitarian process, all of which is discussed further in Chapter 5.

5. *In Hidden Spaces*: The untold stories of the women of Rozelle House

5.1 Introduction

This chapter is an account of *In Hidden Spaces*, the second performance of this thesis. This project took the form of a collaborative devising process based entirely at Rozelle House, Ayr which lasted from the 11th-22nd of July 2016. The performers involved in were Teri Beveridge, Annaliese Broughton (who performed in *CauseWay* and *Souvenir*), Poppy Lironi (who co-created and performed in *Souvenir*), Kirsty Mackenzie, Rebecca Wilkie⁶ and myself. All of these women are past or present students of the BA(Hons) Performance course at UWS and have waived their right to anonymity in this thesis. I employ the term

Fig. 4: The cast on the main staircase in Rozelle House

⁶ Not to be confused with Fiona Wilkie, author and academic

'collective' to refer to the team, by which I mean a group of individuals who work in collaboration, although not always all at the same time, a similar model to that used by companies such as 21Common, Fish and Game and Forced Entertainment. For example, some of the *In Hidden Spaces* performers were involved in the other performances. Our collective differed from a company in that it was more fluid and less binding; we drifted apart and together, rather than committing to collaborating on all future works.

During the process we used principles from Smith's mythogeography and explored discourses surrounding feminist theatre practice, particularly those relating to hierarchy. We combined performance experiments with the documented history of the house in order to explore the Herstory of the site. Our explorations and performance experiments resulted in four public performances at Rozelle on the 23rd and 24th of July 2016. Unlike the previous chapter on *CauseWay*, here the process of creation is the focus rather than the public performance. In exploring the process in more detail, I intend to elucidate the ways in which a prolonged engagement with the physical aspects of a site, in addition to its Herstory, can reconfigure a space for the individuals involved. However, I will begin by giving an account of the public performances in order to offer a full understanding of the project, before going on to explore the process in further detail.

5.2 Performance summary

The fragmented performance style of *In Hidden Spaces* was created to recapture the style of the development process. In reflective discussions we, the performers, noted how the freedom to explore the space, and the time afforded to quiet moments in unpeopled rooms, were key in reclaiming the space for ourselves. Early in the development process, we employed The Mythogeographical Manifesto (Smith, 2010:114-116) as a basis for spatial exploration. We dedicated a significant amount of time to being in the space,

looking around freely, sitting alone and eschewing preconceptions of what Rozelle House is and had been. This part of the process had a particularly strong influence on the formation of our work, and allowed for a 'completely different set of sensations from those enjoyed by the visitor on an organised jaunt' (Smith, 2010:115). We began to develop a sense of ownership within the space and wanted the audience to feel the same way. In order to achieve this we decided to offer the audience a sense of agency in the space; rather than guiding them along an obligatory route, we offered them maps. The maps illustrated where they could find performers in the house.

Four of the performances were in a one-to-one format and were repeated throughout the 45-minute performance period with different audience members. The other two pieces were durational, with the performers carrying out routines that lasted throughout the work. Also placed across the site were plaques with information about the women the performance was inspired by and headphones where audience members could listen to poetry and folktales that inspired or were inspired by our time at Rozelle. The piece ran for forty five minutes and, in that time, few audience members were able to experience every section of the work. Furthermore, the order in which each section was viewed was different for every audience member. Therefore there can be no definitive report of how the performance worked. Instead, the description that follows will cover the opening monologue, each of the six performances and the finale for which all members of audience were brought together in the courtyard. This account of the work attempts to offer as full an experience for the reader as possible. To this end, sections of text from the performance are included and indicated through the use of Courier New font (as in Chapter 4).

Broughton and Mackenzie met the audience in the vestibule of the house and performed a rhyming prologue, echoing the form of the opening scene in *CauseWay*. They offered the audience rules as to how to move around the house (see Appendix 2). After distributing

maps to the audience, Broughton and Mackenzie led them through to the main hallway where we (the other performers) were waiting on the staircase (see Fig. 4). Broughton and Mackenzie joined us on the stairs, at which point Lironi hummed a line from the protest song *Bread and Roses*. Broughton then instructed:

*Close your eyes and count to ten before you open them again. Then
we want you to come and find us.*

Once the audience had closed their eyes, each of us, the performers, ran to our allocated performance spaces within the house. The audience then opened their eyes and set off to look for performers.

On finding Beveridge, she pressed a button on a five-minute timer. The audience member was then sternly taught how to set up a tea tray for guests in no more than five minutes.

*So, to start with you'd ask me my name. Don't tell them yours, it
doesn't matter.*

After completing this task, Beveridge sat down to enjoy a cup of tea made by the audience member before dismissing them when the alarm on her timer sounded.

On finding Broughton they would either be asked to hide a Russian Doll or to teach her how to sew. This was followed a conversation about why she was in the house, that she had left her family who lived in Germany, and a request to a member of the audience to post a letter for her. Those who opened this letter read words inspired by the story of Susanne Schaeffer, a Jewish evacuee from Berlin, who was brought to Rozelle House on Kindertransport in 1939 (Stevenson, 2014).

On finding Mackenzie they encountered her moving around the main courtyard, scrubbing clothes, shaking them and hanging them on the washing line. This routine became freer, and she began to dance. Depending on where they watched from they may have picked

up a pair of headphones and heard a Waulking song⁷. As the song became quieter, they heard a recording of a poem, written by Beveridge, inspired by the lives of the maids of the house.

*The world turns
She turns
Jessie
Who?
Sweep. Wipe. Lift.
Stop
Breathe
Sweep. Wipe. Lift.
Dry hands, tired eyes.*

As the headphones were reset, Mackenzie would reset and begin the routine again.

On finding me they saw a woman reading a passage from Alice in Wonderland to five teddy bears. I invited them to sit down with me, to talk. I told them that I was practising stories for my daughter who loves books. I told them that these teddy bears are for the other children I want in the future. I asked if they had a favourite childhood story, and if they could tell it to me. I asked who used to tell them this story. I said I had to get on, and I thanked them. I picked up each teddy bear, kissed it, and then covered all of them with a blanket. I guided the audience member out and asked them to thank whoever it was that told them their bedtime story. I indicated towards a sign saying that Lady Jean Hamilton, who grew up in the house, outlived five of her children. Some looked at the sign, some didn't.

On finding Wilkie they were invited to play a game. They were taken to a windowsill where she pulled down the blinds.

It's better this way, it's quieter.

They were given half of a deck of cards, and told the rules of the game.

⁷ A traditional Hebridean song sung by women while making Harris tweed

Black cards mean we tell each other a secret. Royal cards mean we tell each other a wish that we have. Cards with a star on them mean we get to ask the other one a question.

Over the course of the game Wilkie revealed facts about herself, partially based on her real life and partially based on Lady Jane Hamilton. When the game was over she asked the audience member to write her a message on a card, and she wrote one for them. After exchanging cards she thanked them for listening, and invited them to continue in their journey.

On finding Lironi they saw her winding a ball of red wool around the servants' staircase (see Fig. 5). They heard her singing *Wisely and Slow, What A Voice, Hopeless, Sadness Don't Own Me, or No Me, No You, No More* depending on which point they walked into the corridor. She may have looked at them as she passed by, she may not have.

After forty minutes had passed the performances were interrupted by a song sung over the tannoy:

*As we go marching, marching
In the beauty of the day*

During the prologue, audience members had been told to make their way to the courtyard on hearing this song. We, the performers, finished what we were doing and headed out to the courtyard too, guiding any audience members that were unsure of the way. Once in the courtyard, the audience watched as Lironi began to sing *Bread and Roses*. The rest of us then joined in, standing still for one verse and then beginning to destroy the props we had brought out from our performances: a book, a ball of wool, a sheet, a pack of cards, a Russian doll and a kettle. For the final verse we sang in unison in the centre of the courtyard. When the song was finished, we lined up alongside the exit and indicated to the

audience that they should leave. The audience then watched as we shut the courtyard gates and silently made our way back into the house.

Fig. 5. Lironi performs on the maid's staircase. Photograph reproduced with the written consent of the photographed subject.

This chapter focuses primarily on the development process, the relationship between the performers and the site, and the methods employed during our process that were useful in reconfiguring our conceptualisations of Rozelle House. One of the primary differences between this project and *CauseWay* was my position as a performer within a collective. Rather than writing and directing the work, I created it in collaboration with a group of performers. Therefore, the analysis of the work includes subjective statements as it is impossible to separate my own experiences from those of the group. In order to gain

perspectives from those involved in *In Hidden Spaces*, I held a focus group with four of the six performers (Broughton and Beveridge were unable to attend, but answered questions by email). Audience surveys were also carried out, and have been combined with the data from the focus group in order further to contextualise my discussion. While several themes arose in the focus group discussion, this chapter concentrates specifically on the tension between hierarchy and collaborative devising, mobility, and the use of character. These themes were chosen due to their alignment with those arising in the analysis of *CauseWay*, and also their prevalence in the focus group discussion.

5.3 On Hierarchy, Collaboration and Care

Before beginning the project at Rozelle House I met with my fellow performers to discuss the project. The group was working as a collective for the first time, and I was aware that, given that the project would only last for two weeks, we would need to develop a shorthand and sense of comfort with one another as quickly as possible (see Fig.6). While this is arguably desirable for all artistic collectives, I called the first meeting in order to address a tension between the feminist principles of the work and the notion of hierarchy. Hierarchy is, of course, the cornerstone of capitalist social structures and is a key contributor to 'gender privilege' (Case, 1988:85). The elite, white male sits atop the Western capitalist pyramid (Massey, 1994). Theatre is traditionally developed and created in line with this top-down division of power, with the director, however benevolently, assuming control in the rehearsal room (Sidiropoulou, 2011). I view this hierarchical structure, which was used in *CauseWay*, as problematic within a feminist performance process. Therefore I asked the performers to consider everyone as equal partners within the process and in the development of *In Hidden Spaces*. However, the tension between my ideals for the process and the reality of my position within the team (as organiser, PhD researcher and, to some extent, director) existed throughout the process. The following

section will discuss how this manifested in the process and the methods employed to respond to this tension.

Fig. 6: Mackenzie and Wilkie during a creative response session

It was my aim within the process of creating *In Hidden Spaces* that we would develop a working style in which each performer perceived herself to have equal influence and right to contribute. Ianello (1992:xi) argues that a stark binary exists between organisational structures and feminist principles, stating that,

organisation theory begins from the world as it is, a world in which hierarchies organise all aspects of life. It does not ask whether hierarchies should exist, but simply how they can be run more smoothly. Feminist theory, on the other hand, begins from the world as it ought to be, one in which gender hierarchies have been eliminated; thus, it assumes the possibility for fundamental social change.

Our explorations of Rozelle worked towards using Herstorical data – by which I mean accounts of women’s histories – to create a feminist understanding of the space. The colonial, androcentric power structures that had contributed to the creation of the site were based firmly in hierarchy, therefore I wanted to exclude this from our practice as much as possible. I employed several methods in order to achieve this, including having each member of the collective lead exercises and sharing the role of director at different points throughout the process.

The use of creative response during the project seemed to be particularly useful for the group as it engendered a sense of artistic agency (see Fig. 6). This method involved asking performers to give feedback on work by offering a short performance-based response rather than verbal feedback. During the focus group Wilkie noted that she felt this method allowed each of the performance sections to develop in tandem, with ‘everyone’s ideas patched together’ rather than one overarching creative vision. Lironi, furthermore, stated that our working methods allowed her to feel comfortable offering critiques of the performances created, a task usually reserved for directors. Mackenzie recalled that,

even when we were creating pieces we weren’t particularly creating them for ourselves thinking ‘well, I’m gonna do this one ‘cause this is my favourite’. It was more like we were just coming up with ideas and what naturally fell from it was we found people that would suit something better than others.

Using creative response, and developing separate performance pieces alongside one another, clearly went some way in giving a sense of shared ownership of the work. While the fact remained that the project was part of my thesis, and that I had brought the group together, a shared division of directorial work and the use of creative response as a tool both helped contribute to developing a nonhierarchical, feminist process (see Case, 1988).

Ritual and Care

During my preparations for *In Hidden Spaces*, I noted that Smith's (2010) account of his mythogeographical journey included several references to his caring for and being cared for by the people he encountered. Pausing on his travels to listen to a stranger's story, being provided with food, and being offered help when traversing difficult or obscure pathways all seemed to affect his experience and the meanings he took from it. Following from this, it seemed incumbent upon me to take care into consideration in the rehearsal process. Care as a concept has been traditionally aligned with the feminine experience (see Clement, 1996; Noddings, 1984). This is largely due to the antiquated concept of women fixed in the domestic sphere, the 'mother, lover-to-whom-you-will-one-day-return' who maintains the home for the working or wandering man (Massey, 1994:180).

The woman-as-carer archetype is problematic and could be interpreted as limiting. In the focus group discussion, however, the notion of care continued to be implicitly referenced. Lironi and Mackenzie, for example, discussed the care that was taken to be open to each other's viewpoints as something that had been lacking in previous devising processes. Both attributed this to the fact that we were an all female collective. While it would be disingenuous to imply that women never argue with one another in creative settings, it seemed that we had developed an atmosphere where we prioritised care within the collective, which led to a sense of comfort and shared experience within the group (see Fig. 6). Through developing a dynamic of 'receptivity, relatedness and responsiveness' (Noddings, 1984:2), our process became one imbued with care, which impacted upon the relationships within the collective and with the space in which we worked.

One material example of this was the morning 'routine' we developed over the course of the fortnight. Rather than starting immediately with warm ups or script work, we began the day by spending half an hour drinking tea in the art room and discussing our evenings. Each day a different person would make tea for everyone, and someone else would wash up afterwards. This is hardly a unique experience for a company, however it seemed to have an effect on the developing artistic and personal relationships. During the focus group discussion, Lironi continually referred to our daily practice of having tea together in the art room before beginning to work:

I just felt like we were all in the same boat. And all of us could have...it was just like this completely uncensored conversation, like this uncensored conversation of ideas. It's like all just sit round the table and have a cup of tea in the morning and talk about genuinely anything.

Here Lironi clearly makes a link between our working relationship and this morning routine. Mackenzie also noted how spending this time together, serving one another drinks, allowed her to feel more 'relaxed', and Wilkie stated that 'it bonded us'. What developed over the course of our time at Rozelle was a strong, supportive group dynamic that prioritised the personal and the professional, as is evident in Fig. 6. I argue that one of the key aspects of this dynamic was this morning ritual of care; enter the space, prepare drinks to both comfort and stimulate, check that each person is well and ready to begin.

I use the term ritual despite it being 'slippery' and difficult to define (Schechner 1993:228) because our morning tea exchange speaks to the ethological use of the term. Through repeated actions this section of the day came to be understood as essential, and each member of the collective understood the roles that must be played. In turn, participating in this daily routine had a 'bonding function' within the collective (Huxley, 1966:266).

Furthermore, this ritual should not be viewed as separate from the artistic process, particularly given that we were interested in the experiences of domestic servants. While the practices I describe perhaps began as quotidian, through daily repetition they

developed into a rehearsed routine which can be understood as a performance in itself (Schechner, 2002). The care offered to one another through the preparation and service of tea contributed to our understanding of one another, and, to some degree, an appreciation of the experiences of Rozelle's domestic staff. The importance of care in the group bonding is also evident from the focus group responses. We made room in our process for a 'period of openness, of non-action, of learning and of listening' that could not be separated from the process of making (Kester, 2004:118). The awareness of the work as

Fig. 7: The collective exploring the ground at Rozelle

my own project was never completely absent from the project, and much of the organisational work fell to me. However the creative methods discussed and the significance placed upon care went some way towards eschewing the director/performer hierarchy dynamic.

The notion of care and of sharing social time together was, as indicated by the discussion in the focus group, an important factor in allowing the performers to relate to one another.

Referring to the morning routine, Mackenzie noted that,

you felt comfortable. I think when it did get down to, when we were like, 'right let's start coming up with performance pieces', we were so comfortable and relaxed in the environment and with each other that we weren't- Like, I didn't feel that stress or that anxiety about showing things or doing things.

Throughout the focus group each performer commented how the dynamic between the collective transferred onto our relationship with the space, allowing us to feel, as noted by Mackenzie, 'so comfortable in the space and comfortable with the house'. Care can be understood as key in developing a sense of comfort with others and within space (Noddings, 1984). Given that the final performance would involve the audience being given the freedom to explore the space, and that we wanted them to feel comfortable with this, we felt that care should be thematically central to the work. This was covered in a variety of ways, including Beveridge's instructions on how to care for guests; Mackenzie's movement section where she took on domestic tasks; and my own performance where motherhood and childcare was the central theme. This focus on care was, in fact, one of the reasons that motherhood became thematically central in my subsequent work on *Souvenir*.

As previously noted, using the ties between care and the feminine can reinforce problematic stereotypes. Many of the women *In Hidden Spaces* provided the types of care we represented. It was, however, important that our work was able to comment that this was not a definitive vision of womanhood, and that 'the attempt to confine women to the domestic sphere was both a specifically spatial control and, through that, a social control in identity' (Massey, 1994:179). Therefore, in the finale of the performance each performer subverted the roles they had taken on throughout the piece by destroying the objects that had symbolised their roles within the house. This final section can be viewed as a

manifestation of our exploration of the identities of the women, the notion of gender hierarchies and the burden of care. The items were destroyed, a rallying song was sung and yet, in returning to the house, we acknowledged that the problems inherent in the interplay between gender and heritage sites continue to exist.

5.4 Im/Mobility and the Artistic Collective

In the previous chapter on *CauseWay* I noted that the mobility of the performance proved significant in the audience's engagement with the space. Furthermore, I discussed the notion of collective mobility and how moving as a group can be aligned with marching as a form of political protest. At the beginning of the *In Hidden Spaces* project, there were no specific intentions as to how mobility should manifest itself in the work other than that it should, in some way, be present throughout the process. One of the earliest exercises carried out in rehearsal was having the group move around the space so as to begin to collect our perceptions of the space 'on the hoof' rather than by reading histories of the site (Smith, 2010:9). While none of my questions during the focus group specifically referenced mobility, it quickly became part of the dialogue. It was Lironi who first drew our attention to our mobility as a collective, noting that,

when we'd go round the house, like, in a group and be filming. So everyone knew that we were doing some- like, anybody that was walking past us knew that we were a team of people that were doing something together.

Lironi's words here, taken from the focus group discussion, refer to the visitors and staff and their perceptions of our presence. She seems to suggest that working as an individual performer contravening the 'rules' of the space can strengthen the sense of being observed with caution, like the 'dangerous 'other'' (Wilkie, 2002:245; Urry, 2007:63). Visitors and staff seemed uncertain of what was happening, and a lone body moving against the natural flow of the space posited a threat to the status quo. However, in Lironi's

experience, being in a group demarcated us as safer, people who were clearly working on something and therefore had more of a right to be there.

During the focus group, Mackenzie drew attention to another interpretation of the necessity for group mobility, stating that moving around the space together offered 'safety in numbers'. While Mackenzie makes no reference specifically to her gender here, her words echo Urry's (2007:67) discussion of mobility as a male privilege and the 'power relations' inherent in a body moving through space. The perceived 'safety' of the mobile female body is contingent on the presence of others; whether in terms of a sense of physical threat or, in the case of our work, a safety and support in creative practice. I argue that this feeling of 'safety in numbers' noted by Mackenzie cannot be separated from what Massey (1994:180) calls 'spatial control', which,

whether enforced through the power of convention of symbolism, or through the straightforward threat of violence, can be a fundamental element in the constitution of gender in its (highly varied) forms

Gendered power structures are present in all spaces and I argue that women are more acutely aware of the lack of ownership and authority felt in unfamiliar spaces. I attribute this, in part, to societal conditioning that teaches women to keep safe and never to walk alone at night; we apply this understanding of the gendered hierarchies of space to all of those we inhabit (see Heddon & Turner, 2012). I do not claim that we felt concerned about our physical safety in Rozelle. However, I would argue that the sense of uncertainty and 'safety in numbers' can be linked to women generally feeling less at ease in unknown spaces than men.

Towards the end of the focus group discussion, Mackenzie once again mentioned that her sense of comfort in the space was bolstered by 'strength in numbers'. Noting this theme arising again led me to surmise that the presence of other performers was a key factor in

allowing Mackenzie to move freely around the space. While it is normal for individuals to feel safer within a group, women have a greater sense of 'unease and fear in public spaces' (Rose, 1999). In terms of heritage sites, Aitchison (1996:n.p.) argues that such spaces are 'patriarchally controlled, masculinised, and structured in such a way as to exclude women'. In accepting Aitchison's argument it is perhaps unsurprising that Mackenzie felt more comfortable working in the house as part of a group. Rozelle is, however, a complex space to frame in such terms. The house is now an art gallery, and doesn't explicitly promote the 'Great Man' narrative seen in so many heritage sites (see Carlyle, 1840; Smith, 2008). Furthermore, as a collective we were engaging in a creative practice that was almost unprecedented in that particular setting. I would not necessarily state that gender representations within heritage sites contributed to Mackenzie feeling unsafe in the space. What I do note is that this allusion was made by Mackenzie twice, and it is clear that she and Lironi both held a preference for working as a group within the space over working alone.

In order to further understand the interplay between women, mobility and space, it is useful to consider politics of the body. Much writing on mobility suggests that the subject free herself of identity politics and become a neutral, nomadic subject (see, for example, Wrights & Sites, 2006). The majority of these works, however, code the subject as 'explicitly and implicitly (...) typically male' (Heddon & Turner, 2012:226). The frequent attention drawn to the physical features of the female body means that women cannot interact with a space in the neutral manner suggested by many writers on mobility (see Mulvey, 1975). Such limitations underwrite how women experience space. I would argue that, given the repeated allusions to 'safety in numbers', these limitations impacted upon the performers during the *In Hidden Spaces* project. The presence of the group, then, created a feeling of security. Collective mobility became an important tool in engendering a

connection between the performers and the space and in reinforcing commitment to creative practice.

It should be noted here that, while I argue a feminist approach to heritage performance should include collective mobility, I do not suggest that women are incapable of working alone in such spaces. The issues at play between gender and spatial relations are far more complex; for example, I noted in our focus group that we might have felt a greater sense of ownership or authority within the space had we been of a closer age to the Rozelle staff. I am not claiming, therefore, that women need more help in creating heritage performance, and it would be problematic to suggest this. Instead, I acknowledge the experiences of the *In Hidden Spaces* performers which, when explored through the lens of much writing on mobility, suggest that women's movement remains inhibited. The final performance work responded to this, but also subverted this sense of inhibition by offering the audience the chance to move freely around the space. The piece did not advocate that women should be 'fixed' within space (Massey, 1994:11). Instead it highlighted and problematised issues of gender and mobility, as noted by one audience member who stated that the work 'made me feel really sad that we are STILL marching!' (Participant IHSQ1). As with *CauseWay*, the mobility of the piece drew attention to gender inequality and the form highlighted the thematic content of the work; that we need to continue to move forward.

Immobility

Throughout our explorations of Rozelle we responded to our early discomfort in the space in a variety of ways. The decision to develop solo, one-to-one performances was made relatively early in the process. This form reconceptualises the voyeuristic power dynamic between performer and audience i.e. I will perform and you will watch. Zerihan (2006) has

noted that the one-to-one format has the potential to eschew hegemonic, masculinist modes of communication by offering an egalitarian interaction where both performers and audience members are active agents in the work. One method we used in dealing with the perception of vulnerability in solo mobility was to constrict the movement of some performers to one room within the house with the intention that a 'more constrained perspective might itself prove revealing' (Heddon & Turner, 2012:228). There exists a gender-based disparity in freedom of movement, particularly in Rozelle and houses of its kind where both class and gender dictated the domains and mobility of those within it. Indeed, the public rooms and bedrooms would only have been accessible to the residents and specific members of staff. The purpose of exploring women's experience of

Fig. 8: Wilkie in the upstairs 'bedroom'

space is to understand and respond to the impact of this disparity. *In Hidden Spaces* was, therefore, a response to the limited nature of women's lives at Rozelle. The sense of inhibition, of being 'trapped' (as Wilkie stated in the focus group), became a dominant theme in the devising process. The performances acknowledged and responded to this theme.

One of the clearest examples of this was Wilkie's performance, which was inspired by the life of Lady Jane Hamilton⁸. This section took place in what would have been one of the upstairs bedrooms (see Fig. 8). In this section Wilkie was physically constrained by the house; she didn't leave her room and invited audience members to sit on a window ledge with her. She closed the blinds to further highlight the limitations of her gender and social position. However, the performance was not without hope. She guided the audience's view out of the window to the expansive lands around the house. She discussed her hopes for the future and attempted to establish a connection with each audience member. This section of the work employed the aforementioned 'actor-as-signpost' model of performance discussed by Smith (2009:160), in which the performer uses their presence to highlight salient components of the site while still leaving room for audience interpretation. Wilkie did not seek to overwrite the space with her own narrative. Instead she used her gendered perspective to draw attention to its problematic nature, while also emphasising the performance-based interaction as an opportunity for its reconfiguration. Varying levels of mobility in feminist site-specific performance, then, can highlight the present as a liminal space between past and future; through an acknowledgement of what has been and an exploration of the possibilities for change.

⁸ Jane Hamilton, 1735-1809, was the daughter of the original owner Robert Hamilton

While I noted that this chapter's primary focus is the explorations we carried out at Rozelle, the impact of mobility on the audience experience is also key to this study. As was the case in responses from *CauseWay*, the mobility of the work also played an important role in how several audience members interpreted *In Hidden Spaces*. As the audience moved around Rozelle, their perceptions of the space had to continually adapt in a very real sense. Audience members noted how they were taken 'out of [their] comfort zone', and that the freedom of movement offered the sense that 'there are many stories here, just waiting to be uncovered' (Participants IHSQ 2 & 3). The audience members were not passive recipients of the hegemonic narrative offered by Rozelle, but instead were encouraged to seek their own understanding of the space. The mobile body has a heightened sense of space, never being able to settle in and rather always interpreting and exploring new locations. This is true even on a biological level as,

in the case of visual perception, our eyes are constantly in motion within their sockets, and our bodies (carrying those sockets) also shift, even when at rest, and this is accentuated by walking. As a result the information we get from the ambient array of light falling upon our immediate surroundings is varied and expressive to a perceptual system sensitive to difference.
(Smith, 2009:160-161)

Contextualising Smith's argument within feminist heritage performance, I argue that the mobility of the work allowed the audience a greater opportunity to reconfigure the site than a static work could (see section 5.5). As the audience moved around Rozelle, their perceptions of the space continually shifted and in this way the site was opened to multiple conceptualisations that contributed to a new, dynamic identity.

5.5 Characterising the site

It is important to note here that the development and final performance of *In Hidden Spaces* existed within specific parameters. This study aims to explore Herstory in relation to site, and makes use of feminist principles in order to do so. It is for this reason that we felt a semblance of character was necessary in the work; we wanted to represent these

women and chose what we felt was the most appropriate form. Artistic work that takes involves a prolonged period spent in a site cannot be understood as a neutral process, as noted by Hawkins (2014:155):

to think art-site relations through residency is to navigate key tensions that sit at the heart of these questions, namely the need to negotiate a tightrope between an over-valorisation of immersion and engagement as inherently good, as set against programmatic forms of production, wherein the artist's *a priori* assumptions and projects are imposed upon a site

Although Hawkins is specifically referencing artistic residencies, the issues she notes here were present in our work at Rozelle. The tension between what we knew and wanted to project onto the site and what we found when we worked there proved difficult during the creation process. We carried a constant awareness of the brief of the project – a feminist interpretation of the site – which at times inhibited our process. There existed a pressure, real or perceived, to include Herstorical facts and figures that had informed our experience. I would argue that applying feminist principles of performance making to the site without necessarily exploring Herstorical information is, in fact, quite another (and entirely worthwhile) area for investigation. It should be acknowledged, therefore, that the project existed within the limits of the study, and that the methods discussed here are particularly pertinent to those creating site-specific Herstorical performance, rather than those wishing to develop a feminist reading of a site.

The purpose of *CauseWay* as a live performance was to represent a very specific story. Notable events had happened and in developing the performance I aimed to challenge the dominant biographical narrative of the site (the life of Burns) by overlaying it with another (the journey of Parker and Moorhead). When we began exploring Rozelle, however, there was not one, specific Herstorical story that offered itself as the sole basis for a performance (for more on the women of Rozelle see Aitchison, 1994). The beginning of our process involved each of the artists looking over photocopies of censuses and notes I had written about the Hamilton women (from Aitchison's work). In addition to this, some of

the artists carried out their own research outwith rehearsal hours and brought new stories and Herstorical figures to the process, most notably Broughton's discovery of the story of Susanne Schaeffer. This Herstorical information formed the basis from which we explored the site and the narratives within it. Therefore, in our early work, we used exercises that invoked the women of the house in order to locate what the arc of this performance might be. One notable example of this occurred early in the first week, when each performer was asked to move around the house as one of the women who had lived there. However, I noted in my rehearsal journal that,

characters seem less relevant. We are aware that first-person interpretation just isn't the right form for this piece; we want to invoke the ideologies of the space rather than create a drama on top of them. We want the audience to be free to create their own narrative.

Fig. 9: Broughton as Susanne Schaeffer

We anticipated that dressing in period costume and using antiquated language might present a barrier between audience and performer; the two could not exist in the same moment as we would be playing characters from the past. In fact, as noted in Chapter 4, Smith (2009) argues that character should be eschewed entirely in favour of the actor-as-signpost model. The challenge presented to us, then, was to what extent we could represent the lives of these women and the issues inherent in their stories without pretending to be them.

Our struggles with characterisation manifested in a variety of ways throughout the process.

Broughton, for example, shared the story of Susanne Schaeffer (see Fig. 9).

Much of the work Broughton created during our time at Rozelle was inspired by

Schaeffer's story, as was her performance in the final work. Reflecting on this during the focus group, Mackenzie noted:

I remember [Broughton] said halfway through and she was like 'yeah I was just off home last night and I was just researching Susanne and I actually realised that she's not a character, like she was an actual person that got, like taken here from Germany'. And it just hit me, like these are actual people that people haven't respected enough to write about or use this house to tell their story.

That this story was real, and that Schaeffer had lived in this house, resonated deeply with Mackenzie. As discussed in the previous chapter on *CauseWay*, authenticity is a key focus in debates surrounding heritage performance, and 'perceptions of authenticity remain crucial to individuals' meaning-making processes' (Kidd, 2011:31-32). As a collective, we felt that the form of one-to-one performance, with its inherent potential for moments of connection between performer and audience member, could be combined with Schaeffer's story in order to offer a performative interaction rooted in Herstorical authenticity.

Maintaining a continual awareness of the actor-as-signpost model, one of the first steps we took to fuse the mythogeographical framework with our found narratives was to position ourselves as audience members in the rehearsal process.

Audience agency

The first week of *In Hidden Spaces* generally took the form of creating short performances and sharing these with the group. One of Broughton's earliest pieces involved having us interact in different ways with the space she had chosen, i.e. moving across the floor, hiding objects and becoming statues. A discussion amongst the collective after this sharing suggested that taking an active role and having agency in the performance shifted how we interacted with the space. We were able to place ourselves within the narrative of the site and this piece helped us challenge the 'normal' manner of inhabiting a heritage site. Smith (2013:107) has noted that offering the audience agency 'facilitated a certain self-mythologization of the audience members that enabled them to transfer the disruptive qualities of the tour and its space to the disruption of themselves'. Rather than observing a drama unfold, we were offered the opportunity to become an active participant in the world Broughton was creating and, in this way, reimagine the possibilities of how we could interact with the site as a whole. In developing this piece, we started to bring elements of Schaeffer's life at Rozelle into the performance while still maintaining the active agency of the audience. We decided to invite rather than force the audience into Broughton's game in order that they feel open and comfortable within the challenge presented to them (Jackson, 2011). By the end of the process, Broughton had us hiding Russian dolls and teaching her how to sew, reclaiming the site as a space of play while still retaining the authenticity of Schaeffer's experience.

It is necessary to punctuate this discussion with an acknowledgement that our work at Rozelle did not adhere rigidly to the actor-as-signpost model. While we did use our presence to gesture outwards towards the site and reveal the potential trajectories within the space, we also used character to varying degrees through the performance (Smith,

2009). Smith (2009:162) argues that privileging the performer over the site is reductive and 'diminishes (...) connections' that might be experienced between the performer, site and audience. While I agree that inserting psychological drama into a site can render the site as simply a backdrop, I would argue that, in the case of creating Herstorical site-specific performance, the performer's identity and that of the women represented must be privileged over the site itself. This is due to the dominant discourse of men's experience in heritage sites (Smith 2008); these sites repress Herstorical narratives and therefore attention must be drawn to the feminist stance of the performers and the gender of those represented when creating such works. Furthermore, as noted in section 4.4, the use of character can be understood as an effective component in catalysing the imagination of the audience and therefore offering the audience renewed understandings of space (Rancière, 2011).

As mentioned in the section on mobility, the experience of being in Rozelle was always underwritten by our gender. During the focus group, I noted how 'people [staff] would often say 'girls' to us at times and I was like 'we're adults', you know?'. While one may argue that young men may have been referred to as 'lads', there is a strong precedent for theoretical discussion of this practice specifically regarding women (see Duncan, 2006; Messner et al, 1993). Referring to a grown woman in such a manner is not uncommon and 'reinforces the infantilization which has gone on ever since she was born' (Greer, 1970:112). Therefore, while Smith's model was an incredibly important tool throughout our process, I would argue that site-specific performance with an explicitly political agenda must take steps to highlight this. In our case our physical, gendered presence was given precedent, alongside the Herstorical narrative, in order to reconfigure the androcentric power structures evident in the space.

Flexible characterisation

The ease that we developed in relating to each other within the collective was projected onto our relationship with the space itself. Lironi noted in the focus group discussion:

I think towards the end of the first week, for me, was when we'd get out of the car and look up at the house every morning and just be like 'back at the office'. But the best job because you know that you're gonna go in, go to the toilet, get a cup of tea, chat for half an hour and then get to work and it was that kind of, like, brilliant routine.

Lironi's words here mark a clear correlation between spending leisure time as a group (chatting and drinking tea) and feeling a sense of ownership within the space ('back at the office'). It was incumbent upon us as performers, then, to recreate something of this sense of connection to the audience member. One of the most problematic aspects of playing characters in *In Hidden Spaces* was that we felt it could inhibit the chance for connection

Fig. 10: Broughton and Lironi perform a silent duet through a window Photograph reproduced with the written consent of the subjects.

between performer and audience member as it roots the work in pretence; for example, we would be required to feign ignorance of 21st century life rather than basing the interaction in present-day reality. In using performance to create a relationship between performer, character and the space we enacted the concept of the socio-spatial dialectic (Soja, 1980). We achieved this by creating new associations and new connections within the site and highlighting its status as a relational entity (Massey, 1994). I argue that offering this performer/audience connection provided a simulacrum of our experience in the site, and therefore offered the audience a degree of the ownership that we felt in the space.

In order to achieve this, we adapted the concept of 'transparent performance' which is 'analogous to a domestic slideshow, where photographic images are projected onto the most convenient wall, revealing both the images and the cracks in the surface onto which they are projected' (Smith, 2009:162). Rather than understanding ourselves as being projected onto the site, the Herstorical figures were projected onto ourselves. Our performing bodies, overlaid with the identities of Herstorical figures, worked in tandem with the site to represent the lives lived within it. This is a model I term flexible characterisation, as it involves the characteristics of a Herstorical figure (or figures) being combined with the identity of a performer. These identities are then performed flexibly during an interaction with an audience; the performer offers moments of their own experiences alongside those of their 'character'.

Within our work at Rozelle, flexible characterisation was developed through a process of experimentation and exchange. Once we had focussed on specific individuals from Rozelle's past (particularly Lady Jean Hamilton and Susanne Schaeffer), we each shifted between the roles of performer and audience in rehearsal. We discussed the commonalities we had with the characters we were portraying, and included these in our

performances. In a similar manner to Smith's (2009: 162) work, where 'performers leave a trace' upon the site, here the Herstorical women left a trace upon us. We experimented with the levels of information to divulge, which sections of the performances would be informed by ourselves and which by the Herstorical character. What resulted was that some performances were rooted more in Herstorical fact than others. Broughton's piece, for example, included less information from her real life than Wilkie's as we agreed the story of Susanne Schaeffer felt more connected to contemporary society (possibly due to its chronological proximity, having occurred in the 20th rather than the 18th century). The ratio of self to character was not always a conscious decision, but an evolution of the pieces brought about by interaction and responses from the others in the collective; in some instances the character's lives were prioritised in order to illuminate certain narratives, and in other instances we drew more upon the performers' experiences. In the public performance of *In Hidden Spaces*, each performer presented a hybrid character, informed to greater or lesser extents by their own lives and the lives of the women they had researched.

During the first week of *In Hidden Spaces*, when a tension between character and performer was troubling the process, in order to tangibly conceptualise flexible characterisation, I suggested that we consider the women we were inspired by as images drawn on acetate sheets and projected onto ourselves. Wilkie stated in the focus group that she found this concept particularly useful:

my whole thing was having a genuine connection with someone, even a stranger, in a short space of time and just being open and taking that time to be open and connect with someone. So I couldn't have done that if I wasn't being elements of me and being a real person, because people just wouldn't have connected with that.

By adopting this model, we could represent the stories of the women of Rozelle without the need for acting, and therefore we would not need to feel limited by their experiences. In

imbuing the work with both Herstorical and personal ideologies, flexible characterisation allowed us to represent the space as 'a particular moment in those networks of social relations and understandings' (Massey, 1994:5). The 'cracks' of our individual personalities could be shown in order to offer the audience a truthful experience in the hope of offering the connection we (the performers) had developed with the space and with one another.

5.6 Conclusion

As the second performance in this study, *In Hidden Spaces* highlighted a number of concepts and principles that became vital to my research. Our collaborative working process marked a departure from traditional theatrical power structures by offering each performer the opportunity to plan and lead rehearsals. In this way, the *In Hidden Spaces* project can be understood as aligned with the collectivist principles that Ianello (1992) argues are central to feminism. The time spent working in the site and, indeed, the performance itself continued to draw upon the discourses surrounding gender and mobility that were so central to *CauseWay*. However, the work also departed from the semi-realism of *CauseWay* by combining Herstorical characters with the real lives of the performers through flexible characterisation. By the end of the project, it was clear that mobility and care had been crucial components of our relationship with the site and, therefore, it was key that these be included in the final performance work of this study. While both *CauseWay* and *In Hidden Spaces* explored women's narratives, the Herstorical data available to me was primarily accounts of socially mobile and elite women. In response to this, while *Souvenir* drew from the same theoretical principles as the preceding performances, I changed my focus in order to gather information on the lives of 'ordinary' women of South Ayrshire. This was achieved through facilitating reminiscence workshops with community participants and developing the stories shared into the final performance, which I will discuss in Chapter 6.

6. Souvenir

Fig. 11. Rehearsing on Ayr beach.
Photograph is reproduced with the written consent
of the subjects.

6.1 Introduction

The final performance work within this study was *Souvenir*, performed on Ayr beach on the 27th-29th May 2017. This work was a co-production with the Gaiety Theatre in Ayr, and it was included in their summer programme. The project took place in two stages: first, a series of reminiscence sessions with residents of Ayr and its environs (see section 3.2), followed by the creation of the public performance. At these sessions participants were invited to share their memories of growing up and/or living near the beach. The participants of the reminiscence sessions were not research subjects, and therefore I did

not collect specific information on age range or gender. However, I can state that there were around 20 participants in total, men and women, and they were all older adults (65 and above). These sessions took place in October 2016 and January 2017.

I worked with Poppy Lironi (one of the performers from *In Hidden Spaces*) during these sessions and then subsequently to develop these stories into a performance. Annaliese Broughton, who performed in *CauseWay* and *In Hidden Spaces*, took the role of stage manager in the public performances. Both performers had a strong understanding of the aims of the project, having been involved in the previous works. As with *In Hidden Spaces*, Broughton and Lironi waived their right to anonymity in this thesis. *Souvenir* was inspired by the stories that were told to us by the participants, in addition to local myth and folk songs. The development and rehearsal process took place almost entirely on Ayr beach (with a few days at Ayr Gaiety studios when the rain and wind became too formidable). The final performance work incorporated elements of tour guiding, performance, movement and storytelling. The fragmented structure was chosen to reflect the site itself, alluding to the site as a liminal space between two ecologies, littered with ideological and material flotsam and jetsam (see Kershaw, 2007).

During the process, Lironi and I drew upon Berger's (2016) concept of 'hydrological dramaturgy' in order to foreground the links between water and the maternal in the process (see section 6.3). Smith's mythogeography (2010) continued to be a key text in the development of the work. The process was ambulatory, and we implemented the same hyper-sensitivity to space that we had during *In Hidden Spaces*. Members of the audience were asked to complete questionnaires at the end of the performance. Furthermore, I facilitated a conversation with Lironi and kept reflective journals throughout the rehearsal period. As with the previous chapters, the full script for *Souvenir* is

appended to this thesis (Appendix 3). The following chapter draws primarily from the latter two sources as the focus is placed here upon the experience of the performer. This chapter begins with a short account of the performance, followed by an exploration of the thematic content of both the rehearsal process and the performance. In Chapter 4 the primary focus was on the performance, whereas Chapter 5 focussed on the process. What follows here is a discussion of both, with particular attention to the landscape and how natural, uncontrollable space impacts upon site-specific performance.

6.2 Performance summary

The three performances of *Souvenir* all began outside Pirate Pete's Family Entertainment Centre, a large white building that dominates the main route down to the beachfront. The beginning of the performance was usually informal, and saw Lironi and me chatting with the audience who had arrived as we waited for the others. Once everyone was in place, I read aloud a postcard about a romantic trip to the beach. Lironi then welcomed everyone and slipped into a tour guide persona, informing the audience that the building we were standing outside was originally the Ayr Pavilion; the central focus of Ayr's nightlife from its opening in 1911 to its closure in 1995. Lironi asked the audience to follow her, and provided rules for 'a successful beach experience' (Appendix 3). She then began to sing *The Tide Full in*, an old maritime folk song, as the audience continued to follow her towards the sand. I took over the guiding role, sharing fragments of information about Ayr beach, some mythical, most entirely fabricated⁹.

Negotiating the flotsam and jetsam of reclining bodies, abandoned rubbish and dead jellyfish, we eventually made our way to one of the Lang Scots Mile markers along the esplanade, where our fellow performer Annaliese Broughton was guarding several beach

⁹ See section on *Myths and Mis-guiding* for a description of how this information was developed.

blankets and a home made picnic. Once the audience was settled in the performance area, we performed a short movement piece incorporating several moments that were to come in the ensuing action. After this, Lironi told us about the myth of the selkies, seals that can cast off their skins and take human form. She then ran to the sea and unsuccessfully attempted to summon a selkie. On her return, we shared a picnic with the audience before discussing whether we could give up our children, like selkies did, and return to the sea. This was followed by a monologue, performed by myself, about the birth of my daughter. Lironi then sang a song she had written named *Come Ashore*, and asked the audience to join in. Next, she instructed the audience to say 'no' to anything she said, and began to ask each of them a question.

The sections that followed included a group rendition of *Under the Boardwalk*, a movement piece accompanied by a voice recording of the words of a reminiscence session participant, and another sing-along to *The Dark Island*. Lironi spoke of her desire to move to Arran, and then we moved into the final section of the work. Lironi and I changed into swimming costumes, and asked the audience to follow us to the sea. We took on the personas of two sisters, and told another story from the reminiscence sessions about a participant who had lost her mother when she was 5-years-old. This section ended with both of us running into the sea and swimming away. Once we had waved goodbye to the audience, Broughton (our fellow performer) informed them that we had 'returned to the sea', and escorted them back to the picnic spot.

In order to ensure continuity in this study, audience members were asked to complete short questionnaires, as was the case with *In Hidden Spaces* and *CauseWay*. These questionnaires were distributed in order that the audience members could give feedback on their experience and their understanding of the themes of the work. While this

feedback was collated and analysed, it has not been employed to any great extent in the following chapter as the focus is placed upon the experience of the performer in space. The performance was intended to be intimate, with a maximum of ten audience members per showing (although we exceeded this slightly on the second day). Of 33 audience members, 22 completed these questionnaires, a similar response rate to that of *In Hidden Spaces*. Of these respondents, the largest age group was those in the 45-54 age range. This can be attributed, in part, to members of a social media group that attend theatre together and had used that platform to arrange a group outing. All of this group were of a similar age, and they comprised the entire audience of the first performance. The respondents were overwhelmingly female, with only 4 males completing the questionnaires. The questionnaires were intended to give the audience an opportunity to

Fig. 12: Lironi setting up on the first performance day

offer an insight into their work that might, in turn, impact upon my analysis of the performance. Throughout this study I have found that, in order to attain a high response rate from the audience, short, paper surveys are more successful than focus groups or online forms (Gunter et al, 2002). The views offered by the audience were, therefore, rather succinct and did not offer a particularly deep level of insight. The conversation I had with Lironi offered a more profound discussion of the project, not least because of her position as co-collaborator. As with the previous chapters, my analysis is based on my discussion with Lironi, and the reflective journal I kept during the process.

In analysing these sources, I once again found mobility to be a key component in developing and staging the work, particularly in relation to the specific, dynamic nature of the performance site. Furthermore, as with *In Hidden Spaces*, the interplay between care and hierarchy was an important consideration in the project. As this was the only performance work of this study to take place entirely outdoors in a semi-natural environment, the particular logistics and meanings this brought to the project have been an important consideration in my analysis. In this chapter I will discuss each of these themes and their relation to the project, beginning with a discussion of devising performance in a natural space, followed by mobility and closing with hierarchy and care.

6.3 Nature, heritage and performance

The motivation to create a final performance work on Ayr beach was borne of several different, although not mutually exclusive, reasons. In the first instance, the South Ayrshire Place Partnership, who funded the performances created for this study, wanted new art works to be developed for Ayr beachfront. In addition to this, I believed that it was important within this study to collect and share testimonies of or about women from the community; narratives that are so often lacking within what Smith (2008:162) terms

the 'authorised heritage discourse'. Sharing memories of visits to the sea allowed us to gain an understanding of the living Herstories of Ayr, by which I mean stories of those still living within the area. The reminiscence sessions also provided an insight into how these women feel about the site today. Many of the participants spoke of the beach in the 1960s/70s as a lively site with high levels of tourism, and lamented its current state:

Ayr seafront in its vibrant heyday – an experience not to be missed and one that has sadly disappeared into the mists of time!
(Appendix 3)

At the beginning of the development process we found ourselves in somewhat of a quandary. While wary of re-presenting the site as a 'nostalgic utopia', we wanted to convey the Herstorical narratives shared within the reminiscence sessions (Smith, 2013:103). In order to reconcile a celebration of the Herstory of the space with its current identity, we decided to begin our process by setting aside the human narratives of the space (as far as possible) and focusing upon its physiographical features.

The physical identity of the space itself was an influential element within our working process. The space is by no means free from human intervention: there is a vast esplanade running along the beachfront, punctuated with play parks and shops and constantly lined with cars. However, once on the sand, the site is permeated with a sense of wildness. The beach is human made, and yet performs itself as a natural landscape. It is something of a hybrid, materially speaking, which aligns it with mythogeographical practice where 'hybridity' as a concept is understood as key (Smith, 2010). Particularly on wet, cold days, which were numerous during our rehearsals, the beach is largely unpeopled, with only the sounds of the waves and the cries of birds to be heard.

Our rehearsal period began on a particularly rainy day and, unlike with *CauseWay* and *In Hidden Spaces*, there was nowhere for us to shelter. Without any specific rehearsal plans,

we went to the beach with two buckets and spades. In doing this, we prompted a connection to our own childhoods, engaging in a practice that Philo (2003:16) has termed 'daydreaming', which involves developing an interpretive connection between adult and childhood 'reveries'. We discussed how, as children, trips to the beach would take place regardless of weather conditions. This first rehearsal in the site can be understood as a mobilisation of Smith's (2010:116) argument for 'foregrounding the mythogeographer's autobiographical and non-rational associations'. In approaching the space through play, we were attempting to escape from the 'treadmill of theory, evidence and analysis' that can so often inhibit spatialised acts of memory (Jones, 2005:206). We wanted to exist within the site, to connect with our own past experiences of inhabiting such spaces, and to put ourselves back into a playful, childlike frame of mind (see Philo, 2003). Our aim in carrying out such work was to explore the different ways we could interact with the space in order to foster new connections with it.

The following is an extract from the journal I kept during the process:

The torrential Scottish rain had abated and we wanted to play. Poppy had £6 in her purse, which was just enough to buy two flimsy bucket and spade play sets. I started by making a sandcastle while Poppy kicked a ball around. Then, I was overcome with a strong desire to dig a hole. I kept digging, pushing deeper into the sand, thrusting the spade into the hard-packed grains. I thought about women, about the women who had worked here. I thought about the repetitive, physical labour of those working in the traditional industries. Picking cockles, gutting fish. Pushing and pulling. My movements took on the rhythm of the sea. I fell into a trance-like state until I was hit on the head by Poppy's ball.

She was bored, I could tell. I asked her what she would have done here when she was 7. She said go for a swim. So we did.

She ran in first. I followed.

It was hard to breathe when the water hit our lungs, but the longer we were in the more this abated. The one other beachgoer tried to seem like he wasn't staring.

When we eventually came out everyone wanted to talk to us.

'Isn't it freezing?!'

'I'm a swimming teacher and I'd never go in there today. Good on you!'

Although we began our work aiming primarily to explore the physical features of the space, this extract clearly illustrates how our own Herstories impacted upon this rehearsal. In interpreting the space through Soja's (1980) socio-spatial dialectic, it appears difficult to entirely set aside human narratives when interacting with natural spaces. Indeed, as our process continued we allowed more of ourselves and the Herstories we'd found or heard to permeate our work. However, by playing and interacting with the sand and the sea we began to appropriate elements of nature into our work. The rhythms of the waves, for example, were incorporated into my digging. My movements began to create a new identity of the space; an identity formed of the sand, the waves, my research and my memories. In this moment, I was physically creating something ephemeral within the space, moving the sand into a pattern that, like the waves, would eventually vanish 'in a disappearing flickering of reality' (Sleigh-Johnson, 2016:7). In subsequently running into the water, we used the space in a childlike manner, breaking the rules of adult conduct on a rainy beach. Each of these moments spoke to the temporal identity of the piece we wanted to create; one with room for nostalgia and critique, embedded in the past and present conceptualisations of the space.

Ayr beach is constituted of water and sand, as is the case with any beachfront. In developing the work we found that both of these elements – here I borrow from the classical understanding of the term – physically and thematically affected the rehearsal process. I will now explore the ways in which our relationship with these physical, natural elements impacted upon the work. In order to reflect what is generally the experience of any beach-goer, I will traverse the sand before venturing into the water. In analysing the

conversation with Lironi, sand appeared to impact particularly upon the physical elements of the performance work. In the first instance, Lironi felt it was an inconvenience:

We became good at being on the beach, but it took us, it took me certainly two weeks to get to being good at being on the beach. It was like a constant coming home, ridding yourself of sand, putting stuff in the wash, thinking about what you can wear the next day that's going to survive the sand, so you're not going to get sand in your trousers (...) it was just constant.

I also recalled in this conversation that, after the final performance, it was necessary to fill buckets with sand from my bath at home, so great was the volume I had brought home.

Our interactions with the sand at Ayr beach call to mind Massey's (1994:7) assertion that 'localities can in a sense be present in one another, both inside and outside at the same time'. In one sense, the beach was present in our homes because, as Lironi stated, we had to practically and mentally prepare before going there. Furthermore, in a more material sense, both of us brought sand home with us on our clothes and props every day. During the day, the sand was a space of creativity, where our ideas and stories were formed. On returning home, it became somewhat of an irritant, spilling into cracks in floors and covering surfaces. The sand we brought home, however, was a trace of our work. Ingold (2007:44) conceptualises the idea of a trace as 'enduring mark on a solid surface', something that movement leaves behind. During the creation of *Souvenir*, however, we became the 'solid surface', and the beach left its mark upon us and our homes (I still find sand in corners now, six months on from the work). In order to work in the space, we had to embrace elements of wildness that were not present within either *CauseWay* or *In Hidden Spaces*. In this way, the site and the metaphors we took from it were omnipresent throughout our lives during these two weeks.

As our process developed, a sense of sandiness began to permeate the ways in which we created *Souvenir*. One of the earliest exercises we carried out was a walk from either side

of the beach towards one another. I created a movement to reflect the wave-like patterns that had been left in the sand by the sea; we wrote words and numbers in the sand; and we found that our bodies reacted to the shifting nature of the grains as we moved. The words that were written in the sand can be understood in terms of Smith's (2010:89) notion of 'decaying art' that is 'released to perform its disappearance'. As with many of Smith's mythogeographical interventions, our work was imbued with a sense of ephemerality; everything physical we created would disappear with the movement of the sand or the erasure of the waves. In order to move within the space, Lironi noted that extra physical effort was required:

I feel like a lot of the movement stuff that we did just completely came out of the fact that we were on the sand. (...) [It] never felt the same in the studio. Because it didn't have the weight of the sand that you were hitting against.

During our conversation, both Lironi and myself noted the sense of exertion we felt working on the sand, and the fatigue that came with it.

Transposing the movement sections from the studio to the sand changed how we moved: it became more physically arduous, and took on new shapes and paces. Our bodies were tested and our movements slowed, but in this slowing we found that both our bodies and our movements became the focus of the performance. If the moving body can be understood as a rejection of patriarchal 'modes of representation', then these sections became a moment within the work to highlight our status as women and performers (Braidotti, 1994:23). In these moments of silence our bodies became the focus: we performed walking as pregnant women, running as young girls. All the while we expressed ourselves in a different language, one that broke from 'the sedentary, phallogocentric monologism' of written and spoken knowledge exchange (Braidotti, 1994: 23). Certain movements or gestures were heightened or exaggerated by the sand, which in turn drew more focus to how we moved our bodies. In one scene, as I read a poem, Lironi performed

a movement piece inspired by the rhythms of the space: the wind, the waves and the slowness of moving on sand. She stretched her arm slowly outwards, and in the sunlight her muscles, her size and the elegance of her gesture were highlighted. This moment evoked a contemporary understanding of the feminine body; small, and elegant, but also strong and measured. The slower pace drew attention to our physicality, emphasised our (female) bodies, and spoke to a connection between femininity and wildness (see Sleight-Johnson, 2016; Massey, 1994).

Fig. 13: Lironi after our first swim in the sea.
Photograph reproduced with written
consent from the subjects.

While sand only became central to the work once rehearsals began, water seemed to inform the development of *Souvenir* from the very beginning (by which I mean October

2016, when reminiscence sessions began). The songs chosen for the reminiscence sessions primarily centred around water; *The Dark Island*, *The Song of the Clyde*, *Ye Banks and Braes o' Bonnie Doon*. Water became a metaphorical vessel for the creation of new connections and ideas, and in time it became something of a third collaborator in our work (Berger, 2016). I would argue for an analogous relationship between this conceptualisation of water as a creative vessel and the notion of community; in order for individuals to thrive, there needs to exist an environment of support and collectivist activity. This could clearly be seen in the community groups we worked with during the reminiscence sessions, as the meetings offered a chance for creative and personal connection. Furthermore, Lironi created a document filled with stories, myths and quotations about the sea as a stimulus for our work. She also noted that swimming in the sea on our first day of rehearsals (see Fig. 13) was important in the formation of the piece:

VB: What (...) is particularly memorable or formational?

(...)

PL: The first time we went into the sea.

The movement and presence of the water shaped Lironi's experience, and the development of the project as a whole.

While ideas of water and the sea continually drifted in and out of my creative consciousness, I found myself once more struggling with the notion of feminism within this work. While Lironi noted in our conversation that our personal stances (as feminists) would imbue the work with the necessary politics, I felt myself lacking a sense of theoretical grounding for this connection between women and the sea. Stories shared by and about women in the reminiscence sessions, and myths about Selkie women all strengthened this connection, yet I continued to struggle in theorising it. While still approaching the space with a mythogeographical lens, I found a more specific conceptualisation of women and the sea in arguments put forward by Berger (2016:22), in particular her notion of

'hydrological dramaturgy'. Hydrological dramaturgy means reproducing the form and rhythm of the sea through repetition, improvisation and collectivism. Berger (2016:22) contends that it 'may perform such a feminine symbolic function by emulating the facilitative environment associated with the mother and the sea'. I do not wish to reduce the identity of women solely to motherhood. However, a significant number of the stories we had collected in the reminiscence session discussed familial and, in particular, maternal relationships. My personal position as a mother, and the concept of care (first explored during *In Hidden Spaces*) allowed for this sea-as-mother metaphor to have a useful place within the development of the work.

Moving forward from this idea, in *Souvenir* the sea itself provided a backdrop, soundscape and rhythmic structure for the development of the piece. Ideas of hydrological dramaturgy, which will be discussed further in the following sections of this chapter, were used throughout our rehearsal process. Further to this, the rhythms of the sea were key in forming the final performance script, as noted in my reflective journal:

The text flows. It has a constant, rhythmic undercurrent that sustains it. And then there are interjections, interruptions that disturb the pace. They are rogue waves, out of sync with the others. You didn't see them coming as they splash up against you. They have their own rhythm that is simultaneously part of and separate to the meta-current.

Throughout the development and performances of *Souvenir*, water remained a powerful presence, materially and metaphorically. In engaging with ideas of water, and finding links between the sea and the feminine, we developed a work that embodied both the natural qualities of the space and the feminist aims of this study (see Berger, 2016; Sleigh-Johnson, 2016). What followed, then, was how best to continue to imbue the work with the principles of mobility and care that had been so present in the previous performances.

6.4 Mobility: wind and waves

Questions of how we move through space were purposefully part of this process from the outset. This was due partly to the chronological position of the work within this study; given that mobility had continually been a key thematic concern in the preceding projects, it was important to continue to foreground this in the creation of *Souvenir*. Furthermore, the site of Ayr seafront was particularly suited to exploring mobility within performance. This is due to its size and the constant movement that occurs in such a space; shifting sands beneath one's feet, the continual movement of the water, and the flow of humans moving along the esplanade and on the beach. Given that the central impetus of this thesis is exploring the potential for reconceptualising space through performance, the ever-shifting environment of the seafront was understood to be relevant from the beginning of the *Souvenir* project.

That the site continued to be physically formed and reformed by tidal patterns presented a unique opportunity to explore spatial mobilities and dynamism. To move through such a space permitted us to leave only an ephemeral mark, unlike the more permanent lines that can be made by continually following one route on firmer ground (see Ingold, 2007). By incorporating mobility into the process and the performance we did not follow one course again and again, but made, and then lost, multiple pathways. We aimed to underline the conceptualisation of the sea as a space of 'multiple beginnings and departures instead of designating origins while affecting no closure' (Berger, 2016:22). Our trajectories, both physical and conceptual, marked a variety of possible paths that, within the beach environment, are ultimately as ephemeral as live performance itself. Therefore, in order to imbue our process with mobility, the rehearsal period started with Smith's (2010) principal mythogeographical strategy: walking.

Fig. 14: Walking on the beach. Photograph reproduced with the written consent of the subjects.

The alignment of mobility with male privilege, previously discussed in the chapters on *CauseWay* and *In Hidden Spaces*, underpinned the task I set for myself and Lironi on the second day of rehearsals for *Souvenir*: to walk the length of the beach. In his description of mythogeographical practice, Smith (2010:112) highlights moving through space as key in uncovering ‘a set of uneven and inconsistent ‘anywheres’, partly experienced, partly imagined’. To move through space while employing a mythogeographical lens is to be open to the possibilities of that space: not just consuming what is there, but making room for what might have been or could be. In order to re-discover and reconceptualise space, walking practice is vital (Smith, 2010). So, too, is a hyper-sensitivity to spatial features, in this case the wind, the wave rhythms, the beach walkers and the grains of sand. I would note that, during my preparations for this work, my attention was drawn to Smith’s

(2010:31) potentially unremarkable statement that, in his walking practice, he 'has left his family for a while'. There is a strong stigma attached to mothers leaving their families, which is perhaps why women are 'the 'exception' to an unstated norm' within discourses surrounding walking (Heddon & Turner, 2012:225). In order to reclaim walking as a free, universal practice, it was consciously placed at the centre of our development process.

It was with the aforementioned gendered implications of mobility in mind that I proposed Lironi and I walk from each end of the beach and meet in the middle (see Massey, 1994; Heddon & Turner, 2012). This exercise was inspired by Abramović's 1988 work *The Lovers: The Great Wall Walk*. This performance involved two artists (Abramović and Ulay) walking towards one another from opposite ends of the Great Wall of China to end their romantic relationship. The walk taken by Lironi and myself lasted two hours in total, during which I made an audio recording of my thoughts and acts in order that I might use them as text in the final performances (see Fig. 14). Reflecting upon this in the conversation, I noted that,

I remember having this moment of being like, of walking and thinking, how privileged we are to be able to do that and to do it as part of a creative process. (...) It's something that for so long, for so many people, in the past, it wasn't an option for them to wander off. But also even throughout the world, just to be able to walk somewhere for two hours just with your own thoughts, and how much of a privilege that is and how- I think, for me, having that sense of privilege to what we were doing kind of drove me on as well, it was like... I said that in the [recording], I was like 'I feel like I'm doing this for the women who were never able to'.

This walking exercise was underwritten by my gender throughout, particularly the knowledge of the stark contrast between my ability to undertake this walk compared to those women whose lives have been explored throughout this study. Furthermore, the act was one of reclaiming the landscape, where the threat of danger felt minimal, and highlighted that walking within a natural landscape can be understood as allowing women the freedom from 'cultural norms that constrain' (Heddon & Turner, 2012:236).

During much of this walk I was entirely alone, and therefore felt comfortable in making creative interventions in the space, including a movement sequence developed along the way (a task I had set for Lironi and myself to carry out during the walk). Although this was a beach on the edge of a busy town, the space felt neutral, at least in terms of gender. In my perception the beach was not aligned with gender power systems, as can be the case with even the most unremarkable of landscapes (Massey, 1994). The further along the beach I walked, the more natural the landscape became and the fewer people I encountered. In this manner, I argue that the use of mobility as a feminist strategy within the rehearsal process can be particularly effective within a natural rather than urban landscape. It was my experience on this particular, isolated route that the detachment from the male gaze, which pervades much of urban life, is effective in offering walking women a heightened sense of creative freedom and agency (Mulvey, 1975).

My conversation with Lironi afforded me the space to discuss my own experiences of the development process for *Souvenir*. In this way, Lironi and I were able to compare our views on the work we had done, and the beach walk was a particular focus in our discussion. Other forms of mobility were employed as a catalyst for creating material throughout the development period; for example, we swam in the sea on eight of the ten rehearsal days. The amount of time dedicated to the beach walk in the conversation, however, suggests that it was particularly significant in our process. Whilst there were parallels between Lironi's experience and my own, she described a sense of harshness in her account:

I felt like there was a direct purpose for me to get to you. But I was going against the wind so it wasn't a kind of, like, pleasurable, let's look at the view and feel the sun and wander along. Like, it was very purpose driven, like I was fighting to get somewhere.

Lironi's experience, here, can be understood as a performance within itself; the 'purpose' she felt was aligned with the performance task I had set and the sense of 'fighting' was

borne of this (Schechner, 1977). Indeed, Lironi's perceptions shaped her experience as much as the weather did, and these perceptions can be understood as demonstrative of the body's ability to push forward through adverse conditions if there is a strong enough sense of purpose.

Lironi's account aligned her movement with classical conceptualisation's of the Hero's journey, a narratology concept wherein a protagonist goes on a journey, overcomes obstacles and then returns home somehow changed (see Campbell, 1949). Lironi continued to move forward despite the 'inconvenience' of her surroundings (Urry, 2007:85). The length of her journey was by no means Herculean; it lasted for two hours in total and did not involve life-threatening encounters. The process of a female body moving through difficult conditions shouldn't, however, be understood as apolitical. Her words in the conversation brought to mind those I had written for the dramatised versions of Ethel Moorhead and Frances Parker: *My legs keep moving*. In using this dialogue to align feminist politics with Massey's assertions of mobility as 'gender-disturbing' (1994:11), the performance underlined mobility as a key element in feminist work. While Lironi was not walking along the beach in protest, her movement was imbued with the gendered implications of walking alone (see Heddon & Turner, 2012).

It should be noted that, while the above argument has become fundamental to my study, there is a danger that it establishes an essentialist binary between the capabilities of the bodies of women and the bodies of men, particularly in terms of walking in wild landscapes. It is important that women's mobility is not conceptualised as more difficult or exceptional:

Rather than suggesting a greater scale of heroism for the female walker, it may well be more useful politically to draw attention to the many women who do undertake walking on this scale and emerge unscathed. This might generate reassurance that the wild is neither more nor less dangerous to women than it

is to men, which in turn may serve to rewrite the inscriptions of space and gender, as well as presumed walking competencies (Heddon & Turner, 2012:229)

Once again, I wish to draw attention to the fact that the beach walk was a relatively low-risk undertaking. While I do not suggest that it was on the same scale as some of the walks discussed by Heddon and Turner, the argument proposed here informed our practice. By moving through the space, in particular the more isolated, difficult sections, we were making a statement about the possibilities of mobility for women. Furthermore, several sections of movement and text that were developed from this were used in the final performance (see Appendix 3) meaning that, even in the sections where the audience was static, the mobility of our process was present throughout.

Myths and Mis-guiding

As was the case with both *CauseWay* and *In Hidden Spaces*, the public performance of *Souvenir* drew on tour guiding as an opening for the work. Due to the Gaiety Theatre's brochure deadlines, I had to decide upon the audience meeting point several months before the devising process began. Therefore, we knew we had to begin at the old Ayr Pavilion. The building itself is a testimony to the rewriting of space, the Victorian-style building now housing a pirate-themed family restaurant. In creating this section of the work, we wanted to reveal the histories of the space that we had discovered, or had been told to us by those participating in the reminiscence sessions. We aimed to be 'sensitive to the ways that the land and the cities are managed, owned, controlled and exploited' and also to the 'flows of power' permeating the space (Smith, 2014:12). In dramatising the site, we became active agents in reconceptualising its identity. The opening of the performance can be understood as a meeting point of the stories we were told and what they became when they overlaid or were overlaid with the physical identity of the space. Walking and re-walking our route became an essential part of the development of this

section, as our attention was drawn to different elements of the space each time we followed our performance path.

In order to achieve this, Lironi and I both created tours for one another in rehearsal. These were primarily improvised, an action that Berger (2016) argues can be understood as aligned with feminism and the maternal. She reflects on her own performance practice, which aimed to emulate forms of the sea:

Through the use of improvisation my performance equally provided a gestational milieu in which creation was facilitated but not controlled by a singular creative genius; it simply happened.
(2016:22)

In our process, improvisation combined with our knowledge of the site, with myths and fictional Herstories. We drew from the Wrights & Sites' concept of *mis-guiding* which can be employed to reframe space and eschew the 'closure of historic interpretation' (Smith, 2009:160). This framework, which is one of the key tools of mythogeography, allowed us to find 'holey spaces' (Smith, 2014:12) where we could insert Herstorical narratives into the site. In the final performance, the walk from the Pavilion down to the beach included factual, fictional and entirely fabricated narratives for the audience to consume. We renamed Arran, known locally as the Sleeping Warrior, so it became the Sleeping Goddess; we told the audience that Mary, Queen of Scots liked to visit Ayr beach; and we shared a story of siren women saving Ayr from a tyrannical pirate. In explicitly foregrounding Herstorical narratives along our walk, we posed a challenge to the space in order to reconfigure it; in a material sense we offered a 'bodily act of reading and writing coastlines' (Carpenter, 2016:16).

In developing these myths for the performance, we alluded to the possibilities of the space, both past and future. We drew upon existing myths in order to root the work in the traditions of the site and imbue a sense of authenticity (Kidd, 2011). However, by adapting

these myths to foreground the experiences of women, we offered an imagined reality of the site, one that might have existed in a matriarchal society. In sharing these ostensibly 'real' myths and folk tales, we conceptualised Ayr beach as a space of things that might have been. By using established spatial mythologies (which are, of course, fictional themselves) alongside more modern stories of women, we reconfigured not only the present identity of the space (by grounding it in women's stories) but also its past. In referencing these stories, Lironi and I were 'connecting the diverse layers and exploiting the gaps between them as places of revelation and change' (Smith 2010:116). Layering imagined Herstories onto local myths implied new possibilities for a feminist understanding of the space, highlighting that women's stories were always there, and still are. Using myth in this way can offer performers the opportunity to reform associations the audience have with a space by drawing upon and subverting popular, well-known stories. The aim here is not to deceive the audience, but instead to draw upon their own associations in order to activate connections with their past, present and future understandings of what the space is and could be.

We, audience and performers, moved as a collective, much like in *CauseWay*, although this time not in protest but in a quieter, slower manner. In our slowness, however, we still disrupted the space with this unexpected performance work, therefore setting ourselves once again as a challenge to the 'rules' of the site (Wilkie, 2002:246). Taking the time to draw attention to the possibilities of the space allowed our journey to be the focus, rather than our destination. Through our walking 'tour', Lironi and I implored the audience to consider the Herstories that may have taken place. We prioritised women's stories and alluded to the links between the sea and the maternal. We used flexible characterisation, shifting between performing ourselves and the women we had met, to highlight the dynamic interplay between the site's past and present. We shared movement works

based on the experiences of mothers and daughters. During the performance work we, the performers and the audience, reconfigured the site as a space of Herstory. I argue, then, that whether or not mobility is directly aligned with politics through text, it remains a vital element of feminist site-specific performance.

6.5 Revisiting care

From the very earliest stages of this work it was clear that care and, in particular, familial relationships would play an important role in whatever the final performance of *Souvenir* would become. Our primary source for the performance was the stories shared at the reminiscence sessions and frequently the stories shared pertained to spending time on the beach with family. In one of the earliest sessions, the one participant who attended offered her observation that ‘it’s the mother that holds everyone together’¹⁰. She discussed being taken to the beach by her mother, and, in turn, taking her own children there. It was during this session that the sense of ritual and care, so pivotal to the *In Hidden Spaces* project, started to become present within the work. The conceptualisation of the sea as a ‘benevolent’ rather than a harsh or particularly violent entity aligns it with classical views of the feminine and the maternal (Berger, 2016:17). Berger’s argument, in turn, leads to the sea being understood as a space of care where myriad life forms are held and nurtured. It was with this conceptualisation of sea and care in mind that Lironi and I decided to place care and the dynamics of the mother/child relationship at the centre of our process.

Souvenir was the second time I had collaborated with Lironi, the first being during *In Hidden Spaces* and, therefore, there already existed a professional foundation to our

¹⁰ These words were written into in the final scene of *Souvenir* (Appendix 3)

relationship. During *In Hidden Spaces*, however, there were limits to a sense of equality within the process, largely due to the size of the collective and the varied experience of those involved. Within *Souvenir*, however, the sense of hierarchy was far less present,

Fig. 15: Laughing during rehearsals.
Photograph reproduced with the written consent of
the subjects.

which could be linked to Lironi feeling a stronger sense of agency as a collaborator for the second time. While Lironi noted in our conversation that ‘it was like your project’, we also both agreed that both of our voices were equally present in the process and in the final performance. I argue that this was due to a developing sense of care and comfort that we shared, and a sense of ‘interdependence’ upon each others’ contributions and observations (Hughes et al, 2005: 259). The following extract from a conversation

between us, for example, demonstrates the humour and trust that was involved in our work:

PL: I feel like you asked for my opinion quite a lot on things, which was nice.

VB: Even about whether my milk was going to be alright in my fridge.

PL: Yeah or, like if you were going to be too cold without a jumper on.

Here we are both referring to my tendency to ask Lironi everyday questions throughout our time working together, including the lifespan of milk. In this way, I was seeking care and reassurance within our relationship and instead of being in charge I sought a 'reciprocally dependent' relationship where we each took on the roles of 'the one-caring and the cared-for' (Noddings, 1984:58). I would argue that this sense of connection strengthened not only our personal but also our professional relationship (see Fig. 15). This can be understood as aligning with MacDonald's (2010:n.p.) conceptualisation of artistic friendship as 'a generative, poetic exchange'. As I noted in our conversation about the process: 'that level of trust that you have creatively maybe spills over a bit'.

The link between familial and working relationships was clearly demarcated by Lironi's observation in our conversation that,

I realised through uni that all I've really wanted is a sister, like, all I- I've found, like, I feel like I've found sisters in all my female friends (...) so to sit there that day and, like, see you write us as sisters and the, like, to actually do it was just, like, it was such a weird, weird thing as well because we wrote ourselves into it (...) Like we weren't- we were characters but we weren't, em, so like the bits of, like information about your life and about my life just made it, like, seem more real.

Here Lironi, refers to the final scene, where we performed a duologue as two sisters who lost their mother, based partially on a story shared at a reminiscence session. This blurring of our real and imagined personas used the flexible characterisation model developed during *In Hidden Spaces* to heighten the sense of connection and care, by casting us as sisters, and it also spoke to the liminality of the work itself. Our process was physically sited within an ecotone – by definition a liminal space where two biological

communities meet – and through it we continually explored the ‘homologies between the real material conditions and the imaginary world of the production’ (Kershaw, 2007:7).

Prioritising Smith’s (2010:116) aforementioned emphasis on ‘hybridity’ in mythogeographical work, we used fragments from our lives, alongside other women’s Herstories and local myth.

As Lironi observed, in performing our own stories alongside those from the reminiscence sessions, the narratives that we shared ‘could have been our memories, but we know that it isn’t. But then we did perform it so it is a memory’. The liminality of the work allowed us to create personal connections with it and, in a sense, the memories of those that we worked with became our own memories. We created a familial Herstory between us that, although fictional, made space for this kind of caring bond within our process. In this way, the flexible characterisation model impacted not only upon the final performance, but upon the relationship between Lironi and I. By combining our own narratives with the concept of care in the final performance (see below) we found that our personal relationship was understood as fundamental to the process. Rather identifying our process as individualistic, a concept traditionally viewed by some as patriarchal, the relationship and care we shared became central within the work (Hughes et al, 2005).

In exploring care within our process and in the performance of *Souvenir*, familial and, in particular, maternal relationships were a central concern. Two specific stories shared during the reminiscence sessions heavily influenced our performance and were incorporated into the work in different forms: a written story of visiting the beach while pregnant and another story, shared during a discussion, of a participant losing her mother at a young age (Appendix 3). It was from these stories, and our own experiences, that our

focus upon the maternal evolved. The maternal can be understood as not just a thematic feature within the work, but also a metaphor for the creative, feminist process:

The maternal – envisioned as the creative potential of femininity while at the same time cast out of ‘proper’ cultural production – together with its imaginary link to the sea can be instated as a figure that gives shape to another vision of cultural production.
(Berger, 2016:18)

As aforementioned, the sea can be understood as a creative, life-giving force with the potential for creating and shaping the world. Furthermore, if fluidity as a concept appears to exist beyond ‘proper’ patriarchal structures of power through strength and solidity, then this feminist understanding of the sea and the maternal has the potential to offer new ideas of challenging such problematic ideals. It was with this in mind that Lironi and I used the particular rhythms of the space to explore methods of creation that foregrounded family and the maternal.

One of the clearest examples of this was a section in *Souvenir* where Lironi performed a movement piece while I read a poem (Appendix 3). Both of these fragments, created over the course of the first week, developed in response to the rhythms of the tidal flows and the notion of maternal care. The movement piece performed in the final iteration of this section was first developed during Lironi’s beach walk, combining the five movements she had made during this time. The fluidity in her movement, which she attributed to the wind on that day, can also be understood as a manifestation of the constant oceanic underscore created by the waves. Waves in themselves can be conceptualised, similarly to the pregnant body, as present within the present but also as a harbinger of future life; ‘an ever-repeated movement to come’ (Sleigh-Johnson, 2016:8). The sea, then, can be understood as intrinsically linked with the future; waves breaking constantly upon the shore, foretelling the others that will follow and follow.

Throughout the rehearsal period, Lironi and I continually talked of the beach as a verge, as the beginning of something. These discussions became manifest within our script: 'we're on the verge of everything, swimming in the promises of what is yet to come and wrapped up in the never-ending sky' (Appendix 3). Lironi's movement in this section can be understood as a response to these ideas; in using the rhythms of the sea, she created movements that spoke to the notion of the sea as a continual making and remaking of life. With regards to the creation of this section in my reflective journal, I noted 'as she rises and falls from one side of the room to the other it feels as though we've brought the sea with us into the room. It's a constant in everything we do'. As Lironi moved fluidly through the space, in sync with the waves, she emphasised how tidal movements remake space by '[troubling] the fixity of the cartographic coastline' (Carpenter, 2016:15). This section subtly underlined the sea and the female body as a space of productivity and, in order to further accentuate the link with the maternal, it was paired with text I had written from a mother's perspective.

As discussed in the previous section, the feminist stance of this work underwrote the beach walk, and I perceived a specific sense of purpose within it due to the importance of women's mobility throughout this thesis. This can be understood as specifically linked to the role of the mother, so frequently conceptualised as static within the home (Massey, 1994). Throughout the development of this work, my own identity as a mother was constantly present, as noted in my reflective journal:

The weekend was not as refreshing and restful as I had hoped – it never is when you have a two-year-old at home. I start the day feeling fatigued and lazy. Life spills into the process. (...) I need to get home for 5.30pm to see my daughter. Life spills in.

It was, perhaps, due to my role as a caregiver that the section of text I developed during my walk centred around this idea of mothers being fixed within the home. The development process of *Souvenir* was particularly impacted by the schedules I needed to

keep as a mother, and the care I needed to provide beyond our working hours. I would argue that making space for the personal within the professional is a particularly useful method of grounding care within the working process. In walking practice, as in all rehearsal time, 'human needs, feelings and cognitions' should be understood as integral to the process, rather than an inconvenience (Noddings, 1984:27). Care for the mind and body should be prioritised, lest the performing body be 'destroyed' in the process (Smith, 2010:33). Within *Souvenir*, this impacted in a practical sense as our working days were often shorter due to physical fatigue or the necessity to return home to my daughter. Care also became thematically central to the work as we explored mothering and, during the beach walk and resulting text, took space for reflection upon this particular form of caregiving.

The poem, which developed from the voice recording I made during the beach walk, made explicit links between care and inhibited mobility:

And I have a home to go to. And I have little faces to wash
and hands to clean. And I have food to make. I have things
to get back to.
But not now.

(Appendix 3)

Both this section of text and Lironi's movement piece used repetition as a framework. The use of repetition strengthened a sense of affinity between the performance work and the constant movement of the waves, while also making links with the repetition of rituals of care that continue throughout motherhood (Noddings, 1984). Furthermore, it underlined 'the gestational logic of water' that Berger (2016:20-21) argues can challenge patriarchal ontologies by challenging 'the self-sufficient Cartesian subject, a subject that is inevitably imagined as masculine'. We did not aim to be 'self-sufficient', but instead to place care and interdependent relationships at the centre of our process. As the text and the movement formed and reformed in repetitious waves, so the performance work made and

remade itself. Our words and bodies brought to mind feminine/maternal care, and the use of repetition foregrounded the links between the maternal and the sea.

The audience members that have attended each of the performances in this study have varied substantially in age and in their previous engagement with theatre and performance. I have, therefore, found it useful to communicate the thematic content of the works in a variety of ways. I would argue that, in this way, those who attended the performances were active agents throughout this study, as views of past audiences were taken into consideration in the development of subsequent works. It should be acknowledged that the use of repetition in order to represent the sea and the maternal is somewhat perceptual and interpretive. In discussing her own performance practice, Berger (2016:23) notes the relationship between the sea and the maternal should be understood as one rooted in symbolism:

‘the dramaturgy of the piece *recalled* the wave patterns of sea, *corresponded* to the temporal processes of oceans and *suggested* the productive environment of the womb’ (23).

These distinctions are important in highlighting that the performance structure is metaphorical and potentially ambiguous. I do not suggest that a variety of audiences could not take meanings from these interpretive sections. However, my analysis of audience feedback throughout this study indicates that a form of artistic bricolage, combining poetic, interpretive work with the more straightforward, has been beneficial to the audience’s meaning making process. I argue, therefore, that more tangible representations of care were also important in rendering the performance accessible (see, for example, the discussion of our picnic at the end of this section).

Lironi and I found that, as with *In Hidden Spaces*, the daily rituals of care were an important part of the process. During our conversation, Lironi noted that drinking coffee and singing in the car on the way to Ayr ‘was what tea was the last time’. The

understanding of and providing for each other's needs can be understood as integral to a process. Franks (2012), for example, argues that without effective communication even the act of sharing coffee can become a potential strain on a working relationship. It was this understanding of the necessary care that each collaborator required in order to work effectively that resulted in a productive and enjoyable process (Noddings, 1984).

Furthermore, there was a sense of shared history from our previous work together; we knew which drinks one another liked and which songs we both enjoyed. It was with this in mind that we decided to represent both of these elements in the public performance.

One of the first decisions Lironi and I made when planning the reminiscence groups was to use music during the sessions. Singing has been found to have positive effects on participants in reminiscence groups (see Lee, 2002; Lesta & Petocz, 2006). Before the sessions began, I consulted with a practitioner from the Village Storytelling Centre in Glasgow who specialises in reminiscence work. After discussing the project, she recommended songs that might work well with older adults. We felt that, by choosing songs that were popular among this specific age group, we could present an opportunity for interaction within the sessions and offer a sense of shared experience, particularly by using folk songs known across generations. During the first week of rehearsals, we discussed using these songs in the performance in order to maintain a link with the reminiscence groups, but also to re-establish the connections we found in these groups. Furthermore, in asking the audience to sing with us during the performance, we were signposting a part of our process that had been instrumental in developing our working relationship. These songs were a marker of shared pasts, an ephemeral and 'shifting landmark along paths of observation and cultural encounter' (Smith, 2009: 164). The use of folk songs within the performance can be understood as an indication of a shared

culture, but furthermore as an expression of music as an essential element in developing a connected, care-full working process.

Another section to the performance inspired by care, mothering and the stories shared in the reminiscence groups was the picnic provided for the audience. This took place after Lironi returned from the sea, at which point we provided home made sandwiches on Mother's Pride bread. Some spread with cheese, some with jam, which was noted by one of our reminiscence participants as a childhood favourite (see Appendix 3). We used these sandwiches as Herstorical markers, using the same bread and fillings that our reminiscence participants had related to their childhood. Using flexible characterisation once more, we synchronistically performed our selves and the mothers that had been discussed during the reminiscence sessions. In preparing and distributing these sandwiches, we took on the traditional maternal role (Giles, 2014). In asking each audience their preference in turn, we took time out of the scripted text to tend to their needs.

The repetition of this offer of food, while a necessity, drew the performance once more towards the rhythms of the sea and the 'multiple beginnings' it represents, in particular those associated with pregnancy and early motherhood (Berger, 2016:22). Furthermore, the ecotonal status of the site as a liminal space between land and sea was highlighted, as we provided food suggested by participants at the reminiscence sessions, foregrounding the performance as an in-between space rooted in both the past and the present (Kershaw, 2007). Our status also became liminal, as it intimated the role of both performer and caregiver. This picnic was followed almost immediately by an account of my daughter's birth, thereby connecting the provision of food to 'facilitative environment associated with the mother and the sea' (Berger, 2016:22). In offering food to our

audience, we carried out a tangible act of care while also signposting the work towards themes of Herstory and motherhood.

6.6 Conclusion

It is necessary to acknowledge that the development of *Souvenir* was unique within this study in a number of ways. The performance was the only one to use stories offered by living women and, furthermore, Ayr beachfront is not a designated heritage site in the manner of the RBBM or Rozelle House. In addition to this, as the final performance in the study, the work drew not only from the theoretical frameworks of the study but also from the conceptual and practical understandings that I had gained throughout my research. The emphasis on care, for example, was purposefully explored rather than arising naturally from performer to performer interactions, as was the case with *In Hidden Spaces*. The performance was conceived as a mobile work, in response to the mobility that had been fundamental to both *In Hidden Spaces* and *CauseWay*. While Berger's (2016) work was used only in this final performance, the influence of Massey (1994) and Smith (2010) can clearly be seen throughout each of the performance works. In focusing on care and mobility in *Souvenir*, I was able to further my exploration of how these concepts contribute to feminist heritage performance. This is, I argue, a key strength of a PaR study, as each of the performances have built upon one another while still uncovering new understandings of how heritage, feminism and performance can interact. In Chapter 7, I provide a summation of the study and discuss the key principles that my work can offer to feminist heritage performance.

7. Conclusion

7.1 Introduction

The primary aim of this study was to explore how heritage sites could be reconfigured through feminist performance practice in order to address the problematic interplay between space, gender and heritage mooted by Massey (1994) and Smith (2008). The performances created, *CauseWay*, *In Hidden Spaces* and *Souvenir*, were simultaneously products of and subjects for research. The primary advantage of using the practice-as-research methodology in academic study is that the artistic works developed can be further explored through theoretical analysis (Barrett, 2007). While all research works may be re-theorised, developing practice and undertaking further exploration through exegesis is at the core of PaR. This, however, gave rise to a tension between the aims set out during the early stages and the findings and themes that surfaced during the development of the performances.

As the study progressed, the performers' experiences came to be a key consideration in exploring feminist performance practice. Exploring the performance process, in addition to the performances themselves, allowed for an understanding of which tools were useful in such a process. In this final chapter, I give a brief recapitulation of each of the performances. I then discuss how the research questions informed my study and my findings as they relate to each question. I outline the implications my work holds for increased representation of Herstories in heritage sites. Furthermore, I set out principles that can be extrapolated from this study for those exploring similar themes in future research. This discussion will be framed within the context of previous research in the area, in order to make clear the specific contribution to knowledge offered by this study.

Before beginning this discussion, I shall reiterate the key research questions for the benefit of the reader:

- How does feminist performance practice impact upon visitors' and performers' interactions with heritage sites?
- To what extent can feminist performance practice reconfigure the androcentric nature of heritage sites?
- In what ways can feminist principles be enacted to create performance that can be termed both site-specific and feminist?
- Which aspects of or strategies for creating site-specific performance practice are particularly relevant to a feminist process?

7.2 Visitors, performers and the socio-spatial dialectic

The following subsection explores both the first and second research questions of this study, focusing on the impact the performances had on the space. In order to discuss how the performances affected the space I must also consider how they affected those individuals interacting with it, as our perceptions of space form its identity (Massey, 2005). In Chapters 1 and 2, I proposed Soja's (1980) socio-spatial dialectic as a framework for understanding how the ideas behind this study would be enacted. Soja (1980:225) argues that the social and the spatial 'shape and [are] simultaneously shaped by the other'. The notion that space is not fixed, but can be challenged and changed through social interaction and intervention was the basis for the development and production of each of the performances in this study (Massey, 1994).

As Smith (2013) notes, people often enter heritage sites with preconceived notions about what they will encounter. However, these perceptions are mutable, and can be influenced by alternative narratives presented through performance. The performances created

became the 'social' within the socio-spatial dialectic, developed in order to offer new understandings of well-known spaces. In the following section, I shall explore the extent to which the performance spaces were altered for both audience members and the performers involved in each of the works.

The performances

As noted in Chapter One, the Robert Burns Birthplace Museum can be understood as a catalyst for this study. My original research proposal was borne of my research into Frances Parker and Ethel Moorhead; both the story itself and that it was unrepresented in the museum. This is a pertinent example of Smith's (2008:159) argument that 'heritage is gendered, in that it is too often 'masculine''. *CauseWay*, then, rendered Herstory a prominent feature within the site and used a variety of techniques to align the space with feminism (see Chapter 4). In terms of how the performance changed the space, the analysis of this work centred on the audience experience rather than that of the creative team. In contrast to *In Hidden Spaces* and *Souvenir*, where performers spent time exploring the space, *CauseWay* was a play with a script that was handed to performers at the start of rehearsals. Consequently, my analysis focused on the reception rather than the development of the work. Audiences noted in the questionnaire feedback that they had 'never heard of these two women before', and that the performance highlighted 'the forgotten (overlooked) history of women'. While the performance clearly highlighted Herstory within the site, I would note that such an event could be viewed as tokenistic. This is problematic as the representation of women within the site doesn't necessarily improve once the event has finished, and the reconceptualisation that has occurred for audience members may be fleeting (Smith, 2008).

In order to address this, my analysis of the second project in the study, *In Hidden Spaces*, drew attention not only to the audience experience but also to that of the performers. Rather than approaching the site with one clear narrative, the process was rooted in investigation. The Herstorical data gathered on Rozelle served as a point of departure for the process, one in which the physicality of the space took precedent over human history. We employed Mike Pearson's (2010:19) site-specific questions as an initial exercise, and attempted to be 'sensitive to difference' within the space (Smith, 2009:161). The performance that developed from this work combined Herstorical accounts of Rozelle House with sections that developed from our interpretations of the space and the women that had inhabited it. Reflecting on the data gathered from the project clearly indicated that the process of creation was just as important in reconfiguring the space as the final performances, perhaps even more so.

As was the case with *CauseWay*, audience members recognised the feminist themes of the work. Several discussed 'feminism' and 'the history of women' in their questionnaire feedback. It was during the focus group with the performers, however, that I found specific insights into which aspects of the process had an impact upon how they understood the space. The notion of feeling safe within the space was important. Wilkie stated in our focus group discussion that 'it did feel (...) like we weren't that welcome and there were places we couldn't go, but very quickly it became like it was our house and we could go wherever we wanted'. Feeling comfortable, feeling at home, feeling safe; each of these continued to be mentioned throughout the focus group, indicating the importance of this perception. As Smith (2008:161) notes, there is a 'sense of belonging often considered to be fostered by the links between heritage and identity'. Applying this argument to the *In Hidden Spaces* project, it is clear that the performers found a sense of belonging in the space that didn't exist at the beginning of the work. By exploring the space in this way, and perceiving a

freedom to do so, a country house, an 'elite-masculine' power symbol, became a place towards which we developed a sense of belonging (Smith, 2008:165). A collective of six female performers developed an artistic process, rooted in mythogeography, to reclaim the space for themselves. On analysing the data collected from the *In Hidden Spaces* project, I found that time is a key tool in reconfiguring spaces of heritage. Through a prolonged exploration of a site, individuals connect with the space over a period of time and are therefore able to project their identities onto the space and gain an understanding of the multifarious narratives within it.

The analysis of *In Hidden Spaces* also involved audience feedback, although it was primarily based on the experiences of the performers. In developing the final performance work, *Souvenir*, I understood that prioritising the process over the performance was vital in exploring how best to reconfigure perceptions of and interactions with space. Just as the focus of analysis in *CauseWay* had been the responses of the audience, the analysis of *Souvenir* focused solely on the perceptions of the performers. The site itself, Ayr beach, is not strictly a heritage site. Furthermore, the androcentrism of the space is disputable although, as with the majority of South Ayrshire tourist sites, the Burnsian connection is promoted along the esplanade, with quotes from his work appearing on placards. Rather than challenging perceptions of the space, then, the objective was to present it as a site of women's stories.

Our process drew on the theories of walking proposed by Heddon and Turner (2012:229), specifically that placing women within 'wild' spaces can be understood to 'rewrite the inscriptions of space and gender'. The creation of the work engaged deeply with the natural landscape and involved solo walks, swimming, rhythmic improvisation and play. In our conversation regarding the rehearsal period, my collaborator Poppy Lironi noted that

such exercises gave a sense of 'purpose' to our work within the space. As was the case with *In Hidden Spaces*, the beach became a place that we knew, where we were needed, and where we belonged. These projects brought a new facet to the socio-spatial dialectic: that of time. Themes and ideas can be easily introduced to a space. It is, however, the act of spending time within a space, exploring it and understanding the self within it, that may then change our conceptualisations of it.

Audience data from *CauseWay* outlines an engagement with feminist themes, but perhaps an ephemeral one. The liveness of performance allows for a tangible, shared experience between performer and audience, yet also renders it fleeting (Phelan, 1993). However, it does not necessarily address the issues of Herstorical absence in heritage sites beyond the performance dates (Smith, 2008). Our time at Rozelle, however, is indicative of the efficacy of prolonged creative work in sites of heritage. The *Souvenir* project served to further this understanding, as it was the time we afforded ourselves in the space that impacted upon our perceptions. A profound, longitudinal exploration of site, then, must be understood as a key practical tool in exploring Herstory in heritage and in heritage sites, one that should be implemented across the wider heritage industry.

7.3 Feminism and heritage sites

The notion of feminism, and its presence within the performances created during this study, has been a source of tension within my research. The basic concept of representing women in these spaces, as called for by Smith (2008), was present throughout the study. However, incorporating the themes of feminism within the performance works and processes became less explicit during the course of the study. This was particularly the case with the *In Hidden Spaces* and *Souvenir* projects, which were not as explicitly political as *CauseWay*. As discussed in Chapters 5 and 6, the development processes of

the second and third performances prioritised mythogeographical spatial exploration; looking around, being in space, subverting traditional usage (Smith, 2010). Gender, of course, informed our work, and I employed feminist ethics of collectivism throughout the rehearsal periods (Ianello, 1992; Case, 1988). However, in reflecting on the performances themselves, *CauseWay* appears to be the most overtly feminist, with politics imbuing the narrative throughout.

As noted above, this was clearly reflected in the audience feedback, with ‘feminism’ and ‘women’ being key words throughout the data from *CauseWay* audiences. The performances of *In Hidden Spaces* and *Souvenir*, while exploring women’s stories, ostensibly drew upon feminist politics to a lesser extent. It may be considered somewhat ironic, then, that the development processes of these works were positioned at the opposite ends of the political spectrum. *Causeway*, the more conspicuously feminist work, was created in a more traditional (read patriarchal) style of theatre, with one person directing the work (see section 4.5). *In Hidden Spaces* and *Souvenir* involved using a collaborative approach to performance-making. What follows in this section is a discussion of how feminist principles were employed within each of the projects, and the areas of the process that necessitate critique.

The developments that have occurred within the feminist movement over the past century, and those that have yet to occur, were one of the key themes of *CauseWay*. These ideas were highlighted by Frances Parker’s speech at the end of the work (see Appendix 1). This speech can be understood as an artistic unpacking of Dolezal’s (2010) argument that, as women have gained more rights, other freedoms have been taken from them, and that the necessity to conform to certain physical and social ideals has become greater. The piece also incorporated ideas from first-wave feminists, such as the use of the bicycle, so central

to the suffrage movement (Bly, 1896). Throughout this thesis I have aligned mobility with feminism in terms of site-specific performance practice, and this will be discussed further in the following subsection. I have previously observed that ‘employing the promenade form, and selecting relevant forms of transport can (...) be viewed as a means of engaging with feminism and site-specificity’ (Bianchi, 2016:65). These are only a few examples of how the *CauseWay* script and performance engaged with feminist principles, and the centrality of feminism was clearly reflected in the opinions and feedback offered by the audience. While the process did not, perhaps, result in the same levels of site-performer engagement as the subsequent works, the text and mobility imbued the space with feminist themes.

Although the performance of *CauseWay* itself was rooted in the first-wave feminist struggles of the suffragettes, it is incumbent upon me to highlight a disparity between the themes of the work and the creation of the work itself. In the first instance, several scholars have argued for a more phenomenological approach to feminist performance work (see Zerihan, 2006; Embree & Fisher, 2000). The rationale for this line of thought stems from the links between language development and patriarchy, and what follows from this is that feminist performance should eschew text and language where possible (see Spender, 1980; Zerihan, 2006). This was not the case within *CauseWay*, as the piece was almost entirely text-based. The performance was also the only one to include male performers, which, while not specifically anti-feminist, cast women (in the final scenes) as subordinate to male authority figures, as is the case throughout the heritage industry (Smith, 2008).

While these factors should necessarily be explored and critiqued as not in keeping with the principles of the work, I argue that the process of creating the work itself was the more problematic aspect of the project. The performances of *CauseWay* were both written and

directed by myself, therefore fitting in to more traditional structures of theatre creation (Sidiropoulou, 2011). In using the director/performer form in the rehearsal process, the project afforded less of a creative voice to the performers and aligned itself with hierarchical, patriarchal power structures (Case, 1988). I therefore addressed this issue in the two performances that followed.

In terms of the public performances of *In Hidden Spaces* and *Souvenir*, the specific themes offered to the audience were intentionally far more ambiguous than those of *CauseWay*. The casts in both performances consisted entirely of women, and the works explored a variety of Herstorical narratives. The performance of *In Hidden Spaces* gave a voice to the undocumented domestic workers of the house, something so often lacking in representations of women in heritage (Smith, 2008). Within *Souvenir*, the stories of local women were set to the rhythms of the space in order to explore links between the sea and the feminine (see Berger, 2016). However, analysis of the audience feedback suggested that a far wider range of themes was taken from these works. Several audience members mentioned gender politics, and themes such as the difficulty of domestic work in general were prevalent in the data from *In Hidden Spaces*. Audiences from *Souvenir* discussed themes of childhood, nature, with one audience member commenting in the questionnaire that 'these tales and reminiscences were not gender-specific, gender-driven or gender-typical'. It is clear from these responses that, while feminism was present within the work, it was not understood to be as central as was the case in *CauseWay*.

While the performances may not have been explicitly feminist, the development processes of both *In Hidden Spaces* and *Souvenir* can be understood as practically applying feminist principles to site-specific performance. The blending of spatial theory and feminism manifested in three specific aspects of the work: mobility, care and nonhierarchical

methods. In the final subsection of this conclusion, I will explore how concepts of care and mobility were enacted in each of these projects in greater detail. Before finishing this section, I will briefly discuss hierarchy, a structure that was integral to the creation of *CauseWay*, and how the development of *In Hidden Spaces* and *Souvenir* was rooted in a collectivist, collaborative approach.

Taking Iannello's (1992) argument of an oppositional binary between feminism and hierarchy as a starting point, the role of director was not appointed to any specific individual in the development of either of the latter works. I acknowledge that in both of these projects I was the one to make final decisions on certain aspects, and the sense that this was *my* project remained present. However, my directorial positioning became less prevalent across both of these performances. In our conversation after *Souvenir*, Poppy Lironi, a collaborator for both *In Hidden Spaces* and *Souvenir*, noted a shift in our positions of power in the course of both processes, and how her opinions felt more important in the final work. I would note here, however, that I attribute some of this to the development of a friendship between Lironi and myself (MacDonald, 2010). I contend that, in creating feminist heritage performance, a collectivist style of performance devising is preferable to the director/performer paradigm. Furthermore, in order to develop collectivist, feminist models for creating performance work, collaboration must align with a personal sense of artistic respect and trust. I consider this further below.

7.4 Feminist principles for heritage performance

Throughout this chapter I have offered insights into how the performances were created in this study, in addition to exploring the research questions set out at its inception. In concluding this thesis, I propose three key principles that should be understood as integral in developing feminist heritage performance: the incorporation of mobility, flexible

characterisation and the prioritisation of care. The argument that mobility can offer new understandings of the interplay between space and movement has been integrated into discourses surrounding contemporary performance over the past decade (see Wilkie, 2012; Overend, 2013; Heddon & Turner, 2012). Smith (2009) has discussed the use of character, and it speaks to the notion of accuracy in heritage performance raised by Jackson and Kidd (2011). Care, while currently explored to a lesser degree in site-specific performance studies, has come to be a consideration for some artist researchers (see Beswick, 2017). In this final section, I wish to offer an overview of these concepts as they related to this study. I argue that mobility, flexible characterisation and care be understood as vital principles when creating feminist heritage performance.

Mobility

Massey's (1994:11) argument of mobility as being 'gender-disturbing' has come to be a cornerstone of this study. Questions of how women have moved and continue to move through space resonated throughout each of the performances. In the first instance, with *CauseWay*, the entire performance was mobile, with audience members joining the performers in walking through the village of Alloway. In the context of this work, not only was the mobility of women brought to the fore, but a mobile community was also created, wherein the audience and performers joined in a march towards an act of feminist protest. If mobility has a formative impact upon society then here an ephemeral, feminist society was created in the course of the performance (Urry, 2007). In drawing upon Herstorical forms of transport, and in giving the audience and performers a single, if fleeting, feminist purpose, mobility can be understood as a feminist act within the context of *CauseWay* (Bianchi, 2016).

In response to this, mobility became a central concern in the development of *In Hidden Spaces* and *Souvenir*. Rather than creating specifically mobile performances, my process focused instead upon how women move through space and the possibilities this offers when creating performance in heritage sites. The 'rules' of spaces of heritage can be problematic for theatre-makers, and this was perceived to be the case during the *In Hidden Spaces* project at Rozelle House (Wilkie, 2002:245). During our focus group, Mackenzie and Lironi spoke about feeling limited, uninvited, and that moving in groups engendered a sense of 'safety'. Aligning these reflections with current discourses surrounding women's mobility, most notably the work of Heddon and Turner (2012), suggests that women continue to feel an inhibited freedom of movement.

Within the *In Hidden Spaces* project and in the subsequent development of *Souvenir*, mobility was incorporated into the process. Performers were encouraged to move around the house and the grounds of Rozelle; Lironi and I undertook solo walks along Ayr beach. These activities were specifically chosen in order to respond to discourses surrounding women, mobility and safety. What resulted from this were perceptions of belonging within the space and reflexive conceptualisations of women's Herstorical mobility. The performances themselves both included mobile sections to represent the position of mobility within the work. It was in the process, however, that mobility offered new insights into how women can interact with spaces of heritage, both natural and human made. Therefore, mobility should be understood not only as a component of a final feminist performance work, but vital within a site-based feminist working process.

Care

The concept of care within the creative process developed not from a theoretical precedent, but from the rehearsals themselves. Care was not a central concern in the

analysis or creation of *CauseWay*, although it was thematically present in the performance in the relationship between Frances Parker and Ethel Moorhead. Instead, it was during the development of *In Hidden Spaces* that I began to explore and theorise how our personal relationships to one another impacted upon the artistic process. This focus upon care developed from my reading of acts of care throughout Smith's (2010) *Mythogeography*, and was augmented during the focus group carried out with the performers in *In Hidden Spaces*. Not only were we exploring domestic work, but the care we provided one another through sharing of personal experiences and cups of tea created a bonding ritual within the collective (see Schechner, 1993; Huxley, 1996). It was due to these observations that I again explored care within *Souvenir*, this time drawing upon stories from community participants to focus upon maternal care.

Souvenir used the audible rhythms of the space in order to explore the relationship between the female body and the sea. This can be understood as building upon Berger's (2016:23) practice-as-research work, which she describes as 'suggesting' the links between the sea and the maternal. Motherhood and care became central themes of the work. Furthermore, a caring relationship developed between us as performers and collaborators, resulting in increased levels of professional and personal trust. While acknowledging that care has problematic ties to oppressive views of womanhood, these performance projects are demonstrative of its potential as a positive tool within feminist, site-based heritage performance (Hughes et al, 2005). Including care thematically within such performances allows performers to explore the narratives of working-class women that are often sidelined. Additionally, integrating tangible exchanges of care into the artistic process allows for an increased sense of trust and shared experience within the collective.

Flexible Characterisation

My interaction with characterisation has fluctuated throughout this study. Indeed, it might be argued that the classical form of performers-playing-characters has diminished with each subsequent project. Smith (2009:159) in particular advises against inserting 'realist and psychological dramaturgy' into site-specific performance, arguing instead for the actor-as-signpost model (see Chapter 5). Throughout the course of my research, I have experimented with varying levels of characterisation in each of the works. At one end of the spectrum, the performers spent almost all of their time in character during *CauseWay*. More fluid identities were used during *In Hidden Spaces*, whereas *Souvenir* could be understood as almost character-less. In this way, I propose the term flexible characterisation as a model through which heritage performers can meaningfully interact with their designated space. Flexible characterisation can be understood as developing from the actor-as-signpost model, while also taking into consideration arguments surrounding authenticity and audience participation in heritage sites (see Kidd, 2011).

I employ 'flexible' here as it speaks to my approach towards character in each of the performances. Even in *CauseWay*, where the performers were in character for the majority of the work, the considerations of the space dictated that roles must be fluid. As an example, in one performance when an audience member had struggled to keep the pace of the rest during the Poet's Path walk, Annaliese Broughton stepped out of the character of Ethel Moorhead in order to explain what they had missed. In this instance, the flexibility of the characterisation can also be aligned with care, making place for the personal in the professional (Noddings, 1984). The task of representing real people, however, was perceived as a vital element of performing Herstory by those involved in the projects, and has been noted as key in previous research on heritage performance and in feedback from the audiences in this study (see Kidd, 2011). In response to these considerations, I

propose that those creating feminist heritage performance develop and embody flexible characters. The identity of the performer should not be conceptualised as negligible as it holds the potential for audience/performer connection explored in Chapter 5. The performer, then, is something of a 'signpost', but one that bears the markers of Herstorical lives (Smith, 2009:159). In this way, performers maintain the ability to connect with the audience while also promoting the marginalised narratives of women so necessary in spaces of heritage.

7.5 Final thoughts: space and time

This study was carried out in three specific heritage sites in a quasi-rural region of the west of Scotland. It cannot be argued that the geographical locus of my research did not impact upon the findings. Indeed, the location of the study itself is one of the factors that render the work unique. The specific narratives, connections and structures that have created each of the sites must be understood as intrinsically linked to the region and country within which they are situated (Massey, 2005). It is due to the scope and specificity of the project, however, that I do not claim to offer a definitive toolkit for creating feminist heritage performance. Instead I advocate two key aspects that should be adopted by staff and performers carrying out creative feminist practice in heritage sites. The first is that of time dedicated to the site and process, the second being the three performance principles outlined above.

In arguing for a renewed focus upon the spatial, Massey (2005:14) notes that 'temporality has been extolled as the vital dimension of life'. Time, then, continues to be conceptualised as 'vital', and I argue that it is through sustained artistic practice that we can interact profoundly with the inherent dynamism of a space (Massey, 1994). I propose that the vitality of time be applied practically to Herstorical practice and creative research,

and that it is only through time that we can begin to fully comprehend the complex multiplicities of space. In developing such performance work, these three theoretical principles can be enacted in order to establish a process rooted in discourses of space, feminism and heritage:

- Processes should by their very nature be mobile, thereby offering performers the freedom of movement denied to so many Herstorical figures. Furthermore, walking practice must be at the core of this in order to sensitise the performers to the mythogrographical possibilities of the site (Smith, 2010).
- The incorporation of flexible characterisation must be understood as key in aligning the representation of real women with the preference for audience-performer connection (see Smith, 2008; Kidd, 2011; Rancière 2011)
- A specific amount of time should be dedicated to personal needs within rehearsal, with care and friendship being understood as feminist concepts central to the work (see Noddings, 1984; MacDonald, 2010).

This study has demonstrated that creative practice offers a new lens through which to explore marginalised narratives in heritage sites. The principles outlined above were integral to the Ayrshire Herstories process. While acknowledging that this study was specific by its very nature, the projects undertaken have provided new knowledge pertaining to the spaces explored and the development of feminist heritage performance. The findings from this study suggest that offering opportunities for prolonged artistic research and incorporating the principles of mobility, flexible characterisation and care into performance processes are key elements of a feminist framework for developing site-specific performance in heritage spaces.

8. Appendices

Introduction

The following appendices, in addition to the footage of the performances, are intended to give a fuller understanding of the works created in this thesis. I note that the scripts and the footage cannot be understood as a replacement of the performances, as unplanned moments that occur in a public space impact profoundly upon the reading of the work. Site-specific performance cannot be adequately reduced to a script and film clip, however these documents offer a further insight into the pieces that cannot be gained from the written portion of my thesis alone. The videos that accompany this thesis do not capture the full experience, but are a representation of the work. I would also note that, in the case of the *Souvenir* video, technical issues have resulted in poor sound quality and an abridged scene (see Appendix 3). Appendices 1 and 3 take the form of a full script, whereas Appendix 2 is fragmented in form due to the durational and unscripted nature of *In Hidden Spaces*. Appendix 4 denotes the ethical procedures undertaken throughout the study, whereas Appendix 5 lists the presentations and publications generated from this thesis. This documentation, therefore, is not perfect. However, in its imperfection it is reflective of the performances themselves; fluid, unstable and different each time.

Appendix 1. *CauseWay* Script

CauseWay: The Story of the Alloway Suffragettes

Sc.1 - Robert Burns Birthplace Museum

*Audience seated around the horseshoe seating area at the back.
Ethel and Frances approach them casually.*

FRANCES

Hello, hi there, hi everyone and welcome to the Robert Burns Birthplace Museum.

ETHEL

A bit of a misnomer as this is not, in fact, Robert Burns' Birthplace...the open plan look wasn't actually all that popular in 1759 - thatched roofs, internal stables and cholera were all much more *en vogue* at that time.

FRANCES

Indeed, this is not the exact location of our national bard's birth - that's a wee bit along the road, and we'll be visiting it soon enough. No, this is a place of celebration of his legacy. Only today, unlike the swathes of tourists and visitors coming in search of the man behind the words, and then maybe a nice cup of tea and scone, we're not here for him.

ETHEL

No, we're not. Today we're going to take you for a spin around Alloway, you'll follow us to a few different places - like a bit of a search party.

FRANCES

Yes, today we're searching for two altogether different individuals.

ETHEL

Two 'bonnie lassies', as Burns may have called them...who would have probably objected strongly to such a patronising term. Today we're looking for two women, and for one story that tells of years of oppression and subjugation and devastation all compacted into one night.

FRANCES

When chapmen billies leave the street,
And drouthy neibors, neibors meet,

ETHEL

What?

FRANCES

Well, I just think if we're going to tell a story we want it to have a sense of gravitas and gothic splendour, you know? Quote a bit of poetry - Rabbie would have liked that.

ETHEL

But, we're not here for him.

FRANCES

No.

ETHEL

And the story we're about to tell happened in the 20th century, so there probably weren't any 'chapmen billies' around, really.

FRANCES

Yes...so we're not going for gothic splendour and poetry then?

ETHEL

Em, maybe not just now, but I'll let you know later on. *(To audience)* Today we're going to take you on a journey that took two women from Glasgow, all the way to this little corner of South Ayrshire, and then back again via an attempted bombing, a visit to Ayr Courthouse and a short stay in Perth Prison. But before we set off on our travels, I think it's best if we introduce you to the women in question. This is Frances Mary Parker, generally known as Fanny but given how the modern Scots dialect has developed we'll maybe just stick to Frances. Born Christmas Eve, 1875 which makes her 38 today, in the summer of 1914.

FRANCES

But definitely a young 38.

ETHEL

From a well-off family, Frances is actually the niece of Lord Kitchener.

FRANCES

He's the guy on all those god-awful war posters, you know pointing his manly, oh-so-omnipotent finger at the terrified young boys of this nation and claiming that "your country needs you". What a prick.

ETHEL

She studied at Cambridge University, and worked as a teacher all over the world before coming back to Scotland and getting swept up in the storm of radical, enraged activity that is the Women's Social and Political Union, or the WSPU.

FRANCES

Founded by Emmeline Pankhurst.

ETHEL

She's what the papers would refer to as a suffragette. She's passionate, infuriated, brilliant and she's my friend. Me? You can call me Ethel.

FRANCES

Ethel Moorhead, artist, excellent gin-drinking companion, suffragette, and my dearest friend.

ETHEL

Cheers, Fran.

FRANCES

No problem. Born in 1870 to an Irish Catholic family living in the UK, she trained in fine arts in Paris before returning to Dundee to care for her elderly parents. She was a particularly active member of the WSPU - described as 'turbulent' by idiotic journalists, she carried out such excellent acts as panning in windows, wrecking police cells, and chucking egg and pepper on Winston Churchill.

ETHEL

He looked a bit hungry that day.

FRANCES

Years from now she'll help me set up and run the Women's Freedom League, which helps women find fair, suitable employment. But for now, we've got another job to do.

ETHEL

It's July, 1914, and Europe is ablaze. Alliances are at breaking point, and war is imminent. But, back home, we're already fighting.

FRANCES

We've been fighting for years - probably for longer than we even realised.

ETHEL

We've been fighting to be taken seriously, to be respected, to have a voice. We've been fighting so that we matter.

FRANCES

We've been fighting for equality, or even just a little nudge towards it. We've been fighting for freedom, we've been fighting for a vote.

ETHEL

And, as the fight has progressed, it's become ever more violent. Chaining ourselves to gates and hosting peaceful protests wasn't getting the attention we needed or deserved so we...we moved things up a notch.

FRANCES

We started to become a bit more...militant.

ETHEL

We break windows.

FRANCES

We wreck the odd police cell.

ETHEL

Last year Frances set fire to a stand at Ayr Racecourse.

FRANCES

Well, you can't prove that can you? They never actually caught me.

ETHEL

And now we've got our sights set on another, much more attention-grabbing Ayrshire building.

FRANCES

We're coming for Rabbie.

ETHEL

For his cottage, to be precise.

FRANCES

And we're coming with gunpowder.

ETHEL

But let's not get too ahead of ourselves. To tell this story properly, we need to go back to where it all started.

FRANCES

And to the three words that it started with.

ETHEL

Votes for women!

FRANCES

Votes for women!

ETHEL

Votes for women!

FRANCES

Votes for women!

ETHEL

We will not give up our fight!

FRANCES

Equal pay and equal rights!

ETHEL

Votes for women!

FRANCES

Votes for women!

ETHEL

We want what the men have got!

FRANCES

It may not be a lot, but we want it just the same!

ETHEL

Votes for women!

FRANCES

Votes for women!

ETHEL

Go home!

FRANCES

Votes for women!

ETHEL

Go home!

FRANCES

We will not give up our fight!

ETHEL

Go home and mind the baby!

FRANCES

Equal pay and equal rights!

ETHEL

Go home and mind the baby!

FRANCES

We want what the men have got!

ETHEL

Ugly, desperate spinster hags!

FRANCES

It may not be a lot, but we want it just the same!

ETHEL

Go home, that's an order!

FRANCES

Order!

ETHEL

Order!

FRANCES

Order!

ETHEL

We call to order the Ayrshire meeting of the Scottish League for
Opposing Women's Suffrage.

*During this section Frances has 'Applause' cards which she holds
up at various moments.*

FRANCES

The month is November, year 1913. We have many learned, prominent speakers here tonight, including our keynote speaker Mrs Archibald Colquhoun whom we are thrilled to have the pleasure of hosting this evening. All of us here are aware of a blight upon modern society, a group of female fanatics known as Suffragettes. These contemptible creatures will do their best to convince the public that we hate women, that we want women to suffer and to be oppressed. When, in fact, quite the opposite is true! All of us gathered here today take the utmost joy in the female of the species, and simply want to prevent her from doing more harm than

good! Women, as we are all aware, are charming creatures and very useful in their proper place. Wouldn't you agree Mrs Colquhoun?

ETHEL

Oh, yes indeed I do!

FRANCES

How lovely. Therefore, without further ado, let me present to you all Mrs Archibald Colquhoun with her most eloquent address entitled "Why women should not have the vote."

'Applause' card.

ETHEL

Thank you, sir. And thank you to all of you here tonight, for joining to promote our most noble of causes - the opposition of female suffrage. Let me begin by stating that I can assure those who do not share my opinions that I can appreciate the fact that there may be those across the country today who wish to secure the vote in order to extend their sphere of usefulness. However, I do not feel their ideas or their tactics have convinced me, nor do I feel they have convinced the rest of the country!

'Applause' card.

Indeed, I remain unconvinced that women will increase their power or usefulness by gaining the Parliamentary vote. Please be aware that I do not contend that women are inferior to men - I object very strongly to the comparison of two things which are so incomparable. You see, whilst women may desire more influence in decisions surrounding the home and children, they simply are not able to take their stand with men in connection with the great Imperial and commercial affairs that affect the country. I do not mean to say that women are not citizens, but they are not citizens on the same terms as men.

'Applause' card.

The citizenship of women is framed around issues of the child and the home. When I think of some awful statistics available to us today I question whether women have forgotten this. These statistics seem to be an indictment of womenkind in this country - the statistics of infant mortality. It seems to me that, were these women not so busy chasing their silly ideals, then the rates of infant mortality in Britain would be altogether lower. When I think of the money and time that has been poured into ridiculous demonstrations and pilgrimages, and the thousands of meetings that have been attended over and over again by the same people at which the same things are said over and over again, when I think of what

might have been done with that time and enthusiasm in the home and the nursery, I wonder whether the women of this nation are off on the wrong track altogether and need to turn back, for the sake of the lives of their children!

'Applause' card.

What we must understand is, there is only one thing that women can do that men cannot do and that is bring up children - women should stick to what they do best and do it! There can be no way of proving that the women of this country will be safer, or receive fairer wages, if they get the vote so really we gain nothing from it. If we upset the balance of power in this country by giving the political vote to women, who have neither the time, opportunity, nor natural capacity for ruling the country, then we would be doing something that would be the greatest danger to the Empire, and the greatest danger to womanhood of this country.

'Applause' card.

FRANCES

(Applauding) Yes! Yes! The greatest danger to womanhood of this country. Please, save us from ourselves by ensuring that we have no say in how our country is run.

ETHEL

Make sure we stay at home so that our babies don't die.

FRANCES

Keep us in our rightful place, and don't worry our pretty, little minds which such masculine issues as politics.

ETHEL

Keep our votes from us - we'll probably do more harm than good.

FRANCES

It's for the best, really.

ETHEL

Oh yes, you're probably right.

FRANCES

Here's the problem though, Ethel, I don't think they are right.

ETHEL

No?

FRANCES

In fact, I would go so far as to say that they're talking a load of shit...that most of this country is full of shit.

ETHEL

You may have a point there, Frances.

FRANCES

I actually reckon that our rallies and our demonstrations and our posters don't go far enough. Because they seem to be making bugger all of a difference.

ETHEL

They don't seem to be opening anyone's eyes, or at least not the right eyes.

FRANCES

We're not getting enough attention for our cause, and if we can't get the right sort of attention, well then you know what we need to do.

ETHEL

What?

FRANCES

We need to go.

ETHEL and FRANCES from back of museum to their bikes, beckoning the audience to follow.

Sc.2 - Poet's Path to Burns Cottage

Frances and Ethel collect their bikes and begin to cycle across the road and onto Poet's Path. F and E stop periodically along the path to deliver their dialogue. A musician will accompany the audience and play during the sections where they are moving to the next stopping point.

FRANCES

38.9 miles make up the road from Glasgow to Alloway - if you can call it a road. It's mainly fields and back lanes, ditches and stony paths once you're out of the city. 38.9 miles of them. That's 68,464 yards of slowly, achingly moving our way across grass and mud and stones. Pushing our way through the dense, unyielding Scottish countryside for 38.9 miles.

ETHEL

38.9 miles. That's 205,392 feet and my feet are on the pedals for every one of them. And my skirts bunch up uncomfortably around my thighs, and my head is overheating because my hair has been coiled around it inside my cap and my heart is beating louder and harder than I think it ever has before. And the reality of what's up ahead, what we have to do, the darkness and the bang and the swirling flames, all of that pulses through me as I go. I'm terrified, and this terror will stay with me for 205,392 feet, but my legs keep moving.

FRANCES

My legs keep moving because they have to, because they are obliged to. They are obliged to keep the wheels turning, keep pushing forward for those who can't...those who don't understand. The women and the men all over this great nation who base their lives around the belief that our two sexes are fundamentally, irretrievably different. My legs ache more and more as they push me forward, and I can feel a burning in them that matches the fire of rage that burns in my chest. All the while I think of those who believe that one half of civilisation is only good for matters of the home, matters of childcare, for needlepoint and piano playing. The people who think that we only fight for equal rights because we hate men, or we have nothing better to do with our time. I think of them as the miles roll by, and my legs keep moving.

ETHEL

They added white lines to the roads this year - big, obtrusive, ugly lines which dictate even further where you can be and how you can be there. The more they create these roads and these lines and chop up the landscape to make it easier to get around the more they fence us in. The more they regulate where we go. The more they can keep an eye on us, and tell us how we should move from one place to another. They tell us how we should move from one place to another and still deny us our right to have any say in the decisions they make. They carve these long, thick, grey wounds across our countrysides and towns all under the guise of giving us more freedom whilst still denying us any sort of voice. And now they regulate us further by streaking these ugly lacerations with white lines - white lines that protect us, they say. White lines

that guide us. White lines that stop us from having accidents. But, here's the thing, we're not looking to stop an accident - we are the accidents. We are the downfall of most proud and virtuous man, the daughters of Eve who bit the apple and caused all creation to fall from paradise. We are temptation and we are weakness and we are only fit for minding the children that are a result of our sins. They give us white lines, they deny us a voice, they try to prevent any accidents. But the beautiful thing that they don't get is, those white lines are guiding our way, guiding the way for our cause, on these 38.9 miles...and we're bringing the accident to them. And so my legs keep moving.

FRANCES

My legs keep moving for the women and the men who need us. The men who support us, who are called hen-pecked, effeminate or simply insane. The men who believe that we are worth just as much as them, and who want us by their side at home and at the polling station. And for the women who are scared of the power we might one day gain, but who need it anyway. The women who work their fingers to the bone in garment factories for less than 1 pence an hour, and who train to become teachers only to be paid less than men who do the same job. The women who are beaten by their husbands, only to be told that what has happened to them is hardly a crime at all. The women who are victims of sexual assault and whose plight is simply laughed off or blamed on the clothes they choose to wear. My legs keep moving so that those women, and those men, they can have a voice, and so that, maybe not today, but maybe 100 years from now we can have equal rights and fair pay and abuse and assault will lead to trials and convictions. My legs keep moving so that, maybe, 100 years from now, downtrodden victims won't be blamed for their own suffering. My legs keep moving...and then they stop.

ETHEL

My legs stop moving because...because we're here.

FRANCES

We're here?

ETHEL

Yes, this is it.

FRANCES

How can you tell? It's so dark.

ETHEL

You see the little white cottage there? Up ahead? That's it! We made it, we're here.

FRANCES

Right, ok, well I suppose that means it's time then?

ETHEL

Somehow, when my legs were moving it didn't seem so real. Only now...now we have to go through with it.

FRANCES

Are you alright? Are you ready?

ETHEL

Yes

FRANCES

Are you sure?

ETHEL

Yes...no. No I'm not sure of anything at all really...other than the fact that I'm not leaving here until it's done.

FRANCES

Steady yourself, take my hand. Remember why our legs kept moving.

ETHEL

Remember why we must keep moving. Take a breath.

FRANCES

And let's go.

The bikes are left just inside the gate, and then everyone makes their way up path and into the cottage.

Sc. 3 - Inside Burns' Cottage

Musicians are already in place, playing 'Green Grow the Rashes' in the first room of the cottage.

FRANCES, ETHEL & MUSICIANS

(sung)

Green grow the rashes, O;
Green grow the rashes, O;
The sweetest hours that e'er I spend,
Are spent among the lasses, O.

ETHEL

So let's start by making one thing extremely clear - Robert Burns
was NOT a feminist.

FRANCES

No, I don't think we could go so far as to call him that.

ETHEL

In fact, he's probably the type of man you'd advise your daughters
to stay well away from.

FRANCES

Or your mothers...or your wives for that matter. It's definitely
true that Burns loved women. He said some nice things about us.

FRANCES

That's maybe as far as you can go in Burns' support for women...he
was very nice to us.

ETHEL

And he did write this -

F, E & M

(sung)

There's nought but care on ev'ry han',
In ev'ry hour that passes, O:
What signifies the life o' man,
An' 'twere na for the lasses, O.

Green grow the rashes, O;
Green grow the rashes, O;
The sweetest hours that e'er I spend,
Are spent among the lasses, O.

Auld Nature swears, the lovely dears
Her noblest work she classes, O:
Her prentice han' she try'd on man,

An' then she made the lasses, O.

Green grow the rashes, O;
Green grow the rashes, O;
The sweetest hours that e'er I spend,
Are spent among the lasses, O.

ETHEL

Her prentice hand she tried on man, and then she made the lasses,
O.

FRANCES

That's just romanticism, though, it's not a declaration of
feminist sympathy.

ETHEL

Well, it goes a bit further than being nice. It basically says
that women were created better than men.

FRANCES

We're not saying that women are better than men, though.

ETHEL

We're not?

FRANCES

No...I mean that's not to say we're not better than men. There are a
lot of men that we are far superior to. But we're just going for
equal.

ETHEL

You're right - all we want is a bit of equality. Which is
something that even the great bard Robert Burns didn't have.

FRANCES

Back when he was around he was in a similar situation to us -
admired, maybe even respected, but certainly not allowed to vote.

ETHEL

God, no! He was a commoner, and only the aristocracy - the male
aristocracy - had any say in politics.

FRANCES

It's not out of the question to say that he was just as unhappy about this as we are, almost 150 years later. And when he was dissatisfied with something, he wasn't afraid to speak out about it - just like us.

F, E & M

(sung)

A prince can mak a belted knight,
A marquis, duke, an' a' that;
But an honest man's abon his might,
Gude faith, he maunna fa' that!
For a' that, an' a' that,
Their dignities an' a' that;
The pith o' sense, an' pride o' worth,
Are higher rank than a' that.

Then let us pray that come it may,
(As come it will for a' that,)
That Sense and Worth, o'er a' the earth,
Shall bear the gree, an' a' that.
For a' that, an' a' that,
It's coming yet for a' that,
That Man to Man, the world o'er,
Shall brothers be for a' that.

ETHEL

Maybe he didn't campaign for women's rights, but he wove the principles of equality through his work.

FRANCES

Maybe if he'd have been around today he'd have sewn the Scottish Suffragettes' thistle onto his lapel and joined us in the fight.

ETHEL

Well, you could say that. Then again, it has been said that people have a tendency to use his words for their own cause without any real certainty that he would've supported it. "More nonsense has been uttered in his name - Than in any's barrin liberty and Christ".

FRANCES

And that's just the problem - we speculate that Burns might have supported our cause, but there are others out there who are just going ahead and declaring it.

ETHEL

They use him to set up Gentleman's clubs that he would never have been allowed into when he was alive.

FRANCES

They hold annual suppers in his name, and bar women from entering. And, let's face it, if anyone would have been happy to have some female company at dinner it would have been Robert Burns.

ETHEL

And for the war, the war that we all know is coming, the war that we all hope will be over by winter but will rage on for most of the decade. The war that will convince young boys to set off on an adventure - to become heroes - only for millions of them to die in ditches, gasping like drowning rats and crying for their mothers. The war that will win glory for our country - for this war, these young boys are told to take inspiration from their national poet.

F, E & M

(sung)

Now's the day, and now's the hour;
See the front o' battle lour;
See approach proud Edward's power—
Chains and slavery!

Wha will be a traitor knave?
Wha can fill a coward's grave!
Wha sae base as be a slave?
Let him turn and flee!

Wha for Scotland's king and law
Freedom's sword will strongly draw,
Freeman stand, or freeman fa',
Let him follow me!

FRANCES

They use his most famous verses to drum up national pride, to send boys off to a muddy field of slaughter in an alien land.

ETHEL

They use him to support the segregation of the sexes.

FRANCES

They use him for whatever cause they deem fit...so maybe it's time that we got in on the action.

ETHEL

(to Frances)

The thing about Burns Cottage is...well, it's the ultimate symbol of the masculine establishment.

FRANCES

Is it?

ETHEL

Yes. Think about it, would we ever be invited to a Burns supper, or allowed into one of the clubs that has his name on it?

FRANCES

Definitely not. And have you seen the reports on the war? Or the soon-to-be-war? They use loads of his verses and his songs. They use him as a symbol of male strength.

ETHEL

So, you see, it's not about attacking his legacy or his works, it's about attacking the people who steal them and use them for oppression.

FRANCES

You know, I read once that he had a stoop in his back because of all the manual labour he did at this cottage. He probably hated the bloody place! Mind you, that obviously didn't affect his ability as a womaniser.

ETHEL

But it's not about that...it's not about how he treated women or anything like that - it's not about him at all. It's about them... and what they've used him for.

FRANCES

It's about them, and it's about us.

F, E & M

(sung)

By oppression's woes and pains!
By your sons in servile chains!
We will drain our dearest veins,
But they shall be free!

Lay the proud usurpers low!
Tyrants fall in every foe!
Liberty's in every blow!—
Let us do or die!

ETHEL

(to audience)

Come on, quickly, let's get outside.

FRANCES

Stay round the back, keep as quiet as possible.

Frances and Ethel usher the audience outside, and take their place behind the cottage.

Sc. 4 - Outside the cottage

Ethel and Frances crouch down behind the cottage, and begin assembling the bombs.

FRANCES

Do you remember the order of everything?

ETHEL

Why? Do you not remember?

FRANCES

No, I'm not saying that it's just that I've never done this before—

ETHEL

Neither have I!

FRANCES

I know, that's why I'm asking how much you remember. We've practised enough, between us we should be able to remember.

ETHEL

My hands are clammy...I can't keep a grip of anything!

FRANCES

Ethel, it's fine.

ETHEL

No it's not, I'm going to drop the gunpowder or something.

FRANCES

Ethel-

ETHEL

And all the little bits, they seemed to fit together perfectly when we practised. But I can't see properly and I...I feel a bit shaky. And my hands -

FRANCES

Ethel! Look at me.

Frances takes Ethel's hands.

FRANCES

It's alright. Everything is going to be alright. You just need to take a moment to steady yourself.

ETHEL

Is this...never mind.

FRANCES

What?

ETHEL

Is this right? Are we doing the right thing?

FRANCES

Yes! You see, we pour the gunpowder into this section and connect the fuse like this before we-

ETHEL

No...I don't mean the assembly I mean the act. Should we even be doing this?

FRANCES

How can you say that? How can you possibly have come all this way only to doubt our plans?

ETHEL

I just...sometimes it feels that no matter what we do we're getting nowhere. And breaking windows and wrecking police cells and setting buildings alight...I'm not sure it's right. And, even if it is, we're just giving the people who hate us more ammunition to call us crazy and unhinged.

FRANCES

Do you remember how we started?

ETHEL

(quietly) Yes.

FRANCES

Do you?

ETHEL

Yes, I remember

FRANCES

It was all peaceful protests and discussions and trying to get the message out there in the nicest way possible. And no one cared! No one listened.

ETHEL

But now...now all they hear is that we attack places and we kick up riots in prisons and I've always felt that it was the only way to get attention. But the only attention we get is columns in the papers condemning what we do, and not talking about our ideals or the importance of our struggle.

FRANCES

At least we're getting attention! At least we're not being dismissed as mollycoddled housewives with too much time on our hands. We are fighting a war, Ethel! And in a war there will be casualties. And we don't kill people or hurt anyone, we don't oppress anyone in the way that they oppress us! We just make statements...massive bloody statements that get people to listen.

ETHEL

But, if people are listening to the wrong thing-

FRANCES

What do you mean?

ETHEL

I mean... I mean what if the riots and the smashing windows and the explosions are so loud that they're drowning out the message? What have we become, if we use evil to fight another evil? Are we just as bad as them? Have we become so caught up in our cause that we don't know right from wrong any more?

FRANCES

Quiet, Ethel.

ETHEL

No, Frances, I'm serious. Are these attacks and the violence and breaking the law, is it ever justified - even for the right cause?

FRANCES

I'm serious, Ethel, you need to be quiet. I can hear something.

ETHEL

What?

FRANCES

Over there, from the bushes, I'm sure I heard a noise.

ETHEL

What sort of noise?

FRANCES

If I knew what sort of noise it was, then I wouldn't be asking you to be quiet, would I?

ETHEL

Frances, I'm sorry, I didn't mean to question the plans we made. I know why you wanted to come here. I know why we do what we do. It's only-

FRANCES

Ethel, it's not about that right now, alright? I just need to hear...I need to know that we're alone.

ETHEL

Sorry.
They wait for a moment.

FRANCES

It's alright...I think we're alright. And I understand your fears, I have them too. But all we can do, all we can ever do is remember what we are fighting for and (*pauses, hearing another sound*)
RUN!!!!

Sc. 5 - The fields behind the cottage

Frances and Ethel make for the field at the back of the house, followed by the nightwatchman. A chase ensues whilst the audience watch from behind the fence. Frances and Ethel are both tackled to the ground, and a violent struggle takes place. Eventually Ethel breaks free, but Frances remains pinned to the ground. Ethel runs as fast as possible away from Frances and the nightwatchman, eventually coming to a halt in front of the audience. While she speaks, Frances is dragged to a standing position and hauled towards the Education Pavilion.

ETHEL

They might have talked of protecting us from ourselves, of how women are gentle and how we need to be handled with care - how we need to be kept inside, far from harms way - but they didn't give a damn about any of that that night. First there was the watchman, Robert Wyllie, who had been employed to keep an eye on the cottage overnight for almost a year. At least if there's one thing you can say for the establishment, for the powers that be, it's that they're not stupid. After other attacks that we'd carried out, they became fearful for the cottage and decided it needed 24-hour surveillance. And so they had taken the solid, dependable Mr

Wyllie on board to keep our sort away. And that's just what he did, in the most forceful way possible. He tackled us both to the ground, pushing our bodies violently into the grass so that we couldn't help but choke on the mud underneath us. I coughed and spat and kicked and scratched at him, and Frances did the same.

But he held firm, hitting and kicking back, pushing his whole weight on top of us and grabbing at our hair. I screamed with pain as his huge hands dug into me, and Frances shouted to him that the bombs were about to go off, and that he better run back if he wanted to save the cottage. All we could do was try anything to get him off of us. Frances' protests mixed with my screams and his shouts for help, all swirling together up into the night and then, so suddenly, vanishing into the noiseless darkness that surrounded us. He didn't believe that the bombs were about to go off, but it unsettled him just enough for his grip on me to falter, and I kicked and fought with everything I had. And, all of a sudden, I was free and I was running and running and gasping and pushing on with even more determination and desperation than I had when I was on that bike. I couldn't look back, that was always the plan. Even though I had no idea what might be happening to Frances we always swore that if we were caught, the most important thing would be escape - even if only for one half of us.

I'd only find out later what had happened to her. I'd only stop to think of it after I had run and run until I'd gotten back to the bikes. I'd only spare a thought for her, my dearest friend, once I'd cycled all those miles back to my home in Glasgow. I'd only weep for her, and for my abandonment of her, when I'd burst in the door of my house and collapsed on the floor, completely shattered in every way that it is possible to shatter a human. Only then would I sob with guilt and fear for my friend, alone in that field, pinned to the ground and choking on the mud. Only when my tears and shaking began to subside would I consider the idea that I should go to her, to hand myself in and sit beside her in our jail cell so that she wouldn't be alone. But then I thought of her face, and I thought of our plan. I thought of how she'd told me that we were at war, and the more of our soldiers they held in captivity the less there were of us to fight. So, instead of going to her, I wept for her and I feared for her and I waited.

I didn't have to wait for long, though. News of what we'd done - what we'd tried to do - made the papers only a day later. They talked about Robert Burns as though he was some sort of God, and we were the heathen witches who had dared attempt to destroy his temple. They talked of how honest Burns' father was, and how zealous and hardworking the watchman had been. All of them pillars of society, in contrast to Frances - the she-devil who attempted to molest his legacy. She told them her name was Janet Arthur - that was the policy we always stuck to; fake names and fake addresses and then do everything in your power to escape.

The papers told how everyone in the village had leapt from their beds at the commotion, and gathered around her as she'd been taken away. She got all the usual bits thrown at her: she was a disgrace to her sex, she should be hanged, she should be shot, how could she do such an evil thing? She just told them that if they didn't understand now, they never would. That she had been obliged to do it, and that she wished she'd had a bloody revolver. That made me laugh when I read it, because it was just typical Frances - defiant to the last. Apparently they'd gone looking for me all around the roads near the cottage, but I was long gone. And she never gave me up, she just told them that she'd done it herself, and if the watchman was seeing double then he must have been drunk.

Ethel comes out from behind the gate, and leads the audience towards the Education Pavilion.

She wasn't treated well in prison. She went on hunger strike, and was violently force-fed by the policemen. When they couldn't get her to open her mouth, they held her down and tried to shove liquids in through her rectum. She was covered in bruises, broken and totally alone. She never admitted it to me, not in the years that followed, but all of those bruises couldn't have come just from the force-feeding. I know that they beat her...maybe even worse. And through all of that, she never gave my name. All she ever thought of was other people - in fact, on her court date she used the money that had been found on her to pay the fine of another woman who had been destined for debtor's prison. People will call her selfish and evil, but nothing could be further from the truth.

After a few weeks had passed, she became so weak, so broken, that the authorities couldn't possibly keep her in prison. Reluctantly, they transferred her to a nursing home from where she found it all too easy to escape. She hid in farmhouses and empty barns, all the while making her way back to us, making her way back to me. I remember that first day that I saw her after the escape. She was about half the size she'd been before, and covered in violent, ugly bruises. She squeezed me so tightly that I could feel her body flinch - she must have been pressing me against her wounds, she must have been in pain, but she didn't care. I thanked her over and over again, and I apologised for abandoning her. She told me that...

FRANCES

(Appearing from behind the audience)

...if you had shown up at that prison I'd have told them you were my dear, insane sister who lies to get attention, and I'd have sent you on your way.

ETHEL

I'm so sorry, Frances. I'm...I didn't

FRANCES

That is enough now, I'm here aren't I? I'm back, I'm safe.

ETHEL

But...but look at your face! Look at your bruises! What they must have put you through, I...I can never forgive myself.

FRANCES

Why? It wasn't you that put me through it. And you going through the same thing certainly wouldn't have made me feel better. No, knowing that you were home, that you were safe, that got me through it. Knowing that we were only one soldier down instead of two, that's what kept me going.

ETHEL

I'm just so happy you're alright.

FRANCES

Oh it'll take more than a few overly-zealous pigs in black hats to break me. Did you see the papers?

ETHEL

I did, of course I did! I kept them all, you definitely captured their imagination.

FRANCES

Did they report everything that happened in court? Did they write about my defence speech?

ETHEL

Yeah, they said it was eloquent and passionate, and that you quoted Robert Burns.

FRANCES

You're damn right I did! Oh, Ethel, you should have seen me. I was poetry in motion. I was fantastical!

ETHEL

(laughing)

I'm sure you were!

FRANCES

You don't believe me? Take a look!

FRANCES beckons ETHEL and the audience to follow her to the Education Pavilion.

Sc. 6 - The Education Pavilion

The space is arranged like a traditional theatre, with Frances at the front behind a table.

FRANCES

My name is Janet Arthur and I plead guilty to the charges before me. I make no attempt to deny or excuse my behaviour, in fact my only regret is that I was unable to complete my mission. Let me start by saying that I was unaware of anyone within close enough range that they might have been harmed by the explosion - this is not our aim. You see, while you worry about the imminent war in Europe you fail to realise we are already at war. I am at war with you, with all of you who continue to deny women the vote and therefore deny them equality. Now this is a war in which we will still do our best to preserve human life, but one in which we will have no regard for property of any kind. If there are buildings and monuments that symbolise female oppression, then they will be targeted and we will not stop until we have won.

As to the question of Robert Burns, you should know that we do not wish to attack the man and his works - in fact many of his writings resonate with our cause. Burns once wrote of Robert the Bruce and the Scottish struggles for independence, "Liberty's in every blow, let us do or die". And that is exactly what we believe - we will strike blow upon blow until our cause is won, and we are happy to die for our beliefs. You, all of you proud Scotsmen, you used to be so proud of your heroes like the Bruce, and now you have taken to torturing women. I wonder what your heroes would say, those who fought so fiercely against oppression, to see you now oppressing the women of your country. No, we do not attack Robert Burns, but we attack the symbol of patriarchal power that you have bastardised him as - and that's why we attack his cottage.

I look at you, at all of you here today, and see two faces. The first of these faces is anger. This I can understand - I have tried to destroy a monument to your beloved national poet. I can

take your anger, but what I cannot take is the other face - the face of pity. You look at me and see someone who fights for an equality that she does not deserve - who cannot understand that men and women are not created equal. To those who pity me, think of this - a newborn baby in it's mothers arms. Not yet confined to the cold, sharp trouser suits or the floaty, feminine skirts in which it will spend its life. Only its mother and father can know which destiny lies ahead of the child - to a stranger, there can be no real knowledge of whether they are looking at a boy or a girl. And for the child itself, as it looks out from its shawl to see a hospital ward filled with other babes just like it, does it see one group that is fundamentally different to the other? Does it think that one half of the newborns in the room are of a lesser status than the rest? Is it born with some innate knowledge that the males have been born to protect and regulate the females - and that the females exist only to be admired?

The answer is no. The newborn baby, even the toddling child, none of them are born with the notion or the will to oppress or fear the opposite sex. It is through our actions, through the social situations that we put them in, that we create difference in children. It is through our narrow-minded views of the world that we bring about segregation and sexism, and raise generation upon generation to believe that one half of the human population simply isn't as good as the other. And that, ladies and gentlemen, is why I cannot take your pity. In fact, I pity you for not seeing that, from the moment we are born, we are created completely equal and that we are doing this great nation a disservice by not allowing all of the voice within it to be heard.

But, much as I despair at your misguided opinions and much as I pity your stupid ideals, I can take solace in one thing. A storm of change is coming, and I know that, fight as you may, you cannot hold back this storm. For thousands of years men have found ways to make women feel like we are secondary, and slowly we are waking up from this nightmare. Slowly, all over the world, little girls are beginning to realise that they don't have to stay in the home and that they are worth more than simply spending their lives as glorified, unpaid servants for men. And once this storm hits, there will be no stopping its path of revolution and reformation. And I know that, once the storm has settled, the people of this country will look back and laugh at the idea that women did not deserve the vote. They will mock the perception that women should not work and should simply stay at home minding the baby. They will be horrified that victims of domestic violence and assault were blamed for their own misfortune, or simply disbelieved. The people of the future will be unable to comprehend that anyone in civilised society ever thought that a man could simply be naturally better than a woman at anything. Because they will live in a world of equality - where little boys and little girls won't be told from birth that they are to have different roles and different hobbies and like different colours. The people who live

a hundred years from now will know that the only way to create oppression and hatred is to force it upon the next generation, and will know better than that. In everything that I do, I believe - no, I know with all my heart that we move towards a world where bigotry and hatred and misogyny will be a thing of the past. And that's why I stand before you today, pleading guilty of my acts in the fight for equality - because, if we do not fight for it, constantly and with every fibre of our being, then we will never achieve it.

THE END

Causeway Song by Jamie McGeechan

A story of Suffrage, of equality
Hardship and struggle in the quest for liberty
A journey from the city to the birthplace of the Bard
A nation's conscience under test, we have to fight on hard

They packed provisions on their bikes and cycled from the toon
Thirty miles ahead, no way back too soon
Over hills and over lands they peddled with their might
Tae change the world for better, for the wimmens right

A story of Suffrage, of equality
Hardship and struggle in the quest for liberty
A journey from the city to the birthplace of the Bard
A nation's conscience under test, we have to fight on hard

They packed provisions with the bombs attached to the bike
The reckoning coming soon try with all their might
Rabbie loved the ladies yes we've often heard it said
He'd surely give them freedom sure as love them in his bed

A story of Suffrage, of equality
Hardship and struggle in the quest for liberty
A journey from the city to the birthplace of the Bard
A nation's conscience under test, we have to fight on hard

Kitchners' face upon the wall your country it needs you
But what could be more honourable than loving women true?
More than mothers, daughters and wives equal to the hilt
A man's a man and so's a lass nae shame, nae loss, nae guilt

They hid their bikes upon the night and crept along the wa'
A plan to blow up Rabbie's wid surely show them a'
Tae gain attention for the Cause, a bravery to dream
They'd surely pay attention to the plight we deem

Appendix 2. *In Hidden Spaces* Script

PROLOGUE

A: Hello everybody, and welcome to Rozelle House. Known for its tearoom, where you can get a big slice of Victoria sponge for £2. A dog walkers paradise, and you can even feed the ducks, what more do you want?

K: But we want to show you a different side to this house, and tell you a story you might not already know. *beat*. So here are your maps. These are for you to keep. You can use the to help you explore all around the house and grounds.

A: Now we are aware that many of you have come with friends, or loved ones which is great, but we to encourage you to explore all around this house alone. But don't worry, I can see a few concerned faces, you will be reunited at the end in the courtyard.

K: When you hear the song over the tannoy, make your way out to the courtyard. The route is shown just there on your map. You may also notice on the map there are a lot of red keys dotted around, now these are to help guide you to the people with stories to tell. However we do encourage you to explore all of the house even the spaces without keys on them.

A: These keys will be dotted about the house on doors, letters, and other objects, so feel free to look, touch, listen and read.

K: But make sure you return them to where they used to be.

A: On your journey, you may come across a fellow audience member chatting to one of the woman of the house, if so, go away for 5 mins find another room to explore or something to do then come back and see if she is ready to speak with you.

K: So come on in. *beat*. Now in this house there is loads for you to see and do, and many people who would like to speak with you. So, use your time wisely.

A: 45 minutes to be exact.

K: And when you hear the song over the tannoy, make your way out to the courtyard for the final act.

A and K open the doors into main stairway. Gesture the audience in. P starts humming 'Bread and Roses'.

beat.

A: Now close your eyes and count to 10 slowly. When you open them again come and find us. ONE, TWO...

Rebecca

Hi, how are you doing? Would you like to play a game of cards?

Follow me.

We have to play on the window sill, this is where me and my sister used to play.

Rebecca guides the audience member to the window sill and pulls down the blind.

This is a game that me and my sister actually made up so you won't know the rules but it's really easy to follow. So, we're going to have a pack of cards just here, take them over, lay them face down. If you get an even card you have to tell me a truth. If it's a royal card, that's a Jack, a King or a Queen, you have to tell me a wish that you have. I'll do the same, obviously. And if you get a card with a little star on it then you can ask me a question, and I'll do the same. Ok? Do you mind if I go first?

Rebecca plays the game with the audience member. She reveals facts about herself, partly based on her own life and partly based on the life of Lady Jane Hamilton.

Thank you so much for playing with me, and listening to me. The way that me and my sister would end the game was that we would take a card each and we'd write a note to each other.

Rebecca hands a card to the audience member and takes one for herself.

So, it can be about the game, it can be anything, really, that you want to write. But usually we'd write something about one of the truths that came out or wish that we had, so...

Each of them write something on a card.

Ok, I will give that to you.

They exchange cards.

Thank you very much, I'm going to keep that, if that's ok? And you can take that away with you. Thanks so much for sitting with me and listening. You probably want to get back to the house so I'll let you get away but...thank you.

Poppy

Poppy moves up and down the stairs, winding a red piece of wool round and round the bannisters and singing songs like this.

*Brother, you will never know
All the things I did for you many years ago
Singer singing songs of pain
Time may spin and years may pass, the song is still the same
Tender woman mourns a man
Sits in silent sorrow with a bottle in her hand
Tell me all you need to tell
Why is it you whisper when you really need to yell*

*Trouble's in tow
Go wisely and slow*

*Brother, you will never know
All the things I did for you many years ago
Singer singing songs of pain
Time may spin and years may pass, the song is still the same
Tender woman mourns a man
Sits in silent sorrow with a bottle in her hand
Tell me all you need to tell
Why is it you whisper when you really need to yell*

*Trouble's in tow
Go wisely and slow*

*Brother, brother
Brother, you will never know
Brother, you will never know
Brother, you will never know*

Teri

Come on, hurry up!

She beckons the audience member towards her bench. She sets a timer on her phone.

Ok, so, I only have five minutes to show you this, thanks for being late. First of all, how to set up a tea tray. Kettle full of boiling water, teabags, coffee, sugar, milk, biscuits and cups to serve it in. Please remove any jewellery or watches, it's very unprofessional. I'm going to ask you to put some hand sanitiser on because your hands can be dirty from doing other things throughout the day. I'm going to ask you to pop some gloves on as well. So, to start with you'd ask me my name. Don't tell them yours, it doesn't matter. Do you want to show me if you can actually make a cup of tea?

Audience member makes a cup of tea, all the while receiving harsh feedback and instructions from Teri, who takes on the role of the guest being served. Teri then drinks the tea, and instructs the audience member to stand silently behind her.

Stay out of sight but just within earshot. Guests like that. They can communicate with you but they don't necessarily have to look at you while they're enjoying their beverage.

You might want to ask if there's anything you can do for me.

Audience member asks.

No.

The timer goes off.

Ok, that's time up. Place the tray back on the bench and please return to the rest of your work in the house. That wasn't the worst trial I've ever done, we'll be in touch.

Annaliese

Annaliese plays in the house. She runs up and down the stairs, plays hopscotch and wanders from room to room. She sings to herself. She carries a Russian doll with her.

Do you want to play a game with me? Ok, you hide this doll and I'll look for it. I'll count to 30 in German.

The audience member hides the doll. Annaliese searches for it, while asking the audience member about their life. She tells them about her life in the house, which is based on the life of Susanne Schaeffer.

Do you know how to sew? Can you teach me?

She sews with the audience member, again trading information about their lives.

Before you go, can you do something for me? Can you post this letter to my Mum and Dad? Thanks.

She wanders off.

Victoria

Victoria is alone in one of the upstairs rooms. She is reading Alice in Wonderland, or singing a lullaby. She sits on a tartan blanket and beside her are five teddy bears.

Hi, how are you? Would you like to sit with me?

The audience member sits down.

Are you just having a wander round the house then? Have you been before? What do you think of the place? It's quite grand isn't it?

And it can be very, very quiet. It's always quiet up here, and it's quite dark. I'm here a lot, actually. Just now I'm trying to learn a story for my wee girl. She likes me to know stories off by heart. I come up here because of the quiet, so I can learn stories and songs for her. That's why I have my little audience of teddies here, so I can rehearse to them. But I get cabin fever, sometimes, so it's nice when someone comes along.

Do you have children? Do you want them?

It's such a cliché, but it changes your life completely. I love my daughter so much, I want to have five in total. I've named these teddies for my future children, actually.

She picks up each teddy in turn.

This is for Jean, this is for Robert, this is for George and this is for Bute.

She asks the audience member about their childhood.

What was your favourite story? Can you tell me it?

The audience member tells their favourite story.

Who used to tell you that story? Can I read you a bit from my book? 'Lastly, she pictured to herself how this same little sister of hers would, in the after-time, be herself a grown woman; and how she would keep, through all her riper years, the simple and loving heart of her childhood: and how she would gather about her other little children, and make their eyes bright and eager with many a strange tale, perhaps even with the dream of Wonderland of long ago: and how she would feel with all their simple sorrows, and find a pleasure in all their simple joys, remembering her own child-life, and the happy summer days'. I love that, isn't it beautiful? But it's a bit sad, isn't it?

I should get back to learning this, actually. I need to tidy up first though, then I'll take you back to the main house.

She picks up each of the teddies and lies them down, naming them as she goes.

Jean. Robert. George. Bute.

She kissed each of them, then covers them with the blanket.

Night night.

To the audience member.

Let me take you back to the main house. Can I ask you to do something for me? Can you say thank you to the person who told you your favourite story? Thank you. Bye.

She leaves them at a plaque describing the life of Lady Jane Hamilton, who 'buried all but one of her five children'.

Kirsty

Kirsty sits in the courtyard with a washing line of red wool tied up around her. She scrubs clothes on a washboard, and then shakes them to the rhythm of the song Alasdair Òig Mhic 'ic Neacail, which audience members can hear on a listening post inside the house. She begins to break from this routine, and the work becomes a dance. She pull the sheets around her as a veil or a cloak or a dress. She dances round the courtyard. Then, as the song ends and begins again, she resets, taking to her work once more.

Alasdair Òig Mhic 'ic Neacail

Hìllin ò hi ho ro ho

Hìllin ò hi ho ro

Na hullairin o ho

Hi o ro ho.

B'fheàrr leam fhìn gum beirinn mac dhut

Còignear no sianar no seachdnar

'S thogainn suas air bharra bas iad

Air mo ghualainn far am faict' iad

Bheirinn glùin is cioch an asgaidh

Bheirinn ceàird an làimh gach fear dhiubh

Fear na Dhiuc 's fear na Chaiptean

Fear air long mhòir à Sasainn

Fear na dhròbhair mòr nam mairtibh

Fear na sgrìobhadair am Peairt dhiubh.

The tale of Lady Sarah and her Gypsy Johnny (listening post)

More than 100 years before this house was even dreamt up in Robert Hamilton's head there lived a young girl, a Lady Sarah Hamilton.

As was expected, she was to be married, to a landed, titled man and she would make his home her own. And though she was happy to oblige, she felt the freedom of girlhood was slipping away from her.

So, one night in the height of summer, she made her way a mile across the moorland to the fair-market. She looked with wonder at the curiosities, and danced to the jigs that the fiddlers played.

As she wandered she caught sight of a young man playing the fiddle. He was tall and broad-shouldered, with beautiful green eyes and hair as black as a winter's night. He took her hand, said 'hello', and from that moment the night was theirs. His name was Gypsy Johnny. They told stories as they sat underneath a rowan tree. He played her a ballad on his fiddle, and when the song was done she fell into his arms. Gazing at one another under the midsummer moon, the two young lovers shared the sweetest kiss that either of them would ever know.

But as the sun began to rise, the memory of her imminent betrothal returned to Lady Sarah. She ran home over the moors and could barely see her way from the tears in her eyes. And in the days that followed it seemed that, at the tender age of 17, her life had ended forever.

In time, her father arranged a marriage to the Earl of Cassilis, and that she would be moving to his estate in Maybole. Sarah agreed listlessly, because if she could not be with her Gypsy Johnny then it didn't matter much who she was married off to. And so a wedding date was set and in time Sarah, like a wilting snow drop, was married to the Earl. She tried to content herself to her new life and, though she thought of him every day, she was resigned to the fact that she would never see her love again.

Time passed and children came, and Sarah found a sort of happiness in her time with them. When she was not taking care of her bairns, she was at her needlework sewing a tapestry that told the story of a young Lady who fell in love with a Gypsy boy.

But a home without love can never be a happy home, and folks began to whisper that the Lady Sarah suffered from a chronic sadness. And these whispers must have travelled far and wide because one day, when the Earl was away on business in Westminster, the watchgate-man at Maybole saw a stranger at the entrance to the house. The fiddle he carried in his hand, he explained, was to be played at a reception to celebrate the return of the Earl.

Lady Sarah was in her sitting room when, as if from nowhere, she heard the sweet strains of a ballad from a lifetime ago. Jumping up from her seat, she ran to the window only to see her Gypsy Johnny playing in the courtyard.

Running down the steps faster than she knew she could, she burst into the courtyard and flung her arms around her love.

"I've come to take you away, Sarah, for yours is a bleak marriage and it willna' keep me from my sweetheart."

No doubt existed in her mind. And, while she wept for the children she must abandon, she left with haste. Joy returned to her heart as she climbed onto her Johnny's steed and galloped away across the hillside.

But if they had thought to escape Maybole before the Earl returned then they were mistaken. When he returned home to find his Lady gone, his response was furious and swift. He searched the countryside and found the lovers reclining by the river Ayr under the shade of a rowan tree. Before either of them could do a thing to stop it, the Earl dismounted his horse and cut down Gypsy Johnny. Sarah screamed with such pain that it shook the very earth about her, and as she fell to the ground with shock the Earl grabbed her and flung her roughly on his horse.

The Earl took her, without jewels or fine dresses, to the tower at the foot of the High Street of Maybole, where she would spend the rest of her days. Where she would watch her children ride by on fair days, children who could barely remember the hidden woman in the tower. And when the hour was late, she would sit by candle-light, sewing her tapestry of the young girl who fell in love with the young, green-eyed gypsy boy.

And I always wonder, when that tapestry was found, did Robert Hamilton know of the fate that had befallen his great-great grandmother? When he hung it in the grand dining room at Rozelle, did he know the terrible price she had paid for falling in love?

Maybe, maybe not. No one will ever know.

So much time has passed that barely a soul can remember Lady Sarah. But what remains, fragmented and hidden, is a tapestry sewn by a heartbroken soul.

Finale

Over the tannoy, the audience hear:

As we go marching, marching, in the beauty of the day.

Audience and performers alike make their way to the courtyard. The performers each stand in a spot around the centre, holding props from their scene. Poppy begins to sing.

Poppy

As we go marching, marching
In the beauty of the day
A million darkened kitchens
A thousand mill lofts grey

Are touched with all the radiance
That a sudden sun discloses
For the people hear us singing
Bread and roses, bread and roses

The other performers begin to stomp the rhythm with their feet.

All

As we go marching, marching
We battle too for men
For they are in the struggle
And together we will win
Our lives shall not be sweated
From birth until life closes
Hearts starve as well as bodies
Give us bread, but give us roses

*The performers begin to move around the circle, destroying the
props they hold in their hands.*

All

As we go marching, marching
We bring the greater days
For the rising of the women
Means the rising of the race
No more the drudge and idler
Ten that toil where one reposes
But the sharing of life's glories
Bread and roses, bread and roses

*The performers go silent. Rebecca beckons the audience to exit via
the gate. Once the audience have left the courtyard, Rebecca
closes the gate with the performers still inside. The performers
walk back into the house.*

THE END

Appendix 3. *Souvenir* script

Poppy and Victoria stand by a post box outside the old Ayr Pavilion. Victoria reads from a postcard.

Victoria

We took a drive down to the beach today. Not intentionally, just a series of events led us there. We shared a flask of soup sitting on one of the stone slopes that led down to the beach. It was seven o'clock in the evening, and so bright. And clear, and windy.

Not clear enough to see Arran, but the heads of Ayr stuck out against the evening light, and the sun was bouncing off the calm waves. I walked for what seemed like miles to reach the sea, the tide so far out. I saw rocks I've never seen before because they're normally covered by the ocean. When I eventually got there

I bent and soaked my hands in the sea, washing my face with the salt water. It cures everything. I felt like I was walking toward the sun. When I came back you'd washed the cup of our flask in the water. I found you sitting on a piece of driftwood, soaking up the sun, your hair wild against the wind. We breathe in waves. Maybe that's why we feel so calm by the sea. We conform to its movement. The ocean can't sync to us. I'm so content with the beauty of this season, and this place, the cherry blossoms on the drive in and you sitting there waiting for us to head home. I'd go anywhere with you.

Poppy

Hi everyone , welcome to Ayr beach and, of course, to *Souvenir*. My name's Poppy.

Victoria

I'm Victoria

Poppy

Thank you all for coming down today. We're going to take you over to the beach, and we'll have a bit of a chat along the way. Let's go. Right now, we're standing outside the old Ayr Pavillion, which is currently Pirate Pete's. Now I know you're thinking that Pirate Pete's is just a great name for a children's adventure play place, but really, Pirate Pete's is named after Piedro Giacomo Guariento, the great Italian pirate who sailed the seven seas, but liked Scotland the best. Most famous of course for commandeering the HMS Waverly - that's why the cafe is called The Waverly - they're constantly competing. Throughout our time at the beach today, we've got a couple of rules for you to follow if you wish to have a successful beach experience:

- 1.If you think about the sea, go to the sea.
- 2.Never, ever step in someone else's sandcastle.

3.If you hear someone singing then make sure you sing along as loud as possible

Poppy begins to sing The Tide Full In.

Victoria

Now, we're going to take this ramp here down onto the beach, if you don't like getting sand in your shoes I'd suggest you take a minute there to take them off. Not a lot of people know this about Ayr beach but it was actually a favourite of Mary, Queen of Scots. She used to travel down here at the fair and dip her toes in the sea, she felt that the South Ayrshire sand and salty air was particularly rejuvenating. Hopefully our story will have a happier end than hers.

Pause

Victoria

I just want to draw your attention to what we can see on the horizon here. The island in front of you is Arran, known as the Sleeping Goddess because, as local myth tells it, an ancient Celtic Goddess lay down here to rest after her heart was broken. Poppy and I haven't been there for ages though so we don't know much more about it. Along at the end here we can see the Heads of Ayr. A lot of people think the cliffs are called that because they stick out in the way they do. In fact, they're named for the shipwreck that took place in 1796 when Pietro Guariento's ship was lured there by sirens. The stern or 'head' of the ship crashed into the rocks and to this day people celebrate the siren maidens saving Ayrshire from Pirate Pete's reign of terror.

Rule number 4. Wash your face and hands in the water. The salt cures everything.

Rule number 5. Always go to the beach when it's raining.

Rule number 6. Write your name in the sand before you leave so that someone will remember you were here.

Poppy¹¹

I could tell you a story about what happened here, 100 years ago. I could tell you about the huts they used to have for changing into your swimsuits and the stands selling rock candy. I could paint you a picture of all the activities and entertainments that would be going on behind you along the esplanade. But right now, standing here looking out in front of you, you're seeing exactly what they would have seen. You're looking at the same horizon, dominated by the same lump of rock that people have been looking at for thousands of years. And, make no mistake, everyone stops and looks. No one wanders along, unaffected by what they see

¹¹ Due to technical issues, the following section (up to p.209) does not appear in the performance film.

before them. Year after year, century after century, we come back to the water, and we see the same thing that we've always seen.

Victoria

What happens in the next hour is, to all intents and purposes, a performance. But this isn't a you-sit-still-while-we-play-characters for ninety minutes type of thing. There isn't one story to tell here, there are hundreds. Some of what you'll hear comes from old Ayrshire myths. Some of it comes from stories told to us by people we've met here. Some of it we made up. We'll have some sandwiches and fizzy juice and we'll sing some songs - we want you to sing along if you know the words.

Poppy

We just want to spend a bit of time on the beach with you.

Victoria

We want to give you something to remember.

Poppy and Victoria perform a movement section based on a trip to the beach.

Victoria

Did you know that we have the exact same percentage of salt in our blood as sea water? That's why we have salt in our sweat, and in our tears. We have the same make up as the ocean...I think that's why we feel drawn to it. There's something in the salty air that makes us feel like we belong. Maybe it reminds us of a simpler time, you know, when people were shorter and lived by the water.

Poppy

Or maybe we're all selkies, searching for our lost skins and trying to get back home.

Victoria

Aye, all the way back to Falkirk

Poppy

Mate, those are kelpies.

Victoria

What?

Poppy

At Falkirk it's the Kelpies. They're water horses. I'm talking about selkies.

Victoria

What's the difference?

Poppy

Selkies are more like mermaids but they've got seal skins instead of fish tails. A bit more realistic.

Victoria

Probably less glamorous though.

Poppy

So like the myth goes that the selkie women lived in the sea, and at night they would come ashore, cast off their seal skins and dance on the beach. Sometimes, men from the town would come down and steal a seal skin, and that would force the selkie woman to live with him as his wife. The woman was made to live and have children with her captor, searching the house at every opportunity for her seal skin so she could get back to the sea. I mean, the selkie myths never really have a happy ending, if the she eventually gets back to the shore, she's leaving her kids behind, and popping up whenever she can to check that they're okay. Like, she was screwed no matter what choice she made.

Victoria

That's patriarchy for you.

Poppy

Do you want to find a selkie?

Victoria

Sorry?

Poppy

I know how to get one.

Victoria

I mean, you just said they're a myth

Poppy

Well that's the theory but have you ever tried to summon one?

Victoria

I can't say I have

Poppy

I saw one once off the coast of Arran.

Victoria

Right.

Poppy

Some of the stories say they're the souls of drowned women. So, to summon them, you have to be sad.

Victoria
Because they're dead?

Poppy
Yup.

Victoria
Have you ever successfully summoned one before?

Poppy
Never tried.

Victoria
How does it work then?

Poppy
Ok, so, you have to go up to the sea and, like, channel the selkie
in your mind.

Victoria
Channel it?

Poppy
Yeah. Like, think of a selkie. Then you have to weep for them.

Victoria
How poetic.

Poppy
You have to give the ocean seven tears, and that summons the
selkie.

Victoria
Exactly seven?

Poppy
Exactly seven. Shall we give it a go?

Victoria
I thought we were gonna build a sandcastle first.

Poppy
Aye, well, we can do that after.

Victoria
Why do you want to summon a selkie?

Poppy
Something to do, innit?

Victoria
Right...

Poppy

Because, like, what's the point of being here if we don't do something memorable? Look at all this water, it's an entire world that's totally hidden from us. We could have a little part of it.

Victoria

Like a selkie pet.

Poppy

Did you not listen to the story? That's bad form mate. You've got to set it free after.

Victoria

Ok.

Poppy

You in?

Victoria

I think I'm just going to stay here with everyone, but you go for it.

Poppy walks to the water and makes a very exaggerated show of crying into the sea.

Poppy

I'm not really sad enough to give seven tears to the ocean.

Poppy

Nah, me neither. Should we have a sandwich?

Victoria

So do you think if you were a selkie you would be able to give up your life and go back to the sea. Give up your child and go back into the water?

Poppy

You crawled out of the sea, straight into my arms. And I wrapped you up in this towel and felt like I was cuddling the whole world.

Surrounded by the screaming laughter and the swells of the sea, you were so still. With the sun beating down, I dried your hair in a towel as you made up songs about the water and built a sandcastle. I could live in these sunlit days for ever.

Victoria lies back on the sand. Poppy builds a belly on her out of sand.

Victoria

Water has been on my mind a lot recently. Am I drinking enough? Are my ankles swelling? How much of me is made of water at this moment? I think the human body is supposed to be around 80% water, but some days it feels like I'm entirely liquid. Tears leak from

my eyes at the slightest stimulus. My bladder seems constantly full and my breasts have swollen almost to bursting. I consist only of water, it swirls inside me constantly finding new ways to escape.

I stand by the shore, feeling the gentle waves as they lap against my aching feet. I think of the watery world that I've created, the only world that she knows. She swims inside me, twisting and turning in the calm waters, dancing around as she grows. As the water kisses my toes she twirls around. Can she hear the waves? Can she feel me shiver as the water, still freezing even in June, splashes my limbs? Tiny fish swim around, the water holding them, nourishing them and helping them to grow. I touch my belly. I look out to sea, over to Arran and the horizon beyond, and the world seems to open up in front of me.

It's 2am. I feel a jolt of pain and then a sudden gush. The night is cold and the wind are howling. The car moves along, fast yet safe, as we move towards the final part of this voyage. I can't stay still. The waves of tightening are too much and when my body is still I can't help but cry out. I am lost in an ocean of time, unable to speak and willing it all to be over. They tell me it's time, they take me along the corridor and help me into the water.

Finally my body feels safe, safe enough to release her. Up and down, in and out, creating a tide within the tiny bathtub. She's born into the water. I catch her in my arms and hold her close to me. She doesn't cry just looks up and blows bubbles like a little pink fish. She's a complete stranger and yet I know everything about her. She's so peaceful, so happy to meet me. So at home in our little ocean, just the two of us. We'll name her after an island, and we'll take her to the seaside. We'll take her to the horizon, and show her the whole world that's in front of her. We'll let the waves lap around her ankles and we'll hear her laugh. We have all of that ahead of us...we have everything ahead of us.

Poppy

Sirens can be found near any body of water, disguised in human form. The only way to protect yourself is to refuse their requests.

Rule number 7: You have to say no to whatever I ask, even though you want to say yes.

-Are you okay?

Will you come home with me?

-Do you know where you're going?

-Can I go with you?

-Will you miss me?

Do you love me?

Didn't I fix you?

Can you keep me safe?

Will you take my hand?

-Are you coming with me?
-Can we stay like this forever?
Are you coming home soon?
Will I see you again?
Do you think it will stay this way forever?

Victoria

No

Pause.

Victoria

On the days when I feel hungry I wish I could go down to the sea. Walk to the beach, see the sun set behind the mountains and feel something. On the days where I am starved I wish I could walk down to the beach and have the waves wash something ashore for me.

Poppy

Rule Number 8: When the seaside makes you melancholic sing some classic beach hits to ward away the sad thoughts.

Victoria

Nice segue.

Under the Boardwalk song

Victoria

A lot of people that we've met felt like this beach had lost something; that it wasn't what it used to be. So, for the benefit of those who didn't visit Ayr beach in its heyday we present: A vintage trip to Ayr in 3 minutes flat.

V/O

Poppy's Gran

It's 1976 - one of the hottest summers for many years. I'm 6 months pregnant and waddling along Ayr seafront with my husband.

We've brought my mother along for the day, travelling 15 miles from the mining village of Dalmellington. Although I had worked in Ayr for the past six years, it was still very much the big town on the coast, where a day at the beach was considered a great day out and where we mingled with families from Glasgow who had arrived en masse for the Glasgow Fair Fortnight. The fine sandy beach was crammed with holidaymakers and day-trippers stretched out on plaid blankets or striped deck chairs hired from vendors on the prom. It was always a challenge to erect the deck chair without trapping your fingers.

Families were paddling in the sea, children running hysterically into the water and grannies with dresses tucked into their knickers, gingerly negotiating the lapping waves. Sandcastles and

pies were built with pail and spade - usually the most intricate ones would be trampled by football enthusiasts or by those with an appetite for destruction.

Frank Codona's Fairground behind the old Ayr baths was home to the Big Wheel, the Waltzer and various stalls where you could win a soft toy, or, if you were lucky, a goldfish that usually survived for a whole week once you got home.

The small boating lake was always popular, with queues forming along the promenade as would-be sailors negotiated the small island in the middle of the lake, manoeuvring the boats, slowly and deliberately, as they soaked up the rays from the elusive Scottish sun.

Adjacent to the boating lake was the seafront jewel in the crown - the small train, running round in a circular track, the carriages transporting parents and toddlers in a continuous loop of delight as the children sat wide-eyed and excited on their seaside trip to nowhere. Life seemed simpler then - no technology to distract from the days outdoor activities.

Victoria

Last summer I remember watching hordes of people in Wellington Square on their phones. I had no idea what they were doing, all standing completely still in random positions around the square. Someone told me they were all playing Pokemon Go...apparently the statue in the middle of the square was PokeStop where you could pick up characters for the game. I didn't really know how I felt about this. Like, no one was interacting with anyone else, they were all glued to their phones. But then again, at least it got people to go outside.

Poppy

The children's play park was home to those bouncing on the see-saw, soaring high on the swings or climbing fearlessly on the monkey puzzle. A small sandpit kept the toddlers amused as their older brothers and sisters supervised from a distance.

The Ayr Pavilion sat majestically in the background, its Victorian turrets acting as a landmark for the Lost Children's Corner and where, as the last day-trippers headed from home, the teenage clubbers in platforms and flares queued in the esplanade awaiting entrance to the latest rave or live rock-band.

Victoria

We queue up at the Wellington for our fish suppers with all the laughing school children and daydreaming holiday makers. We follow the sounds of the waves breaking all the way down to the front, and the skyline opens up before us. It's freezing but we can't stop smiling as we take our shoes off and feel the sand shifting beneath our feet. We're not kids any more and yet we've never been

so young. The water is so cold that it stings our feet, but you take my hand and suddenly your skin against mine is all I can feel. We walk along the front, sharing secrets that are hidden from everyone by the cries of the gulls and the lapping of the waves on the shore. We climb up into the sand dunes and huddle under my coat, creating our own world hidden from the ambling crowds. From just over the top of our fabric fortress we can see Arran. You say that there's snow still lying on top of Goat Fell, and I imagine us going there together. With the ocean ahead of us and sky all around, we imagine all the adventures that lie in wait. The horizon is ours, and the world is filled with possibility and hope. We're on the edge of everything, swimming in promises of what is yet to come and wrapped up in the never ending sky.

Poppy

As early evening approached, the sunburnt and tired hordes made their way past the County buildings, rounding off their day with a fish supper from the Wellington Cafe.

The trains and buses eventually transport the day-trippers home and I make my way, by red double decker bus, back to the Doon Valley, leaving behind a deserted beach, with the North Arran Hills, known as the Sleeping Warrior, as the backdrop. Ayr seafront in its vibrant heyday - an experience not to be missed and one that has sadly disappeared into the mists of time!

Poppy starts playing The Dark Island

Victoria

This song isn't technically about Ayr, just so you know. But, then again, it could be about anywhere in the world that you miss and want to go back to. It could even be about that island right over there. Join in if you know it.

Rule Number 8: Look out as far as you can, and realise that the sea keeps on going even when you think you can see the end.

The Dark Island song.

Victoria

I don't really know where we go from here.

Poppy

We could just stay by the shore.

Victoria

Should we just move here?

Poppy

I think maybe I could move to Arran. I know we've been, but it was a long time ago.

Victoria

I was too old to get on the boat for free, so we all lied and said I was a year younger than I was. It worked. I don't remember anything about Arran.

Poppy

Me neither. But I think I could move there. It doesn't seem too far away. Close enough. I could turn into one of those girls who go on long walks on the beach and climbs mountains just for the sake of it. Maybe I'd learn old folk songs and feel some connection to the land that's surrounded by water. I think maybe I could move to Arran. You'd need a boat to get to me.

Victoria

You're being too romantic about Arran.

Poppy

Yeah, probably.

Pause

Victoria

Rule Number 9: Always run into the sea as fast as your can - you'll be fine once you get your shoulders under.

Poppy

Do you want that envelope now?

Victoria

Oh yeah, thanks.

Poppy fetches an envelope and hands it to Victoria.

Victoria

Opening a letter.

If you walk along the beach far enough then you reach Greenan castle. It's a ruin now, but it looks nice up there on the cliff. Once you pass by there's a solitary house that looks down on the shore. I walked all the way along there every day for a week, and on the third day the old woman who lives in the house came down to ask me what I was doing. I explained that I was working on a show about the beach. She seemed fairly nonplussed by all of this, and just wished me luck. The next day, as I walked my route, I saw her again. She said hello, chatted about the weather for a minute, then gave me this. She said she'd been thinking about me, about the things I was writing about. Then she asked me to share it with you all today.

Poppy moves behind Victoria as she speaks.

The patterns move in waves like my hair does when it's filled with salt.

I get more pains than I used to.
It's as though all that water never really left me, like I'm more
liquid now than I used to be.

Softer.

More malleable.

Easier to break.

I'm not as hard as I once was.

The salt pours into old wounds but it doesn't sting like it used
to.

I suppose that's how you become harder; you just get used to it.

I take my hair out of my hat and the wind makes it dance.

It's wild.

I feel wild.

I feel good.

I want to keep searching. I want to keep feeling the wind on my
face. I don't want to be tamed by roads or bridges or pathways. I
want to be free.

Why do you have to put your stamp on me? Why do you need to take
something that's wild and free and put it in a box?

I won't be neat for you.

You can carve your words and your paths all over me and and the
water will rush in and it'll all wash away.

I don't need anyone to know where I am. I don't need to know what
people think of me. I don't need anyone to know what I'm doing.

It's enough that I know where I am.

The air and the waves embolden me and I'm not scared any more.

And I have a home to go to. And I have little faces to wash and
hands to clean. And I have food to make. I have things to get back
to.

But not now.

Now is for skimming the shoreline and breathing deeply.

Now is for me. Me and the waves.

Everything will wash away and I'll start again.

Poppy

We've got one more story we want to tell you, and we want to tell
you right by the water. You don't have to swim, you don't even
have to paddle, but if you want to dip your toes in then now is
the time to get your shoes and socks off.

Victoria

Rule Number 9: Run into the sea as fast as you can - you'll be
fine once you get your shoulders under.

Victoria leads the audience to the shore.

Victoria

My favourite part of the front was down at Seafield. At the fair,
everyone from all around Glasgow travelled down to take in the sea
air and wash off the dust of the city in the water. The middle of
the beach, this bit here, was heavin' with holidaymakers planting
their windbreaks and staking their claim on a few square feet of

sand. So my Ma would take us all the way along to Seafield. Nobody was bothered about setting up camp down there because you couldn't get a good view of the Heads and the entertainment was all the way back down by the Pavilion, so it was like our own wee playground.

Poppy

Da never took the fair off, it was his busiest time what with all the extra bodies in the town. So it was just the two of us.

Victoria

And Ma, and every day was like something off the front of a postcard. We'd go to The Bents, that's the flat bit right at the front of Seafield, and play rounders, cricket, tennis and races.

Poppy

When it got to lunchtime Ma would shout us over for our picnic.

Victoria

Every day it was the same nutritious feast:

Both of Us

a doorstep of plain bread covered in jam.

Victoria

After that we'd raid through the bins to find glass bottles that we could return for a penny and buy swiss rolls with our riches.

Poppy

The extra helping of jam meant you were at 2 of your 5 a day.

Victoria

Gave us the strength to strip down to our vest and knickers and run into the sea. Ma would make a show of objecting, shouting after us that we'd catch our death or be eaten by a jellyfish, but she loved the chance to have a wee kip - with one eye open, of course, to make sure we weren't trying to drown each other.

Poppy

Which we were.

Victoria

We'd pack up at 5, get the bus back into the town for Da and then wander home with our free chips from the cafe. The next day, we'd be up at 7 in the morning to live the whole day all over again.

Every day, every summer, the three of us down by the sea.

I was five when she left us. I didn't really understand at the time. Ma was tired. She was poorly and she couldn't take us to the beach today. She was just having a wee sleep.

Poppy

But she can sleep on the beach, she always sleeps on the beach and we play in the water.

Victoria

Not today, she needs her rest. She can't look after you today.

Poppy

I can help, I can look after her.

Victoria

No, just run along and play in your room.

Poppy

We can take her to the sea, the sea is supposed to fix things. Da says the salt water can cure anything.

Victoria

Leave her be.

Poppy

Where is she?

Victoria

She's tired.

Poppy

Where is she?

Victoria

She's resting.

Poppy

Where is she?

Victoria

She's in a better place now.

Poppy

When's she getting back?

Victoria

She's not coming back love.

Poppy

I didn't understand.

Victoria

Remember when she used to talk about the selkies? How they stayed for a while, but they were never meant for the land? It's like that. She was only meant to be here for a while.

Poppy
So she's gone to the sea?

Victoria
No, she's gone to the sky.

Poppy
Who's this?

Victoria
It's Da's new friend.

Poppy
Da's new girlfriend.

Victoria
Your new mum.

Poppy
I don't like my new mum. She's not like Ma.

Victoria
Why?

Poppy
She never takes us down the front. Says she's got things to do but she just sits in the back green smoking and gossiping with the neighbours. She took us out one day, a few weeks back after we kept asking. She wouldn't play rounders with us, just wanted us to sit quietly while she sat in the sun. We convinced her to let us play in the sea, just like Ma had. The water felt colder that day, but seeing the sky stretch out before us gave us some kind of hope, I think. We danced around in the water. I felt some seaweed drift by my leg and I squealed at the sliminess of it.

Victoria
Then you started screaming.

Poppy
It was a jellyfish! Jings, it stung like nothing else. The whole beach turned around except her, she just sat smoking her fags and ignoring us.

Victoria
That's not true.

Poppy
It is! I was screaming the place down and she didn't even bother.

Victoria
You're being dramatic.

Poppy

It was only when you picked me up and plonked me onto her lap that she took any notice. And even then all she did was shout at me.

Victoria

Aye, she wasn't happy.

Poppy

Made us pack everything up and marched us home. Said it was my fault, that I'd ruined the day for everyone. Da didn't even say a word.

Victoria

He never did, even when Ma was alive.

Poppy

She'd never have shouted at me like that.

Victoria

You're talking a load of rubbish, Ma shouted at us too.

Poppy

Maybe, but then she'd have held me after. She'd have sung me a wee song to calm me down, and stroked my hair. She'd have called me daft and then wrapped me in a towel and kissed my head.

Victoria

You talk about her like she was an angel, and our stepmother was the devil herself. Ma wasn't perfect, you know.

Poppy

She wasn't an angel, she was much stronger than that. She was the ocean. She was the sea on a warm summer day, and we were all contained within her. We'd play and swim and be pulled in different directions but the currents she created held us all together. I was never the same after she went.

Victoria

It's the mother that holds everybody together.

Poppy

Why do we never come down here anymore?

Victoria

Too many jellyfish?

Poppy

I'm serious.

Victoria

Because we can't be where she isn't.

Poppy

We used to sit here, on the edge of the world, with everything in front of us.

Victoria

The sea feels colder than it used to.

Poppy

We should come here more often. We should come together.

Victoria

We're too old for rounders and sandcastles now.

Poppy

Maybe. But somehow when I'm standing here I feel young again.

Victoria

On the edge of everything.

Poppy

Tell you what, I could go a piece and jam.

Victoria

We should come here again. We should have days on the beach together.

Poppy

It's not like it used to be.

Victoria

It doesn't matter. Different doesn't have to mean worse.

Poppy

We should go for a swim.

Victoria

Now?

Poppy

Yeah.

Victoria

It's freezing.

Poppy

Only until you get your shoulders under.

Victoria

You're aff yer heid.

Poppy
You sound like Ma. Remember how much she'd laugh when we screamed
at the cold?

Victoria
On the count of 3?

Poppy
You're on.

P&V
1,2,3!

Both run into the water and swim off towards Arran.

THE END

Appendix 4. Ethical procedures

4.1

The following section details the formal ethical procedures undertaken over the course of my research. During this study, it was (and currently remains) UWS protocol that all research involving human participants are reviewed and approved by the School of Education ethics committee. As my research did not involve any work with vulnerable groups, it was not considered high risk. I provided the committee with an ethics form for each of the three projects, and ethical approval was granted via email. In each of the projects in this study, those participating in the research (audience members, performers and heritage staff) were provided with information sheets regarding the study and consent forms. Participants were informed that they could withdraw their responses up to three months before submission of this thesis. Below are copies of the information sheets and consent forms used in this study.

4.2 Consent form

Consent Form

Title of Project: Ayrshire Herstories: Reconfiguring specific South Ayrshire heritage sites through feminist performance practice

Name of Researcher: Victoria Bianchi

1. I confirm that I have read and understand the Information Sheet the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.
2. I give my consent to (please circle as appropriate)
 - a. Participating in an interview (approx 20 mins)
 - b. Audio recording of the interview
 - c. Completing the Questionnaire (approx 15-20 mins)
 - d. Participating in a focus group (approx 30-40 mins)
 - e. Audio Recording of the focus group
3. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason.
4. Please indicate whether you agree to take part in this study.

I **agree** to take part in the above study

I **do not agree** to take part in the above study

Name of Participant	Date	Signature
---------------------	------	-----------

Researcher	Date	Signature
------------	------	-----------

4.3 Information Sheet

About the project

Ayrshire Herstories: Reconfiguring specific South Ayrshire heritage sites through feminist performance practice

Researcher

Victoria Bianchi - [REDACTED]

Supervisor

Dr Anne Pirrie - [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Invitation Paragraph

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why this research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Please take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

Thank you for taking the time to read this.

What is the purpose of the study?

This research is being carried out to address a gap within current research regarding women in heritage studies and performance studies. It is a Practice-as-Research study that will disseminate real experiences of women related to specific heritage sites through performance practice. The aim of the study is to offer a renewed understanding of the space, and to explore the treatment of gender issues within the heritage site.

The key concern of my research is that of women in heritage sites. It is based in the understanding that live performance has the potential for radical, immediate intervention in heritage sites.

Heritage is understood to be an influential factor in the formation of identity. My research aims to offer a model whereby heritage sites can begin to move towards a more gender-neutral representation of history. The aspiration is that problematic gender stereotypes won't, therefore, continue to be reinforced in wider society.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen because, as an audience member, you have seen the practical output of this research. Your opinions on the work are vital in developing a deeper understanding of heritage performance.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you decide to take part you are still free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason.

What will happen to me if I take part?

If you decide to take part in this research project, you will be invited to participate in a focus group. This will take place in the Education pavilion and will last between 30-40 minutes. You can leave the focus group at any point.

If you do not wish to be involved in the focus group, you may opt to complete an online questionnaire that will ask about your experiences of viewing the performance. If you wish to complete the questionnaire, please do so before [date]. A link will be provided by the researcher at your request.

Will my taking part in the study be kept confidential?

All information that is collected about you during the course of the research, will be kept strictly confidential and not passed onto any third parties. Any information obtained will be kept in a safe location and computer files will be protected by password access. Pseudonyms will be used in any publication arising from the research in order to protect the anonymity of those who participate.

What will happen to the results of this research study?

This research is being carried out as part of my PhD Studies and is supported by the School Of Education at UWS. The results of this study will be made available through the UWS upon request.

Contact for further information

My dissertation supervisor, Dr Anne Pirrie, and the Ethics Committee have reviewed this project. For further information regarding this study, please do not hesitate to contact me. If you have any concerns regarding the conduct of this research project, please contact the School of Education Ethics Officer:

Dr Lynne Grant-McMahon

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 5. Presentations and Publications

Articles:

'The path to CauseWay: Developing a feminist site-specific performance practice at the Robert Burns Birthplace Museum'. *Platform*, 9(2), pp. 55-78, 2016.

Papers and Talks:

Conference Paper: 'Performing Herstory', (In)visible Stories: An investigation into the status of ICH in Scotland, University of the West of Scotland, May 2018.

Conference Paper: 'In Hidden Spaces: The untold stories of the women of Rozelle House, Ayr', Between Spaces symposium, University of Chichester, July 2017

Competition presentation: 'Ayrshire Herstories', Three Minute Thesis (finalist), University of the West of Scotland, February 2016

Invited talk: 'Myth and legend in South Ayrshire's heritage trail', South Ayrshire Place Partnership Inauguration, Ayr, October 2015

Invited paper: 'Burns and the suffragettes: exploring Herstory at Robert Burns Birthplace Museum'. Performing Methodologies symposium, University of the West of Scotland, Centre for Contemporary Arts, November 2015

9. References

- Abramović, M., 1988. *The Lovers: The Great Wall Walk* [performance]. Great Wall of China.
- Aitchison, C.C., 1996. 'Monumentally male? a guided tour of the heritage tourism industry'. In: *Trouble and Strife: A Radical Feminist Journal*, 14(2). [online] Available at: <<http://www.troubleandstrife.org/articles/issue-34/monumentally-male/>> [Accessed 28th April 2015].
- Aitchison, J., 1994. *The Women of Rozelle (prior to 1860)*. Unpublished.
- Anon, 1914. 'Votes for Women, Gunpowder for Burns'. In: *Glasgow Herald*, 9 July 1914. [online] Available at: <<http://digital.nls.uk/scotlandspages/timeline/1914.html>> [Accessed 22 May 2015].
- Anzaldúa, G., 1987. *Borderlands/La Frontera*. San Francisco: Spinsters/AuntLute Books.
- Austin, G., 1990. 'Feminist Theories: Paying attention to women'. In: Goodman, L., & de Gay, J., (eds.) 1998. *The Routledge Reader in Gender and Performance*. London: Routledge. pp.136 – 143.
- Barrett, E. & Bolt, B., (eds.) 2007. *Practise as Research: Approaches to Creative Arts Enquiry*. London: I.B. Tauris & Co.Ltd.
- BBC News, 2015. *Kirsteen McCue is first woman to address Burns club*. [online] Available at:<<http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-scotland-glasgow-west-30948428>> [Accessed 18th January 2018].
- Bennett, S., 2013. *Theatre & Museums*. Hampshire: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Berger, C., 2016. 'A Chain of Creation, Continuation, Continuity'. In: *Performance Research*, 21(2), pp.17-24.
- Beswick, K., 2017. *Is This Love? Performance On The Streets Of New York*. [conference paper] Between Spaces Symposium, University of Chichester, 30 June 2017.
- Bianchi, V., 2016. 'The path to CauseWay: Developing a feminist site-specific performance practice at the Robert Burns Birthplace Museum' In: *Platform: Journal of Theatre and Performing Arts*, 9(2), pp.55-78.
- Blunt, A. & Rose, G.,1994. *Writing Women and Space: Colonial and Postcolonial Geographies*. New York: The Guilford Press.
- Bly, N., 1896. 'Champion Of Her Sex: Miss Susan B. Anthony'. *Thehairpin.com*. The New York World, 1896. [online] Available at: <<http://thehairpin.com/2014/04/nellie-bly-interviews-susan-b-anthony/>> [Accessed 6th August 2015].
- Bock, G., 1989. 'Women's history and gender history: aspects of an international debate'. In: *Gender & History*, 1(1), pp.7-30.

- Bohlin, A., Martins Holmberg, I., Saltzman, K. & Sjölander-Lindqvist, A., 2012. 'Dynamics of inclusion and exclusion in heritage: reflections from a Ph.D. course'. In: *International Journal of Heritage Studies*, 18(6), pp.654-656.
- Braidotti, R., 1994 [2011]. *Nomadic Subjects: Embodiment and Sexual Difference in Contemporary Feminist Theory*. New York: Columbia University Press.
- Braun, V. & Clarke, V., 2006. 'Using thematic analysis in psychology'. In: *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), pp.77-101.
- Brecht, B., 1964 [2014]. *Brecht on theatre*. London: Bloomsbury Methuen Drama.
- Campbell, J., 1949 [2008]. *The hero with a thousand faces*. California: New World Library.
- Carlyle, T., 1840 [1993]. *On heroes, hero-worship, and the heroic in history* (Vol. 1). Los Angeles: University of California Press.
- Carpenter, J.R., 2016. 'Writing Coastlines'. In: *Performance Research*, 21(2), pp.12-16.
- Case, S.E., 1988 [2008]. *Feminism and theatre*. Hampshire: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Casey, E., 1998. *The Fate of Place*. Los Angeles: University of California Press.
- Clement, G., 1996. *Care, autonomy, and justice: Feminism and the ethic of care*. Boulder: Westview Press.
- Cochrane, K., 2013. *All the rebel women: The rise of the fourth wave of feminism*. Norwich: Guardian Books.
- Cresswell, T., 2015. *Place: An Introduction*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.
- Crooke, E., 2010. 'The politics of community heritage: motivations, authority and control'. In: *International Journal of Heritage Studies*, 16(1-2), pp.16-29.
- Denzin, N.K., 2010. 'Moments, mixed methods, and paradigm dialogs'. In: *Qualitative inquiry*, 16(6), pp.419-427.
- Dolezal, L., 2010. 'The (In)visible Body: Feminism, Phenomenology, and the Case of Cosmetic Surgery'. In: *Hypatia: A Journal of Feminist Philosophy*, 25(2), pp.357-375.
- Drever, E., 1995. *Using Semi-Structured Interviews in Small-Scale Research. A Teacher's Guide*. Edinburgh: The Scottish Council for Research in Education.
- Dreyer, E., 2005. 'Articulations of the city as a gendered construct: research'. In: *De Arte*, 71, pp.4-13.
- Duncan, M.C., 2006. 'Gender warriors in sport: Women and the media'. In: *Handbook of sports and media*, pp.231-252.
- Embree, L. & Fisher, L., (eds.) 2000. *Feminist Phenomenology*. Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Publishers.

Featherstone, D. & Painter, J., (eds.) 2013. *Spatial politics: essays for Doreen Massey*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.

Franks, A., 2012. 'Coffee Cup Ecologies: Some reflections on gathering'. In: *Performance Research*, 17(4), pp.42-48.

Freeman, J., 2010. *Blood, sweat & theory: research through practice in performance*. Oxfordshire: Libri Publishing.

Freshwater, H., 2009. *Theatre & Audience*. Hampshire: Palgrave Macmillan.

Geis S., Fuller R. & Rush J., 1986. 'Lovers of AIDS victims: psychosocial stresses and counselling needs'. In: *Death Studies*, 10, pp.43-53.

Gibson, J., 2011. 'Saying it right: creating ethical verbatim theatre'. In: *NEO: journal for higher degree research students in the social sciences and humanities*, 4, pp.1-18.

Giles, M.V., (ed.) 2014. *Mothering in the age of neoliberalism*. Ontario: Demeter Press.

Gray, C., 1996. 'Inquiry through practice: developing appropriate research strategies'. Cited in: Haseman, B., 2006. 'A manifesto for performative research'. In: *Media International Australia incorporating Culture and Policy*, 118(1), pp.98-106.

Greer, G., 1970 [1992] *The Female Eunuch*. London: HarperCollins Publishers.

Grossberg, L., 2010 'Theorising Context'. In: Featherstone, D. & Painter, J., (eds.) 2013. *Spatial politics: essays for Doreen Massey*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. pp.32-41.

Gunter, B., Nicholas, D., Huntington, P. & Williams, P., 2002. 'Online versus offline research: implications for evaluating digital media'. In: *Aslib Proceedings*, 54(4), pp. 229-239. MCB UP Ltd.

Haesbert, R., 2013. 'A Global Sense of Place and Multi-territoriality: Notes for Dialogue from a 'Peripheral' Point of View'. In: Featherstone, D. & Painter, J. (eds.), 2013. *Spatial politics: essays for Doreen Massey*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. pp.146-157.

Hardt, M. & Negri, A., 2001. *Empire*. Massachusetts: Harvard University Press.

Haseman, B., 2006. 'A manifesto for performative research'. In: *Media International Australia incorporating Culture and Policy*, 118(1), pp.98-106.

Haseman, B., 2007. 'Rupture and recognition: identifying the performance research paradigm'. In: Barrett, E. & Bolt, B., (eds.) 2007. *Practise as Research: Approaches to Creative Arts Enquiry*. London: I.B. Tauris & Co.Ltd. pp.147-158.

Hawkins, H., 2014. *For Creative Geographies: Geography, Visual Arts and the Making of Worlds*. New York: Routledge.

Heddon, D., 2008. *Autobiography and Performance*. Hampshire: Palgrave Macmillan.

Heddon, D. & Turner, C., 2012. 'Walking Women: Shifting the Tales and Scales of Mobility'. In: *Contemporary Theatre Review*, 22(2), pp.224-236.

- Heilmann, A., 2000. *New Woman Fiction: Women Writing First-Wave Feminism*. Hampshire: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Hopes, D., 2015. *RE: Information about RBBM*. [e-mail]. (Personal communication, 16 February 2015).
- Hughes, B., McKie, L., Hopkins, D. & Watson, N., 2005. 'Love's labours lost? Feminism, the disabled people's movement and an ethic of care'. In: *Sociology*, 39(2), pp.259-275.
- Huxley, J., 1966. 'Introduction: A Discussion on Ritualisation of Behaviour in Animals and Man'. In: *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London*. Series B, Biological Sciences, 251, pp.249-271.
- Iannello, K.P., 1992. *Decisions without hierarchy: Feminist interventions in organization theory and practice*. New York: Routledge.
- Ingold, T., 2007 [2016]. *Lines: a brief history*. Oxon: Routledge.
- Ingold, T. & Vergunst, J.L., (eds.) 2008. *Ways of walking: Ethnography and practice on foot*. Hampshire: Ashgate Publishing, Ltd.
- Jackson, A., 2011. 'Engaging the audience: negotiating performance in the museum'. In: Jackson, A., & Kidd, J. (eds.) 2011. *Performing heritage: Research, practice and innovation in museum theatre and live interpretation*. Manchester: Manchester University Press. pp.11-25.
- Jackson, A., & Kidd, J., (eds.) 2011. *Performing heritage: Research, practice and innovation in museum theatre and live interpretation*. Manchester: Manchester University Press.
- Jones, O., 2005. 'An ecology of emotion, memory, self and landscape'. In: Bondi, L., Davidson, J. & Smith M., 2005. *Emotional geographies*. Oxon: Routledge. pp.205-218.
- Katriel, T., 1997. 'Pioneering women revisited: representations of gender in some Israeli settlement museums'. In: *Women's Studies International Forum*, 20(5/6), pp.675-787.
- Kaye, N., 2000. *Site-specific art: performance, place and documentation*. Oxon: Routledge.
- Kellner, D., 1999. 'Theorizing McDonaldization: A multiperspectivist approach'. In: Smart, B., (ed.) 1999. *Resisting McDonaldization*. London: SAGE. pp.186-206.
- Kershaw, B., 2007. *Theatre ecology: environments and performance events*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Kershaw, B., 2011. 'Practice as Research through Performance'. In: Smith H. & Dean., R.T. (eds.), 2011. *Practice-led Research, Research-led Practice in the Creative Arts*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press. pp.104-125.
- Kester, G., 2004. *Conversation Pieces: Community and communication in modern art*. California: University of California Press.

- Kidd, J., 2011. 'Performing the knowing archive: heritage performance and authenticity'. In: *International Journal of Heritage Studies*, 17(1), pp.22-35.
- Kincheloe, J.L., 2001. 'Describing the bricolage: Conceptualizing a new rigor in qualitative research'. In: *Qualitative inquiry*, 7(6), pp.679-692.
- Kolodny, A., 1996. 'Unearthing Herstory.' In: Glotfelty, C. & Fromm, H., (eds.) 1996. *The Ecocriticism Reader*. Athens: University of Georgia Press. pp.170-81.
- Kwon, M., 2002. *One place after another: Site-specific art and locational identity*. Massachusetts: MIT press.
- Lee, H.J., 2002. *The effect of music and reminiscence on the mood of elderly persons with dementia*. (Doctoral dissertation).
- Lefebvre, H., 1974 [1991]. *The Production of Space*. Oxford: Blackwell Publishing.
- Leneman, L., 2004. 'Parker, Frances Mary (1875–1924)'. *Oxford Dictionary of National Biography*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. [online] Available at: <<http://www.oxforddnb.com/view/article/63882>> [Accessed 22 May 2015].
- Lesta, B. and Petocz, P., 2006. 'Familiar group singing: Addressing mood and social behaviour of residents with dementia displaying sundowning'. In: *Australian Journal of Music Therapy*, 17, pp.2-17.
- Little, J., 2007. 'Gender and geography: Developments in the United Kingdom 1980-2006'. In: *Belgeo*, 3, pp.335-348.
- MacDonald, C., 2010. 'Backandforth', *Remembering Performance Panel*, The Arches, NRLA, Available on Podcast (#2) at: <itunes.apple.com/podcast/new-territories-podcasts/id272928756> [Accessed 25 November 2017].
- Mackay, J.A., 1992. *Burns: a biography of Robert Burns*. Edinburgh: Mainstream Publishing Company.
- Marstine, J., (ed.) 2006. *New Museum Theory and Practice: An Introduction*. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Massey, D., 1994. *Space, Place and Gender*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Massey, D., 2011. *Landscape/space/politics*. [online] Available at: <<http://thefutureoflandscape.wordpress.com/landscapespacepolitics-an-essay>> [Accessed 12 May 2015].
- Massey, D., 2005 [2014]. *For Space*. London: SAGE.
- Melrose, S., 1998. 'What do women want (in theatre)?'. In: Goodman, L. & de Gay, J., (eds.) 1998. *The Routledge Reader in Gender and Performance*. London: Routledge. pp. 131-136.

- Merleau-Ponty, M., 1945 [1962]. *Phenomenology of perception*. New Delhi: Shri Jainendra Press.
- Messner, M.A., Duncan, M.C. & Jensen, K., 1993. 'Separating the men from the girls: The gendered language of televised sports'. In: *Gender & Society*, 7(1), pp.121-137.
- Miller, C. & Swift, K., 1976. *Words and Women: New Language in New Times*. New York: Anchor.
- Mulvey, L., 1975. 'Visual pleasure and narrative cinema'. In: Goodman, L. & de Gay, J., (eds.) 1998. *The Routledge Reader in Gender and Performance*. London: Routledge. pp. 270-275.
- Morgan, R., 1970. *Sisterhood is Powerful: An Anthology of Writings from the Women's Liberation Movement*. New York: Vintage.
- Natter, W. & Jones III, J.P., 1997. 'Identity, Space, and other Uncertainties'. In: Benko, G. & Strohmayr U., (eds.) 1997. *Space & Social Theory*. Oxford: Blackwell Publishers Inc. pp.141-161.
- Nelson, R., (ed.) 2013. *Practice as research in the arts: Principles, protocols, pedagogies, resistances*. Hampshire: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Nicholson, H., 2012. 'The Performance of Memory: Drama, Reminiscence and Autobiography'. In: *NJ*, 36(1), pp.62-74.
- Noddings, N., 1984 [2003]. *Caring: A Feminine Approach to Ethics and Moral Education*. Los Angeles: University of California Press.
- Oakley, A., 1972. *Sex, gender and society*. London: Maurice Temple Smith.
- Oppenheim, J., 1911. *Bread and Roses*. [song] Lyrics available at: <<http://unionsong.com/u159.html>> [Accessed 7 February 2018].
- Overend, D., 2013. 'Making routes: Relational journeys in contemporary performance'. In: *Studies in Theatre and Performance*, 33(3), pp.365-381.
- Paasi, A., 2011. 'The region, identity, and power'. In: *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 14, pp.9-16.
- Parry-Davies, E., 2014. 'Storied Space: Epistemology and Place in the Performance Museum'. In: *Platform: Journal of Theatre and Performing Arts*, 8(1), pp.15-29.
- Pearson, M., 2000. *Bubbling Tom* [performance]. Hibaldstow, Lincolnshire.
- Pearson, M., 2006. *In Comes I: Performance, Memory and Landscape*. Exeter: University of Exeter Press.
- Pearson, M., 2010. *Site-Specific Performance*. Hampshire: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Pearson, M. & Shanks, M., 2001. *Theatre/Archaeology*. Oxon: Routledge.
- Phelan, P., 1993 [2003]. *Unmarked: The politics of performance*. London: Routledge.

Philo, C., 2003. 'To Go Back up the Side Hill': Memories, Imaginations and Reveries of Childhood'. In: *Children's Geographies*, 1(1), pp.7-23.

Rancière, J., 2011. *The Emancipated Spectator*. London: Verso.

Reclaim the Night. *Why reclaim the night?* [online] Available at <<http://www.reclaimthenight.co.uk/why.html>> [Accessed 17 Feb 2016].

Robinson, N., 1999. 'The use of focus group methodology – with selected examples from sexual health research'. In: *Journal of advanced nursing*, 29(4), pp.905-913.

Rogers, M., 2012. 'Contextualizing Theories and Practices of Bricolage Research'. In: *The Qualitative Report*, 17(48), pp.1-17.

Rose, G., 1999. Women and everyday spaces. In: Price, J. & Shildrick, M., (eds.) 1999. *Feminist theory and the body: A reader*. New York: Routledge. pp.359-370.

Saldanha, A., 2013. 'Power-Geometry as Philosophy of Space'. In: Featherstone, D. & Painter, J., (eds.) 2013. *Spatial politics: essays for Doreen Massey*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. pp.44-55.

Schechner, R., 1993. *The future of ritual: writings on culture and performance*. London: Routledge.

Schechner, R., 2003. *Performance Theory*. New York: Routledge.

Schechner, R., 2002 [2013]. *Performance studies: An introduction*. Oxon: Routledge.

Schouten, F.F.J., 1995. 'Heritage as Historical Reality'. In: Herbert, D.T., (ed.) 1995. *Heritage, Tourism and Society*. London: Mansell. pp.21–31.

Sidiropoulou, A., 2011. *Authoring Performance: The Director in Contemporary Theatre*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.

Sleigh-Johnson, S., 2016. 'Performance Waves'. In: *Performance Research*, 21(2), pp. 7-11.

Smith, H. & Dean, R.T., (eds.) 2011. *Practice-led Research, Research-led Practice in the Creative Arts*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.

Smith, L., 2008. 'Heritage, gender, identity'. In: Graham, B.J. & Howard, P., (eds.) 2008. *The Ashgate Research Companion to Heritage and Identity*. Hampshire: Ashgate Publishing Ltd. pp.159-180.

Smith, P., 2009. 'Actors as Signposts: A model for site-based and ambulatory performances'. In: *New Theatre Quarterly*, 25(02), pp.159-171.

Smith, P., 2010. *Mythogeography: A Guide to Walking Sideways*. Axminster: Triarchy.

Smith, P., 2012, *Counter-Tourism: The Handbook*. Axminster: Triarchy.

- Smith, P., 2013. 'Turning Tourists into Performers: Revaluating agency, action and space in sites of heritage tourism'. In: *Performance Research: A Journal of the Performing Arts*, 18(2), pp.102-113.
- Smith, P., 2014. *On Walking*. Devon: Triarchy Press.
- Soja, E., 1980. 'The Socio-Spatial Dialectic'. In: *Annals of the Association of American Geographers*, 70(2), pp.207-225.
- Spender, D., 1980. *Man made language*. London: Routledge & Kegan Paul.
- Stavely-Taylor, C., Stavely Taylor, E. & Stavely-Taylor, J., 2012. *Wisely & Slow*. [song] Performed by The Staves on the album *Dead & Born & Grown*. UK: Atlantic Records.
- Stern, J., 2016. *Virtuous educational research: conversations on ethical practice*. Oxford: Peter Lang.
- Stevenson, C., 2014. 'Memories of Susanne Schaeffer'. In: *Carrick Gazette*, 19 July 2014. [online] Available at: <<http://www.carricktoday.co.uk/news/this-weeks-carrick-gazette-letters-page-1-3478358>> [Accessed 6 December 2016].
- Sullivan, G., 2011. 'Making Space: The Purpose and Place of Practice-led Research'. In: Smith, H. & Dean, R.T., (eds.) 2011. *Practice-led Research, Research-led Practice in the Creative Arts*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press. pp.41-65
- Thomson, P., 2003. 'Practice as research'. In: *Studies in Theatre and Performance*, 22(3), pp.159-180.
- Tivers, J., 2002. 'Performing heritage: the use of live 'actors' in heritage presentations'. In: *Leisure Studies*, 21(3-4), pp.187-200.
- Trad. *Alasdair Òig Mhic 'ic Neacail*. Lyrics available at: <http://www.bbc.co.uk/alba/oran/orain/alasdair_oig_mhic_ic_neacail/> [Accessed 6 February 2018].
- Turner, C., 2004. 'Palimpsest or Potential Space? Finding a Vocabulary for Site-Specific Performance'. In: *New Theatre Quarterly*, 20(4), pp.373-390.
- UNESCO, 2017. *The Criteria for Selection*. [online] Available at: <<http://whc.unesco.org/en/criteria/>> [Accessed 6 November 2017].
- Urry, J., 1995. *Consuming Places*. New York: Routledge.
- Urry, J., 2007. *Mobilities*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Wilkie, F., 2002. 'Kinds of Place at Bore Place: Site-Specific Performance and the Rules of Spatial Behaviour'. In: *New Theatre Quarterly*, 18, pp.243-260.
- Wilkie, F., 2002. 'Mapping the Terrain: a Survey of Site-Specific Performance in Britain'. In: *New Theatre Quarterly*, 18(2), pp.140-160.
- Wilkie, F., 2012. 'Site-specific performance and the mobility turn'. In: *Contemporary Theatre Review*, 22(2), pp.203-212.

Wilkie, F., 2015. *Performance, Transport and Mobility: Making Passage*. Hampshire: Palgrave Macmillan.

Wilson, L.A., 2014. *The Gathering/Yr Helfa* [performance]. Snowdonia, Wales.

Workers' Educational Association Lothian Women's Forum, 2013. *Ethel Moorhead 1869 – 1955*. [online] Available at: <<http://www.latebloomers.co.uk/wforum/ScottishSuffragists/ethelmoorhead.html>> [Accessed 22 May 2015].

Wrights & Sites, 2006. 'A manifesto for a new walking culture: 'dealing with the city''. In: *Performance Research*, 11(2), pp.115-122.

Zerihan, R., 2006. 'Intimate Interactions: Returning to the body in One to One Performance'. In: *Body, Space and Technology*, 6. [online] Available at : <<http://people.brunel.ac.uk/bst/vol0601/rachelzerihan/home.html>> [Accessed 12 November 2017].